

D3.6 - Landscape analysis on the value of RDA Outputs to EOSC

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Abbreviations and Acronyms

AAI	Authentication and Authorisation Infrastructure
CODATA	Committee on Data of the International Science Council
EIF	EOSC Interoperability Framework
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
ERIC	European Research Infrastructure Consortium
ESFRI	European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures
EU	European Union
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
GORC	Global Open Research Commons
HE	Horizon Europe
HEI	Higher Education Institution
IC	EOSC Implementation Challenge
IG	RDA Interest Group
MAR	EOSC Multi-Annual Roadmap
OAEG	EOSC Opportunity Area Expert Group
OS	Open Science
PID	Persistent Identifier
RDA	Research Data Alliance
SC	RDA TIGER Selection Committee
SRIA	EOSC Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda
TAB	RDA Technical Advisory Board
TF	EOSC Association Task Force
WDS	World Data System
WG	RDA Working Group

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Note to reader

This report is structured in three parts:

- **Part A** is an extended executive summary which presents readers with an overview of the report, its main findings and recommendations.
- **Part B** is the main body of the report. It contains sections on the EOSC Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda, European projects, European research infrastructures, and European national Open Science policies; it focuses on the results of the various analyses carried out.
- **Part C** contains appendices relevant to the sections in the main body of the report; these appendices contain further background material, detail on the methodologies and deeper analysis of the results.

PART A: EXTENDED EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

1.1 Overview

This report articulates the value and impact of the Research Data Alliance Groups and their Outputs on the European Open Science landscape and particularly the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) ecosystem. The analysis demonstrates the alignment of RDA outputs with key strategic priorities in Europe and the significant potential for leveraging the RDA platform towards harmonising efforts across the region. This is accomplished by mapping RDA outputs and Group activities to the EOSC Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA), Horizon Europe projects, European Research Infrastructures, and European Union member states' National Open Science policies. The RDA TIGER project is highlighted as a valuable initiative towards focusing and amplifying the work of the global RDA community to address European challenges, facilitating cross-fertilisation between European and international initiatives and being a force multiplier of the impact of RDA in the region.

1.2 Key objectives

This report serves the following purposes:

- Provides a resource for European data professionals and the EOSC stakeholders to help them navigate related RDA WGs and outputs, mapped to corresponding EOSC priorities and challenges;
- Facilitates the implementation of RDA WG activities and outputs to address European challenges by directing the reader to the relevant resources;
- Provides a concrete impact report for the value of RDA to EOSC and the broader European research data landscape (including, for example, Horizon Europe projects, ESFRIs and ERICs) as a result of work carried out by RDA TIGER;
- Analyses the gaps and priorities of the SRIA Implementation Challenges and how the RDA can contribute to the EOSC in the future;
- Articulates the benefits that data professionals from across the European research data landscapes and Member States can gain from engaging with RDA WGs to solve shared research data related challenges.

1.3 Recommendations

RECOMMENDATION A: ACTIVITY ALIGNMENT IN A RICH, MULTI-STAKEHOLDER EUROPEAN ENVIRONMENT

Based on RDA TIGER's effort to socialise the impact of RDA WGs in EOSC and Europe in general, there is a clear need for closer collaboration between RDA, EOSC and other major actors in Europe, working towards a less fragmented environment and removing duplication of effort. The

reuse and sharing of data according to the FAIR principles which underpins EOSC needs to be supported by community-developed and endorsed solutions that are adaptable across boundaries.

RECOMMENDATION B: INTERNATIONAL COOPERATION FOR EUROPEAN SOLUTIONS

Many of the RDA outputs highlighted as potential solutions for EOSC and European-related challenges have been adopted and operationalised by initiatives outside Europe. RDA is not only the venue where these solutions are developed, but can also be the platform where knowledge exchange between EOSC and global counterparts should take place. The relationship should be fostered to allow EOSC to realise its ambition to continue to be competitive in the global data economy, while also cooperating with other international counterparts in a global setting.

RECOMMENDATION C: EOSC ASSOCIATION OPPORTUNITY AREA EXPERT GROUPS, TASK FORCES AND ADOPTED RDA SOLUTIONS

The purview of EOSC Association Opportunity Area Expert Groups and Task Forces is closely linked to the key action areas, priorities, gaps and challenges described throughout the SRIA. As these groups and future iterations continue in their work, newly formed OAEs and TFs should engage with RDA and use this report and the extensive mapping of RDA Working Groups to SRIA Implementation Challenges and MAR General Objectives as an example for the potential available solutions within the RDA community, especially those that have been widely implemented and adopted.

RECOMMENDATION D: RDA TO PLAY INTEGRAL ROLE IN POLICY EVOLUTION AND FAIR COMPLIANCE IN EUROPE

The analysis highlighted cross-cutting concerns of the funding streams (i.e., Scalability, Federation, Policy evolution, FAIR compliance, and Wider user base); it is clear from this that the RDA WGs activities map more strongly onto 'Policy evolution' and 'FAIR compliance'. For future funding calls that address these concerns, a directive can be included by the funder for consortia to engage with suitable RDA WGs and report this dialogue in periodic reports; This alignment will enable projects to identify existing solutions and where possible make connections with those who have adopted or implemented these solutions for insights on how these concerns are being practically addressed.

1.4 The RDA TIGER project

RDA TIGER is the first project designed to provide comprehensive services directly to the RDA community. It builds upon successful predecessors (RDA Europe 3.0, 4.0, and RDA4EOSC) that worked towards animating the European RDA community and supporting the internationalisation of

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EOSC and European solutions. Through the support services provided to carefully selected RDA WGs that directly respond to SRIA, and through the socialisation activities carried out by the project, RDA TIGER strengthened the bridge between the European landscape and the global RDA, ultimately supporting the international engagement and alignment of policies, technologies, methodologies and practices relating to European Open Science developments.

As a culmination of the project's amplification of the role of RDA in Europe, RDA TIGER undertook this large-scale landscape analysis taking a holistic approach to investigating RDA's value to the EOSC ecosystem. The RDA TIGER-supported WGs alignment with EOSC is inherent; in acknowledgment of the existence of EOSC-relevant RDA work outside of the project, this report expanded parts of the analysis beyond RDA TIGER-supported WGs. The value of the RDA TIGER initiative in focusing the work of RDA on European priorities underlines this report.

1.5 RDA, EOSC & the European Open Science Landscape

The Research Data Alliance is a global infrastructure with over 16,000 individual members, 100+ organisational and affiliate members, and 35+ regional networks spanning 152 countries. With more than 50% of membership based in Europe, RDA maintains strong commitment to supporting regional developments, including the EOSC Federation. Both RDA (founded 2013) and EOSC (initiated 2016) emerged as innovative state-of-the-art initiatives not only for Europe but globally. Over the past decade, both have mobilised researchers across domains and geographies to build technical and societal bridges promoting collaboration.

The strategic overlap between RDA and EOSC demonstrates deep integration:

- RDA identified as 'key vehicle in implementing EOSC and coordinating international activity' in EOSC workplan 2019-2020
- 20 organisations are members of both RDA and EOSC Association, with 18 of these based in Europe
- 86% of EOSC Association member or observer organisations house RDA members.
- RDA members actively participate in EOSC governing bodies and projects.

This report, taking into consideration the complementarity of the RDA and EOSC, investigates the value of RDA to the EOSC ecosystem and beyond. RDA's solutions permeate the landscape, often without knowledge of the source. This report intends to enable the broader community to recognise and acknowledge the impact of RDA (current and potential) and to direct those working on EOSC-related challenges to existing resources. As this report will showcase, the European landscape is rich but often complicated and difficult to navigate, leading to fragmentation and duplication of effort; this report will be a useful resource towards further alignment.

EOSC SRIA IMPLEMENTATION CHALLENGES

The Strategic Research & Innovation Agenda

Interactive mapping
Kumu visualisation

SCOPE - RDA Working Group activities flowing into EOSC implementation

Articulation of the activities of existing and completed RDA Working Groups that align with and contribute to the Implementation Challenges defined in the EOSC Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA).

The EOSC SRIA defines seven Implementation Challenges, representing the core technical challenges and prerequisites for building and operationalising the EOSC ecosystem.

IMPLEMENTATION CHALLENGES AND SELECTED RELATED WORKING GROUPS

CONCLUSIONS

- Multiple RDA WG activities are relevant to all **seven Implementation Challenges**
- ‘**Metadata and ontologies**’ and ‘**Resource provider environments**’ are the challenges most commonly addressed by RDA WGs (26 each), followed closely by the ‘**EOSC Interoperability Framework**’ (24).
- **Multiple direct references to the RDA outputs** that could be or have already been implemented in addressing the concerns, gaps and priorities of the SRIA.
- RDA activities can support the embedding of **FAIR practices, improve interoperability and reinforce existing collaborations**, demonstrating the value of how globally coordinated, community-driven standards can meaningfully advance the next stages of EOSC development

MAPPING between Implementation Challenges and RDA Working Groups consisted of desk-based research, focused on close reading of Working Group documentation and SRIA document.

1.6 Mapping RDA WG activities to EOSC strategic priorities

The analysis in this section of the report focuses on the relevance of RDA WG outputs and activities to two specific aspects of the EOSC Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA), namely the SRIA's **seven Implementation Challenges** and the **three General Objectives** (2025-2027) of the Multi-Annual Roadmap (MAR). The methodology for this consisted primarily of desk-based research; the focus areas of each WG were examined and associated with the features of the Implementation Challenges and General Objectives where relevant.

[Mapping Research Data Alliance Working Groups to the SRIA Implementation Challenges](#)

SRIA Implementation Challenges

- RDA WGs address the **Identifiers** Implementation Challenge by reducing fragmentation and improving standardisation of persistent identifiers through interoperable frameworks, guided by core information types and PID policies. The work of the [PID Information Types WG](#) and [National PID Strategies WG](#) are of relevance here.
- RDA WGs address the **Metadata and Ontologies** Implementation Challenge by aligning metadata standards and semantic artefacts across domains, enabling discovery, reuse, and cross-disciplinary mapping. The work of [Metadata Standards Catalog WG](#), the [FAIRsharing Registry WG](#), and the [RDA FAIR Mappings WG](#) are of relevance here.
- RDA WGs address the **FAIR Metrics and Certification** Implementation Challenge by operationalising FAIR principles, providing shared assessment metrics, and aligning repository certification criteria to sustain FAIRness. The work of [FAIR Data Maturity Model \(FDMM\) WG](#), the [RDA/WDS TRUST Principles Outreach and Adoption Working Group](#), and the [Community-based catalogue of requirements for trustworthy Technical Repository Service Providers Working Group \(TRSPs WG\)](#) are of relevance here.
- RDA WGs address the **Authentication and Authorisation Infrastructure (AAI)** Implementation Challenge by providing technology-neutral frameworks that recognise AAI as a core component of global research infrastructures. The work of both the [GORC International Model WG](#) and [GORC International Implementations WG](#) are of relevance here.
- RDA WGs address the **User Environments** Implementation Challenge by enhancing access to EOSC resources, promoting FAIR adoption in virtual research environments, and improving usability of digital research tools. The work of the [FAIR for Virtual Research Environments WG](#) and the [RDA-OfR Mapping the landscape of digital research tools \(MaLDReTH\) WG](#) are of relevance here.

- RDA WGs address the **Resource Provider Environments** Implementation Challenge by improving interoperability and alignment of heterogeneous resources, supporting cross-repository integration, data granularity, and FAIR-by-design approaches. The work of The [Research Data Repository Interoperability WG](#), [Data Granularity WG](#), and [Scientific Knowledge Graphs - Interoperability Framework \(SKG-IF\) WG](#) are of relevance here.
- RDA WGs address the **EOSC Interoperability Framework** Implementation Challenge by delivering solutions across technical, semantic, and organisational layers, harmonising metadata standards and repository frameworks, and strengthening organisational interoperability through certification and assessment. The [Data Granularity WG](#), [Multi-Omics Metadata Standards Integration \(MOMSI\) WG](#), and [Community-based catalogue of requirements for trustworthy Technical Repository Service Providers Working Group \(TRSPs WG\)](#) are of relevance here.

MAR General Objectives

- **General Objective 1:** Ensure that Open Science practices and skills are rewarded and taught, becoming the ‘new normal’: All RDA WGs in some way directly or indirectly contribute to the implementation of Open Science practices in research. WGs of relevance identified here are [RDA/CODATA Summer Schools in Data Science and Cloud Computing in the Developing World WG](#) and [WDS/RDA Assessment of Data Fitness for Use WG](#).
- **General Objective 2:** There is a large degree of overlap between this General Objective and the requirement for RDA WGs’ “overarching goal of increasing data-driven innovation” and “to promote data sharing and exchange”. WGs of relevance identified here are [FAIRsharing Registry WG](#), [CoreTrustSeal Maintenance WG](#), and [RDA / CODATA Data Systems, Tools, and Services for Crisis Situations WG](#)
- **General Objective 3:** This is a wide-ranging objective, with much of the relevant RDA WG work focused on the Objective’s associated European, national and organisational levels. WGs of relevance identified here are [Alignment of multilingual vocabularies in the Social Sciences and Humanities WG](#) and [GORC International Implementations Working Group \(GORC II WG\)](#).

The analysis shows that RDA WG work contributes significantly to addressing Implementation Challenges and Multi-Annual Roadmap General Objectives. These globally coordinated, community-driven outputs demonstrate how RDA activities can support the embedding of FAIR practices, improve interoperability and reinforce existing collaborations, ultimately contributing to the development of EOSC.

SCOPE - Mapping Open & Shared Data Practices in Horizon Europe

RDA Working Groups structuring and sustaining the data ecosystem

Methodology: Two-Step Approach

STEP 1 Identify Projects

Identify Horizon Europe projects focusing on open and shared data practices.

STEP 2 Define Mapping Criteria

Define a set of criteria to map Horizon Europe projects with RDA Working Groups (WGs) activities.

- 1. Scalability** Sustainable and scalable access channels ensuring long-term operation of infrastructures.
- 2. Federation** Effective federation of European, national, regional, and institutional resources.
- 3. Policy Evolution** Technical and policy evolution addressing emerging needs, including sensitive data and privacy-by-design.
- 4. FAIR Compliance** Data interoperability and compliance with the FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable).
- 5. Wide User Base** Support for a broad and diverse community of researchers and stakeholders.

HORIZON EUROPE PROGRAMMES

INFRAEOSC Calls

- Address all five criteria
- Strong focus on:
 - Scalability
 - Federation
- High alignment with RDA WGs activities

ERA-OS Calls

- Address two criteria:
 - Policy Evolution
 - Wide User Base
- Limited coverage of technical and infrastructure-oriented criteria

MAPPING RESULTS

RDA WGs and INFRAEOSC projects show broad coverage across all criteria

ERA projects focus mainly on policy-driven aspects

RDA WGs place strong emphasis on FAIR compliance

INFRAEOSC projects emphasize scalability

ERA projects emphasize policy evolution

CONCLUSIONS

RDA WGs activities cover all five open and shared data criteria

The RDA framework is closer to INFRAEOSC projects than to ERA projects

Future INFRAEOSC projects will increasingly focus on federation and wider use

Future ERA projects will primarily focus on policy evolution

RDA WGs represent a valuable reservoir of expertise and guidance for collaboration with current and future Horizon Europe projects

FUTURE TRENDS

Next EOSC Development Phase

- Shift toward an operational phase
- Increased focus on:
 - Federation
 - Wider user base

Future ERA Policy Agenda

- Focus on:
 - Equity
 - Artificial Intelligence
 - Security
 - Assessment of research and data sharing practices

These aspects are mainly addressed through policy evolution

1.7 RDA alignment to the Horizon Europe-funded projects landscape

The report provides a detailed categorisation of 73 Open Science-related Horizon Europe-funded projects across multiple topic areas including data management, skills development, FAIR implementation, research assessment, and policy implementation. Key findings demonstrate that while the RDA working groups map most strongly to concerns related to 'Policy evolution' and 'FAIR compliance', its activity domains are aligned within the European funding landscape. This positioning identifies RDA as a critical partner for addressing cross-cutting challenges in scalability, federation, and user base expansion that span multiple funding streams.

[Mapping Research Data Alliance Working Groups to HE-funded projects](#)

Regarding the two main activity domains, there are several RDA TIGER-supported WGs whose activity is of relevance here: for the 'Policy evolution' activity domain the work of the [Ethics in Agricultural Data WG](#) and the [EOSC-Future/RDA Artificial Intelligence & Data Visitation WG](#) is highlighted in the analysis and results described in Part B of this report; for 'FAIR compliance', the [FAIR Mappings WG](#) and the [Wind Energy Community Standards WG](#) is applicable from domain-agnostic and domain-specific perspectives respectively.

This analysis finds that the RDA community and specifically its WGs are concerned with the activities related to the development and implementation of EOSC and OS practically, and that they also produce (and will continue to produce) outputs that have the potential to be directly implementable by both current projects and future projects.

SCOPE - Map RDA TIGER supported RDA WGs onto ESFRI Landscape Report and the current ERICs

- **Strong alignment** exists between the scope and (planned) outputs of RDA TIGER WGs and ERIC activity areas
- **Discipline-agnostic RDA WGs** addressing access management and licensing, search and discovery, and ingest and appraisal produce outputs relevant to most ERICs
- **More specialised, technology-focused RDA WGs** are relevant to cross-disciplinary subsets of ERICs based on specific activity areas or methodological approaches
- **Several RDA TIGER-supported RDA WGs** address domain-specific challenges related to the implementation of FAIR and CARE Principles and are therefore relevant to particular ERICs

Only two RDA TIGER-supported RDA WGs—RDA Wind Energy Community Standards WG and RDA/ReSA Policies in Research Organisations for Research Software (PRO4RS) WG—could not be mapped to ERICs using the technology-focus taxonomy

CONCLUSIONS

- **Mapping RDA TIGER-supported RDA WGs** to the ERIC landscape and the ESFRI Roadmap shows strong alignment in technology focus
- **Most RDA TIGER-supported WGs** produce outputs relevant to the wider ESFRI landscape
- **As ESFRI becomes more complex**, cross-disciplinary, and globally connected, RDA provides a valuable, global, community-based forum to address ESFRI data-related challenges
- **Experts from ERICs and the broader ESFRI landscape** already contribute to RDA WGs, demonstrating existing engagement
- The mapping reveals significant potential for **deeper collaboration** between the RDA community and ERICs
- **Wider adoption** of RDA Recommendations and Outputs could further benefit ESFRIs, as formal adoption currently remains limited

RESULTS OF ESFRI LANDSCAPE MAPPING

RDA TIGER supported WGs respond to ESFRI landscape challenges related to:

- **An organisational challenge** related to the development of a working EOSC ecosystem in Europe and expected consolidation of generic and thematic e-infrastructure service provisioning and federation of institutional and national services at European level
- **RIs** as both key providers of data and services to EOSC, as well as the key consumers of EOSC services
- **Data standardisation and harmonisation** in thematic RIs
- **Ethical and legal considerations, Big Data and AI**, and data management and stewardship in and across thematic RIs

1.8 RDA alignment to ESFRIs and ERICs

The analysis examines relationships between RDA TIGER-supported working groups and the **30 European Research Infrastructure Consortia (ERICs)** alongside the ESFRI Roadmap 2021. ERICs represent major investments in research infrastructure across domains including energy, environment, health, physical sciences, social sciences, and digital technologies. Research infrastructures face common data management challenges including interoperability, long-term preservation, access policies, and FAIR data implementation. RDA working groups provide domain-agnostic solutions addressing these challenges, whilst maintaining flexibility for domain-specific adaptation.

[Mapping Research Data Alliance Working Groups to European Research Infrastructures](#)

The analysis reveals a close overlap in the technology focus on RDA TIGER-supported RDA WGs and ERICs; in parallel, most RDA TIGER supported RDA WGs develop outputs that are of relevance also to the extended ESFRI landscape. As the ESFRI landscape becomes more complex, more cross-disciplinary, and more globally engaged, RDA as a global, community-based organisation can provide a forum where to develop solutions to the data-related challenges ESFRIs face. A number of experts from ERICs, and the broader ESFRI landscape, already actively contribute to the activities of RDA WGs. However, formal adoption remains limited, with only one documented adoption story in the RDA catalogue from CLARIN-ERIC, suggesting significant opportunity for increased engagement and knowledge exchange.

NATIONAL OPEN SCIENCE POLICIES

Interactive mapping
Kumu visualisation

The report examines Open Science policies across 27 European countries using adapted FOSTER Open Science taxonomy. This systematic approach enables identification of policy strengths, gaps, and opportunities for RDA Working and Interest Group engagement. The analysis maps both RDA groups and national policies to common taxonomy categories, revealing alignment patterns and opportunities.

RDA Working Groups provide practical implementation pathways for existing policy strengths:

FOR REPOSITORY SYSTEMS:

- Data Repository Attributes Working Group defines essential characteristics and quality indicators
- RDA/WDS Certification of Digital Repositories Interest Group establishes trust frameworks

FOR OPEN ACCESS POLICIES:

- Research Data Policy Interest Group provides frameworks for policy development
- Research Funders and Stakeholders Interest Group coordinates mandates and incentives

FOR RESEARCH DATA MANAGEMENT:

- DMP Common Standards Working Group creates standardised formats for data management plans
- Active Data Management Plans Interest Group develops frameworks for dynamic, machine-actionable planning

FOR DATA SHARING:

- Data Citation Working Group establishes citation standards
- FAIR Data Maturity Model Working Group provides assessment frameworks

FOR DATA STANDARDS:

- FAIRsharing Registry maintains connections between policies, standards, and repositories
- Data Foundation and Terminology Working Group provides technical vocabularies
- For emerging domains, RDA provides established frameworks that forward-thinking countries could incorporate into policy:

FOR OPEN SOURCE HARDWARE:

- FAIR Principles for Research Hardware Interest Group offers frameworks for making hardware designs findable and accessible
- Persistent Identification of Instruments Working Group provides identification systems

FOR COLLABORATIVE REVIEW:

- Evaluation of Research Interest Group develops perspectives on alternative assessment methods
- SHARC Interest Group creates recognition systems incentivising transparent peer review

FOR REPRODUCIBILITY TOOLS:

- FAIR for Research Software Working Group provides principles for computational reproducibility
- RDA Reproducibility Checklist Working Group develops systematic evaluation tools
- Data Versioning Interest Group and Research Data Provenance Interest Group offer technical standards

FOR ALTERNATIVE METRICS:

- Data Citation Working Group enables new forms of impact measurement
- Data Usage Metrics Working Group develops metrics for measuring research data usage and impact
- SHARC Interest Group provides recognition systems for broader research activities

FOR OPEN EDUCATIONAL RESOURCES:

- Education and Training on Handling of Research Data Interest Group develops comprehensive curricula
- FAIR for Virtual Research Environments Working Group creates technical standards for collaborative learning infrastructure

1.9 RDA support for policy implementation

The report examines Open Science policies across **27 European countries** using adapted FOSTER Open Science taxonomy. The analysis maps both RDA Working and Interest Groups and national policies to common taxonomy categories, revealing alignment patterns and opportunities.

[Mapping Research Data Alliance Groups to European National Open Science Policies: A Taxonomy-based Analysis](#)

The report highlights areas where the RDA Working and Interest Groups can support *existing policy implementation*:

Repository Systems

- The [Data Repository Attributes Working Group](#) defines essential characteristics of data repositories.
- The [RDA/WDS Certification of Digital Repositories Interest Group](#) examines the repository certification ecosystem.

Open Access Policies

- The [Research Data Policy Interest Group](#) provides frameworks for policy development.
- The [Research Funders and Stakeholders on Open Research and Data Management Policies and Practices IG](#) provides guidelines for incentivising Open Science.

Research Data Management

- The [DMP Common Standards Working Group](#) creates standardised formats for data management plans.
- The [Active Data Management Plans Interest Group](#) develops frameworks for dynamic, machine-actionable data management plans (DMPS).

Data Sharing

- [Data Citation Working Group](#) sets guidelines and recommendations for data citation practices.
- [FAIR Data Maturity Model Working Group](#) provides assessment frameworks for FAIRness.

Data Standards

- [FAIRsharing Registry WG](#) maintains connections between policies, standards, and repositories.
- [Data Foundation and Terminology Working Group](#) has developed a reference data terminology for use across disciplines.

The analysis also identifies *gaps and opportunities for emerging policy priorities*:

- **Open Source Hardware:** Absent from national policies despite growing community adoption
- **Collaborative Review:** Minimal policy coverage for transparent peer review approaches
- **Real-time Documentation and Review Transparency:** Limited national policy coverage
- **Reproducibility Tools:** Early recognition but limited systematic policy frameworks
- **Alternative Metrics:** Growing acknowledgement of need beyond traditional citation metrics
- **Open Educational Resources:** Limited policy coverage despite pedagogical value

The RDA offers immediate opportunities to strengthen and advance European national Open Science policies through its community-developed frameworks and outputs. Countries can prioritise adopting RDA approaches to reproducibility, open peer review, education, data management, and repository systems to address policy gaps, while benefiting from cross-cutting work on research evaluation and credit that supports alternative assessment models and helps integrate emerging research practices into national Open Science strategies.

1.10 Community insights

The RDA TIGER project carried out a number of events in support of this report, aiming to gather broader community perspectives. These activities complemented the analyses conducted for this report by leveraging the existing strengths of the global RDA community and incorporating both Europe-focused and international contributions to ensure that the insights informing this report reflect diverse regional and disciplinary contexts. Activities focused on cross-fertilisation workshops between RDA TIGER-supported WGs and also HE-funded projects EDEN and FIDELIS, community consultations at RDA Plenaries and multiple breakout sessions at the RDA in Europe Summit.

A common thread across all community engagement activities carried out was the need to bring together the currently fragmented European landscape: **Greater harmonisation of community-developed outputs in the Open Data and Open Science ecosystems, increased dialogue between different communities who are working on shared or similar issues, and practical and active coordination of efforts taking place at the European, disciplinary, organisational and sometimes individual levels.**

There is a clear opportunity to strategically leverage the RDA community and outputs as a common reference point for aligning practices, stimulating dialogue between communities, and coordinating implementation activities; doing so can be the next step towards addressing the fragmentation in the landscape described in the SRIA, thus enhancing interoperability and subsequent uptake of these shared solutions.

1.11 Conclusion

This report shows that the RDA, strengthened by targeted support through the RDA TIGER project, is a key contributor to EOSC and the wider European research ecosystem. By aligning globally developed, community-driven solutions with European priorities, RDA addresses technical, organisational, and social challenges underpinning Open Science in Europe, providing outputs that can be readily implemented within EOSC.

The analysis highlights RDA's role as both a source of robust technical and policy solutions and a platform for international knowledge exchange, with many outputs already adopted beyond Europe. It also underscores RDA's strong contribution to policy evolution and FAIR compliance. Closer alignment between RDA, EOSC bodies, and European initiatives can reduce fragmentation, promote reuse of solutions, and accelerate progress towards a more coherent and sustainable EOSC ecosystem.

PART B: LANDSCAPE ANALYSIS RESULTS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

1. Introduction

A key aim of the RDA TIGER project is to maximise the impact that RDA WG results have on the EOSC, global OS, and society. This report articulates the value and impact of the work done by the RDA TIGER consortium throughout the project lifetime, building on the efforts of the wider RDA community since the organisation's inception in 2013, on the overall European landscape and EOSC. Specifically, this deliverable:

- Serves as a resource for the European data professionals and the EOSC users to help them navigate related RDA WGs and Outputs, mapped to corresponding EOSC priorities and challenges;
- Facilitates the implementation of RDA WG activities and outputs to address European challenges by directing the reader to the relevant resources;
- Provides a concrete impact report for the value of RDA to EOSC and the broader European research data landscape (including e.g. ESFRIs and ERICs) as a result of work carried out by RDA TIGER;
- Analyses gaps and priorities relating to the SRIA Implementation Challenges, and how the RDA can contribute to the EOSC in the future;
- Articulates the benefits that data professionals from across the European research data landscapes and Member States can gain from engaging with RDA WGs to solve common research data related challenges.

The motivation for this report arose in part due to the success of the RDA TIGER project's delivery of support services to RDA Working Groups (WGs). Overall, the project has exceeded its goals with respect to the number of WGs supported via in-kind services and financial support, and the desired threshold for positive feedback on the services.¹ Beyond this significant achievement of measurable impact to the work of RDA overall, it is also clear that the RDA TIGER project, through its supported WGs, has consequently made a significant contribution to the overall European landscape, and the EOSC ecosystem in particular.

¹ For example, the project has supported 23 WGs compared to its target of 14, and has exceeded its target of receiving 95% positive feedback. See O'Connor, R., GRAU, N., Saldner, S., Minichiello, F., Lehtsalu, L., & Delipalta, A. (2025). RDA TIGER D6.5: Final quality evaluation report on the RDA TIGER WG services. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17877446>

One of the criteria by which RDA TIGER selected its supported WGs (or WG-related projects) is the extent to which the planned activities and outputs impact the European data sharing and general Open Science landscape, with a focus on EOSC and the Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA). Given RDA's global and multi-disciplinary nature, and its mission to enable the research data communities to address challenges to data sharing, exchange, and interoperability, RDA Groups and Outputs in general have had considerable influence on European activities throughout the years (see section 3 RDA & EOSC below). This leveraging of the RDA as a valuable forum for developing solutions, in combination with the specific focus placed by RDA TIGER on providing support to activities that contribute directly to the SRIA, has led to a rich portfolio of TIGER-supported WGs, all of which have an impact on the European landscape.

Not only are there demonstrable overlaps and complementarities in the concerns and activities of RDA TIGER-supported WGs and specific EOSC-related initiatives, this report also describes how there has already been significant uptake and implementation of RDA outputs within the EOSC ecosystem, demonstrating the value of the bottom-up, solution oriented work carried out by the RDA community at large, which is enhanced by the targeted support provided by the RDA TIGER project.

1.1 Note on methodology

In order to analyse how RDA groups relate to selected policy and thematic areas this report, specifically sections 4, 5, 6, and 7 below, adopts a qualitative rather than strictly reproducible approach. Each section has separate methodological strands as different selections of RDA Groups (e.g., all RDA Working Groups, RDA TIGER-supported WGs, RDA IGs and WGs, etc.) were analysed with respect to different aspects of the European research data landscape. Due to the homogeneity of the latter, this mixed approach allowed the authors to examine how aspects of the work done within RDA can be or have been impactful in a European context. Tools such as [Kumu.io](https://kumu.io) and MS Excel graphs are used to describe and visualise the analyses throughout the report, again employed based on where each approach is appropriate.

2. Setting the Scene

2.1 EOSC & RDA

The RDA is a global, community-based infrastructure with more than 16,000 individual members, 100+ organisational and affiliate members, and over 35 regional networks covering 152 countries. With over 50% of RDA's membership being based in Europe, the RDA maintains its commitment to support developments in the region, including those surrounding the emerging EOSC Federation, in

particular considering the inherent strategic complementarity between the goals of the RDA and the overall EOSC initiative towards making research data FAIR and advancing Open Science in Europe.

The RDA was founded in 2013 (with the idea having been conceived in 2012), with EOSC following in 2016 (with the initial idea in 2015); the two initiatives were innovative and state of the art not only for European standards, but also on the global stage. In the last decade, both the RDA and EOSC have mobilised researchers across domains and geographies to build technical and societal bridges to promote and enhance collaboration. Through different but complementary means, both the RDA and EOSC have helped to turn a new page for research by facilitating practices and solutions that enable the use and re-use of data, facilitating interdisciplinary research, and providing the technical and social infrastructure that supports these objectives.

Europe remains a front-runner in the field of research and development. EOSC governance bodies and in particular EOSC-related projects include individuals who have worked within the RDA with different Working and Interest Groups, or as part of RDA's Governance. As part of the EOSC workplan 2019 - 2020, the RDA was identified as a "key vehicle in implementing the EOSC and coordinating international activity"². In 2020 a report produced by the EC-funded project RDA Europe 4.0³ identified that RDA members have been active across EOSC-related groups and initiatives from early on, from EOSC governing bodies to EOSC-related projects. At the time of writing in 2025 and as this report intends to showcase, the European RDA membership continues to actively participate in the developments surrounding the EOSC Federation and EOSC Nodes, as a natural result of our common vision, strategy and interests. The RDA community plays a key role in shaping this significant next step towards Open Science in Europe, given our long-standing expertise in building technical and social bridges and adoptable solutions. The RDA community's interests and work permeate the EOSC-related activities in Europe, as still evident by the overlap across our membership with that of the EOSC Association. At the organisational level, across the 100 organisational and affiliate members of the RDA globally, 20 are shared with the membership of the EOSC Association, 18 of which are European members. 86% of the EOSC-A member or observer organisations are home to members of RDA. Most importantly, the convergence between the two communities extends to the creation of solutions at the centre of EOSC priority list and challenges, a fact that has driven the RDA TIGER team to create this report.

² *European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) work plan 2019-2020*, Publications Office, 2019, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/972843>

³ Bangert, D., Fava, I., O'Connor, R., Jones, S., Delipalta, A., Garavelli, S., & Biro, T. (2020). Report on RDA integration with other European initiatives (v1.0_draft). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3630265>

2.2 The RDA TIGER Project

RDA TIGER, though the first project of its kind, comes after a series of successful projects aligning the RDA and the EOSC. RDA Europe 3.0 and 4.0 worked towards animating the European RDA community. RDA4EOSC^{4,5} was funded through an EOSC Secretariat Co-creation grant and aimed to support the internationalisation and implementation of the EOSC by leveraging the strengths and network of the Research Data Alliance.

The RDA TIGER project designed and provided a suite of support services that aimed to streamline and facilitate the operations of RDA WGs, ultimately enabling the production of high quality, globally created solutions that address European strategic priorities in the field of Open Science. The services were provided to carefully selected RDA WGs based on specific criteria that consider their demonstrable alignment with the SRIA, thus supporting the development of RDA outputs that can be directly leveraged by the EOSC Partnership.

Through the support services and also the socialisation activities carried out by the project, we aimed to strengthen the bridge between the European landscape and the global RDA, and ultimately supporting the international engagement and alignment of policies, technologies, methodologies, practices and other outputs relating to EOSC and European Open Science developments.

The alignment of RDA TIGER-supported WGs with EOSC is inherent, given the scope of the project. In acknowledgment of the resource and time limitations of projects of this nature which meant that RDA TIGER could not support the whole of the RDA community, and of the fact that RDA work outside of RDA TIGER exists that is of relevance and value to the European landscape, this report expanded parts of the analysis to the entirety of the RDA WGs, and in some cases Interest Groups (IGs). The RDA TIGER project's impact in Europe through its supported WGs, the community engagement activities, streamlining efforts and the dedication to showcase the value of RDA in the region underline this report.

This document, taking into consideration all of the above, therefore takes a holistic approach and investigates the value of RDA to the EOSC ecosystem and beyond. RDA's solutions permeate the landscape, often without knowledge of the source. This report intends to enable the broader community to recognise and acknowledge the impact of RDA (current and potential) and to direct those working on EOSC-related challenges to existing resources. As this report will showcase, the European landscape is rich and often complicated and hard to navigate, leading to fragmentation and duplication of effort. This report will be a useful resource towards further alignment.

⁴ <https://archive.rd-alliance.org/rda4eosc>

⁵ <https://archive.rd-alliance.org/rda4eosc-researchcommunities>

3. EOSC Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda

Following on from how the RDA TIGER project is described above with respect to the wider European landscape, this section describes the significant shared areas of concern of the RDA community and the EOSC, detailing the WG outputs (RDA-endorsed Recommendations and Supporting Outputs) which can be utilised to address aspects of the EOSC Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda version 1.3^{6,7}. Specifically, the seven Action Area Implementation Challenges are examined in the context of the focus areas of current and completed RDA WGs. Where relevant, areas where there is comparatively less commonalities between the concerns of the RDA WGs and SRIA Action Areas are noted, with possible explanations for each provided. Later in this section, a further analysis is done in relation to the SRIA Multi-Annual Roadmap (MAR) General Objectives. See Annex 1 in Part 3 of this report for a description of the methodology and where applicable, further background information on aspects of the SRIA and analysis of the specific relevance of RDA WGs.

3.1. SRIA Implementation Challenges

The EOSC Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA) describes in detail 14 Action Areas where attention is needed in order to develop the EOSC ecosystem. These are divided into two broad categories: Implementation Challenges and Boundary Conditions, each with seven Action Areas. There are several working groups within the RDA that address the second category, the Boundary Challenges, for example, the [RDA Data Steward Career Tracks WG](#), which emerged through collaboration between RDA and EOSC Association Task Force to address the Skills & Training/Rewards & Recognition Boundary Condition, and the [Ethics in Agricultural Data WG](#), which engages those academic, commercial and producers involved in agriculture and addresses the ‘Widening to public and private sectors and going global’ Boundary Challenge⁸.

That being said, this report focuses on the Implementation Challenges. The RDA TIGER Grant Agreement requires that the project “directly contribute to the European Open Science Cloud Partnership, by supporting (via the Working Groups) the international engagement and alignment of

⁶ Horizon Europe Co-programmed Partnership for the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). (2024). Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA) of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) (v1.3, 2024) (1.3). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17582648>; hereafter, this version of the SRIA is referenced in footnotes as “SRIA”, along with the page number quoted.

⁷ At the time of publication of this deliverable, a public consultation is underway for SRIA 2.0. Though this new version of the SRIA may present changes to EOSC priorities or approaches to its development, it is the expectation of the authors of this deliverable that the relationship and collaborations between RDA and EOSC stakeholders will continue into this new phase and that the findings of this report will remain a valuable resource in supporting these.

⁸ The seven Boundary Conditions are Rules of Participation; Landscape monitoring; Business models; Skills and training; Rewards and recognition; Communication; Widening to public and private sectors and going global.

policies, technologies, methodologies, practices and other outputs of EOSC-related and other European Open Science developments”; for this report, the decision was made that focusing on the Implementation Challenges as described in the SRIA, i.e., the primary technical challenges and prerequisites to deploying EOSC, is more in line with the RDA TIGER mission.

The seven Implementation Challenges described in the SRIA are:

- Identifiers;
- Metadata and ontologies;
- FAIR metrics and certification;
- Authentication and authorisation infrastructure;
- User environments;
- Resource provider environments;
- EOSC Interoperability Framework.

In this section, the report looks in detail at how the activity of RDA WGs aligns with efforts to address the Implementation Challenges; first, by looking at the overall relevance of RDA WG activities to the Implementation Challenges, then by providing a more detailed analysis at each Implementation Challenge by highlighting the outputs which WGs have produced that address the gaps and priorities of each, as outlined in the SRIA.

The report examines each individual Implementation Challenge and demonstrates how RDA WG activities and outputs can support efforts to address the gaps and priorities of each. In order to represent the richness of the relationships between RDA WGs and the SRIA Implementation Challenges, a mapping using the [Kumu.io](https://kumu.io), an online platform for creating interactive visual representations of mappings. The overall mapping can be seen below in Figure 1; following the link below will allow the reader to access the mapping directly:

[Mapping Research Data Alliance Working Groups to the SRIA Implementation Challenges](#)

Figure 1. Kumu map representing mapping of RDA WGs to SRIA Implementation Challenges

3.1.1. Identifiers

As is described in SRIA section 5.1.2, there is widespread uptake of PIDs, but emerging technologies and research types have resulted in fragmentation of systems and an unstandardised approach to the development of PID infrastructures. There is a total of nine RDA WGs whose work is of relevance to the ‘Identifiers’ Implementation Challenge. Of these, eight have produced their final Recommendations, with the remaining WG (i.e., [Coordinating Earth, Space, and Environmental Science Data Preservation and Scholarly Publication Processes WG](#)) in the process of producing its outputs. As a result, there is significant relevant work in place which can directly support efforts to address the gaps and priorities outlined in the SRIA in relation to the ‘Identifiers’ challenge. Table 1 below shows the RDA WGs whose work is of relevance to this Implementation Challenge.

Table 1. RDA Working Groups relevant to ‘Identifiers’ SRIA Implementation Challenge

Complex Citations Working Group
Coordinating Earth, Space, and Environmental Science Data Preservation and Scholarly Publication Processes WG
Data Citation WG

RDA TIGER “Research Data Alliance facilitation of Targeted International working Groups for EOSC-related Research solutions” is funded by HORIZON-INFRA-2022-EOSC-0, Project:101094406.

Data Type Registries WG
National PID Strategies WG*
Persistent Identification of Instruments WG
PID Information Types WG
RDA/FORCE11 Software Source Code Identification WG
Research Data Collections WG

*RDA TIGER-supported Working Group

From the analysis conducted the following were the principle WGs identified whose work and outputs are of relevance to Identifiers Implementation Challenge:

- The [PID Information Types \(PIT\) WG](#) has produced an endorsed RDA Recommendation that detailed the “essential types of information associated with persistent identifiers”⁹;
- The [Persistent Identification of Instruments WG](#) has published two outputs focused on developing an identifier system for instruments used for measuring in scientific research.

Further to this, RDA TIGER has funded through its Cascade Grant process a project from the National Open Research Forum in the Republic of Ireland. This project is aiming to implement the Recommendations of the [RDA National PID Strategies Working Group](#) in order to develop the country’s existing national PID strategy and bring it further in line with the EOSC PID policy.

3.1.2. Metadata and ontologies

As noted in the SRIA, metadata and ontologies are foundational to the EOSC. However, “to date an overarching, coordinated approach to metadata and ontologies for scholarly resources has for the most part been missing”¹⁰. The challenge lies not only in the development of high-quality metadata and semantic artefacts, but also in the alignment and coordination of these efforts across disciplines, domains, and infrastructures. Table 2 below shows the RDA WGs whose work is of relevance to this Implementation Challenge.

Table 2. RDA Working Groups relevant to ‘Metadata and ontologies’ SRIA Implementation Challenge

Alignment of multilingual vocabularies in the Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) WG*
Building Immune Digital Twins WG*

⁹ Weigel, T., DiLauro, T., & Zastrow, T. (2015). PID Information Types WG final deliverable. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.15497/FDAA09D5-5ED0-403D-B97A-2675E1EBE786>

¹⁰ SRIA, p.89

CURE-FAIR WG
Data Foundation and Terminology WG
Data Type Registries WG
Discipline-specific Guidance for Data Management Plans WG
DMP Common Standards WG
FAIR Mappings WG*
FAIRification of Genomic Annotations WG*
FAIRsharing Registry: Connecting data policies, standards and databases RDA WG
Harmonised terminologies and schemas for FAIR data in materials science and related domains WG*
I-ADOPT WG*
International Materials Resource Registries WG
Metadata Standards Catalog WG
Metadata Standards Directory WG
Multi-omics Metadata Standards Integration (MOMSI) WG*
Persistent Identification of Instruments WG
RDA / TDWG Metadata Standards for attribution of physical and digital collections stewardship
Research Metadata Schemas WG
Sample Type Classification WG
Small Uncrewed Aircraft and Autonomous Platforms Data WG*
WDS/RDA Assessment of Data Fitness for Use WG
Wheat Data Interoperability WG
Wind Energy Community Standards WG*

*RDA TIGER-supported Working Group

A total of 24 RDA WGs have been identified as directly relevant to the Metadata and Ontologies Implementation Challenge, evenly split between completed and active groups. These WGs address the Implementation Challenge from multiple angles. At the cross-domain level, several WGs have focused on developing high-level metadata standards and schemas to enable interoperability, the

RDA TIGER “Research Data Alliance facilitation of Targeted International working Groups for EOSC-related Research solutions” is funded by HORIZON-INFRA-2022-EOSC-0, Project:101094406.

creation of methods for mapping and aligning semantic artefacts, and the development of searchable catalogues and registries that can be used to identify existing metadata standards and ontologies. At the same time, there is a strong presence of domain-specific WGs working on metadata and ontological guidance in areas such as wind energy, materials science, agricultural science, and the social sciences and humanities, addressing this required aspect of the Implementation Challenge.

From the analysis the following were the principle WGs identified whose work and outputs are of relevance to the Metadata and Ontologies Implementation Challenge, grouped by completed WGs (i.e., those which have produced Recommendations) and ongoing WGs.

- Completed WGs:
 - The [Metadata Standards Catalog WG](#) has produced a searchable, curated registry of metadata standards intended to assist researchers and infrastructure providers in selecting and aligning appropriate schemas;
 - The [I-ADOPT \(Interoperable Descriptions of Observable Property Terminologies\) WG](#) has developed a formalised approach to describing observable properties in a machine-actionable way, supporting semantic interoperability particularly in the environmental and earth sciences;
 - The [FAIRsharing Registry: Connecting data policies, standards and databases RDA WG](#), which has led to the development of the [FAIRsharing.org](#) website.
- Active WGs:
 - [Multi-Omics Metadata Standards Integration \(MOMSI\) WG](#) is tackling the integration of heterogeneous metadata standards in the complex and data-intensive field of multi-omics research;
 - [Building Immune Digital Twins WG](#), another RDA TIGER-supported WG, is addressing the metadata and ontological challenges specific to biomedical simulations and digital twin technologies;
 - [RDA FAIR Mappings WG](#) is currently working toward community-agreed guidelines and tooling to support the alignment of metadata elements and semantic artefacts across different schemas, vocabularies, and ontologies.

3.1.3. FAIR metrics and certification

The SRIA underscores the importance of a FAIR ecosystem, in which the FAIRness of research artefacts is both enabled and sustained by the underlying infrastructure, including the services used to create, manage, store, discover, and reuse them. Table 3 below shows the RDA WGs whose work is of relevance to this Implementation Challenge.

Table 3. RDA Working Groups relevant to ‘FAIR metrics and certification’ SRIA Implementation Challenge

Community-based catalogue of requirements for trustworthy Technical Repository Service Providers Working Group (TRSPs WG)*
CURE-FAIR WG
FAIR Data Maturity Model WG
FAIR for Research Software (FAIR4RS) WG
FAIR for Virtual Research Environments WG
FAIRsharing Registry: Connecting data policies, standards and databases RDA WG
Raising FAIRness in health data and health research performing organisations (HRPOs) WG
RDA Reproducibility Checklist Working Group*
Sample Type Classification WG
Scientific Knowledge Graphs - Interoperability Framework (SKG-IF) WG
WDS/RDA Assessment of Data Fitness for Use WG
Wind Energy Community Standards WG*

*RDA TIGER-supported Working Group

There is a relatively small number of Working Groups relevant to this Implementation Challenge in comparison to others. A total of 12 WGs have been identified as directly relevant; six of which have completed their work, and six of which remain active, including three currently supported under the RDA TIGER project.

The SRIA explicitly references the work of two RDA WGs, as foundations upon which progress on this Implementation Challenge can be built¹¹. The outputs of one of these, the [FAIR Data Maturity Model \(FDMM\) WG](#) have already been widely adopted in Europe, and have been implemented across a number of Horizon Europe projects; the model has served as the basis [F-UJI automated FAIR data assessment tool](#), developed under the FAIRsFAIR project.

From the analysis the following were the principle WGs identified whose work and outputs are of relevance to FAIR metrics and certification Implementation Challenge:

¹¹ SRIA, p.91

- The [FAIR for Research Software \(FAIR4RS\) WG](#), the other one of the two WGs mentioned specifically in this section of the SRIA, has developed a Recommendation on FAIR Principles for Research Software¹²;
- [RDA/WDS TRUST Principles Outreach and Adoption Working Group](#) is currently working on an assessment of how the TRUST principles align with other schemas, principles and certification standards in the repository ecosystem;
- [Community-based catalogue of requirements for trustworthy Technical Repository Service Providers Working Group \(TRSPs WG\)](#) is analysing the repository landscape, specifically with respect to certifications and how these could be extended to providers of services to repositories.

3.1.4. Authentication and authorisation infrastructure

Compared with the other Implementation Challenges and complementary RDA WG activities, there are fewer RDA WGs (seven in total) whose work is of relevance to the Authentication and authorisation infrastructure (AAI) Implementation Challenge. As noted in the SRIA, the role of AAI in a research environment takes place in the context of the global technology marketplace, “which typically focuses on the consumer-business relationship.”¹³ This offers one explanation for why there are so few RDA WGs focused on this Implementation Challenge in comparison to the others; one of the guiding principles of RDA is that it is ‘Non-profit and technology-neutral’, which means that its Groups’ outputs must be free and open at the point of delivery and thus may fall outside the typical consumer-business relationship.

Table 4. RDA Working Groups relevant to ‘Authentication and authorisation infrastructure’ SRIA Implementation Challenge

Brokering Framework Working Group
Data Description Registry Interoperability (DDRI) WG
Global Open Research Commons International Implementations WG*
GORC International Model WG*
Persistent Identification of Instruments WG
RDA/FORCE11 Software Source Code Identification WG

¹² Chue Hong, N. P., Katz, D. S., Barker, M., Lamprecht, A-L, Martinez, C., Psomopoulos, F. E., Harrow, J., Castro, L. J., Gruenpeter, M., Martinez, P. A., Honeyman, T., et al. (2022). FAIR Principles for Research Software version 1.0. (FAIR4RS Principles v1.0). Research Data Alliance. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.15497/RDA00068>

¹³ SRIA, p.93

Scientific Knowledge Graphs - Interoperability Framework (SKG-IF) WG

*RDA TIGER-supported Working Group

From the analysis the following two related WGs were the principle ones identified whose work and outputs are of relevance to Authentication and authorisation infrastructure Implementation Challenge:

- The GORC International Model¹⁴ developed by the [GORC International Model WG](#) has nine essential elements, one of which is ‘ICT Infrastructure’ and which has a specific ‘Authentication and Authorization Infrastructure (AAI)’ category. A new WG, [GORC International Implementations WG](#) will be engaging with those looking to use and implement the model, producing different profiles of how each essential element is approached by commons developers.

3.1.5. User environments

As the SRIA states, “user environments are the digital platforms users go to in order to interact with EOSC and EOSC resources” with a focus on “portals, dashboards, landing websites and, in general, services through which the EOSC resources are accessed” and used by researchers and other stakeholders.¹⁵ As such, there are a lower number of RDA WGs relevant to this Implementation Challenge than others due to the RDA community’s focus being predominantly on issues to do with data sharing and reuse. However, there is activity currently underway within active RDA WGs which is of direct relevance here.

Table 5. RDA Working Groups relevant to ‘User environments’ SRIA Implementation Challenge

Data Description Registry Interoperability (DDRI) WG
FAIR for Virtual Research Environments WG
Global Open Research Commons International Implementations WG*
GORC International Model WG*
Health Data Commons GORC Profile WG*
International Materials Resource Registries WG
RDA-OfR Mapping the landscape of digital research tools WG

¹⁴ Payne, K., Corrie, B., Crawley, F., Harrower, N., Macneil, R., Maxwell, L., Sansone, S.-A., Treloar, A., Woodford, C., Åkerström, W. N., & RDA GORC International Model WG. (2023). The Global Open Research Commons International Model Report, Version 1 (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.15497/RDA00097>

¹⁵ SRIA, p.96

Repository Audit and Certification DSA–WDS Partnership WG
WDS/RDA Assessment of Data Fitness for Use WG
Wheat Data Interoperability WG

*RDA TIGER-supported Working Group

From the analysis the following two related WGs were the principle ones identified whose work and outputs are of relevance to User environments Implementation Challenge:

- The work done by [GORC International Model WG](#) and its follow-on [GORC International Implementations WG](#) feed into the requirements of this Implementation Challenge for there to be a legal framework to underpin the availability of services to users across boundaries;
- [FAIR for Virtual Research Environments WG](#) is developing guidelines on how all types of these environments can be FAIR for users and become FAIR themselves;
- The [RDA-OfR Mapping the landscape of digital research tools \(MaLDReTH\) WG](#) has produced a Recommendation which focuses in part on how to improve user experience of different types of research tools.

3.1.6. Resource provider environments

The impact of RDA WGs’ work on this Implementation Challenge is centred on the interoperability of resources and facilitating the alignment of newly developed resources with existing community practices and services. There are 26 WGs identified as relevant to this, concerned variously with repositories, infrastructure development, and catalogues and registries of services. Ten of these WGs have completed their work and produced Recommendations of relevance here.

Table 6. RDA Working Groups relevant to ‘Resource provider environments’ SRIA Implementation Challenge

Community-based catalogue of requirements for trustworthy Technical Repository Service Providers Working Group (TRSPs WG)*
Computational Modelling of Health Data WG*
CoreTrustSeal Maintenance WG
Data Description Registry Interoperability (DDRI) WG
Data Granularity WG*
Data Repository Attributes WG
Data Usage Metrics WG
FAIR Data Maturity Model WG

RDA TIGER “Research Data Alliance facilitation of Targeted International working Groups for EOSC-related Research solutions” is funded by HORIZON-INFRA-2022-EOSC-0, Project:101094406.

FAIR for Virtual Research Environments WG
FAIRsharing Registry: Connecting data policies, standards and databases RDA WG
Global Open Research Commons International Implementations WG*
GORC International Model WG*
Health Data Commons GORC Profile WG*
International Materials Resource Registries WG
Mapping the Landscape of Digital Research Tools II WG*
Practical Policy WG
RDA-OfR Mapping the landscape of digital research tools WG
RDA/CODATA Data Systems, Tools, and Services for Crisis Situations WG*
RDA/WDS Publishing Data Services WG
RDA/WDS Scholarly Link Exchange (Scholix) WG
RDA/WDS TRUST Principles Outreach and Adoption WG*
Repository Audit and Certification DSA–WDS Partnership WG
Research Data Collections WG
Research Data Repository Interoperability WG
Scientific Knowledge Graphs - Interoperability Framework (SKG-IF) WG
WDS/RDA Assessment of Data Fitness for Use WG

*RDA TIGER-supported Working Group

From the analysis the following were the principle WGs identified whose work and outputs are of relevance to FAIR metrics and certification Implementation Challenge, grouped by completed WGs (i.e., those which have produced Recommendations) and ongoing WGs.

- Completed WGs:
 - The [Research Data Repository Interoperability WG](#)'s Recommendation¹⁶ addresses the issue of combining data and holdings across repositories, a core priority of this Implementation Challenge;

¹⁶ RDA Research Data Repository Interoperability WG. (2018). Research Data Repository Interoperability WG Final Recommendations. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.15497/RDA00025>

- The [Data Granularity WG](#)'s final Recommendation¹⁷ provides guidelines on selecting appropriate levels of granularity for repositories and other infrastructures.
- Active WGs:
 - [FAIR for Virtual Research Environments WG](#) is aiming to develop FAIR-by-design practices for VREs, enabling interoperable integration of tools, workflows, and services with EOSC infrastructures.
 - [Scientific Knowledge Graphs - Interoperability Framework \(SKG-IF\) WG](#) is developing shared models and semantic alignment approaches that enable interoperable, machine-actionable linking of research objects across domains.
 - [Mapping the Landscape of Digital Research Tools II \(MaLDReTH II\) WG](#) is advancing the lifecycle model for the use of research tools developed by the first iteration of this WG, highlighting interoperability challenges and alignment opportunities to support discovery and integration of tools in research workflows.

3.1.7. EOSC Interoperability Framework

The EOSC Interoperability Framework (EIF) Implementation Challenge differs from those discussed above in that the Framework¹⁸ exists as a standalone document produced by the Interoperability Task Force of the EOSC Executive Board FAIR Working Group, with participation from the Architecture WG. As is clear from most if not all of the Implementation Challenges described above, and how RDA WGs address them (or have the potential to further contend with their respective gaps and priorities) interoperability is a cross-cutting concern. “In terms of EOSC, the ‘I’ of FAIR is the critical aspect, as interoperability is the glue that allows EOSC to function.”¹⁹ The SRIA elaborates how the vision for the EOSC is not just the interoperability of data and metadata, but all other resources used in support of research - software, infrastructures, services, tools, models, platforms and semantic artefacts.

Table 7. RDA Working Groups relevant to ‘EOSC Interoperability Framework’ SRIA Implementation Challenge

Agrise semantics WG
Alignment of multilingual vocabularies in the Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) WG*
Community-based catalogue of requirements for trustworthy Technical Repository Service Providers Working Group (TRSPs WG)*

¹⁷ Jenkyns, R., Mathiak, B., McNeill, K., Smith, G., Sun, G., Little, C., Jones, B., Elbert, D., Hellström, M., Schabinger, R., & RDA Data Granularity WG. (2025). Guidance on Data Granularity: Report of the RDA Data Granularity WG (Version 1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.15497/RDA00126>

¹⁸ (2021). *EOSC interoperability framework : report from the EOSC Executive Board Working Groups FAIR and Architecture*. Publications Office. <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/620649>

¹⁹ SRIA, p.101

Data Description Registry Interoperability (DDRI) WG
Data Foundation and Terminology WG
Data Granularity WG*
Data Repository Attributes WG
FAIR for Virtual Research Environments WG
FAIR Mappings WG*
FAIRification of Genomic Annotations WG*
FAIRsharing Registry: Connecting data policies, standards and databases RDA WG
Global Open Research Commons International Implementations WG*
GORC International Model WG*
I-ADOPT WG*
Multi-omics Metadata Standards Integration (MOMSI) WG*
National PID Strategies WG*
RDA-OfR Mapping the landscape of digital research tools WG
RDA/WDS TRUST Principles Outreach and Adoption WG*
Repository Audit and Certification DSA–WDS Partnership WG
Research Data Repository Interoperability WG
Research Metadata Schemas WG
Sample Type Classification WG
Scientific Knowledge Graphs - Interoperability Framework (SKG-IF) WG
Small Uncrewed Aircraft and Autonomous Platforms Data WG*
WDS/RDA Assessment of Data Fitness for Use WG
Wheat Data Interoperability WG

*RDA TIGER-supported Working Group

The EIF itself describes the requirements to achieve interoperability at four different layers; technical, semantic, organisational and legal interoperability. Due to the nature of RDA most of the relevant

RDA TIGER “Research Data Alliance facilitation of Targeted International working Groups for EOSC-related Research solutions” is funded by HORIZON-INFRA-2022-EOSC-0, Project:101094406.

WGs are focusing on the technical and semantic layers of interoperability, with some further WGs focused on specific aspects of the organisational layer.

From the analysis the following were the principle WGs identified whose work and outputs are of relevance to FAIR metrics and certification Implementation Challenge, grouped by those relevant for the technical, semantic and organisational layers of interoperability:

- Technical level:
 - [Data Granularity WG](#)'s Recommendation²⁰ provides guidance for infrastructure developers on how to determine appropriate levels of data granularity;
 - [National PID Strategies WG](#)'s Recommendation includes a checklist for PID policy developers, the use of which supports interoperability across different types of PIDs (e.g., grant identifiers, person identifiers, organisation identifiers, etc.)
- Semantic level:
 - The [Research Data Repository Interoperability WG](#) proposes an overall framework that would support the federation of repositories and their holdings;
 - The outputs of both the [RDA/WDS Certification of Digital Repositories Interest Group](#) and the subsequent [Repository Audit and Certification DSA–WDS Partnership WG](#) also focus on the repository ecosystem and provided the basis of the CoreTrustSeal certification standard;
 - Both the [Multi-Omics Metadata Standards Integration \(MOMSI\) WG](#) and [FAIRification of Genomic Annotations WG](#) address the need for harmonisation within and across disciplines of community specific standards and schemas.
- Organisational level:
 - The [TRUST Principles Outreach and Adoption WG](#) and the [Community-based catalogue of requirements for trustworthy Technical Repository Service Providers Working Group \(TRSPs WG\)](#) both address the need defined in the SRIA for “interoperability certification mechanisms for service providers”²¹

3.2. Multi-Annual Roadmap (MAR)

The section above on the SRIA Implementation Challenges describes how completed and ongoing RDA WGs can address (and in some cases are already addressing) the action areas requiring attention from the European research community and how these efforts can both support and be supported

²⁰ Jenkyns, R., Mathiak, B., McNeill, K., Smith, G., Sun, G., Little, C., Jones, B., Elbert, D., Hellström, M., Schabinger, R., & RDA Data Granularity WG. (2025). Guidance on Data Granularity: Report of the RDA Data Granularity WG (Version 1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.15497/RDA00126>

²¹ SRIA, p.104

by global activities. This next section focuses on the SRIA Multi-Annual Roadmap, specifically on General Objectives for the Stage 3 period (covering 2025-2027). The reasons for limiting the focus here on just the General Objectives and not also on the Strategic and Operational Objectives were to do partly with refining the overall focus of this report and also due to the fact that there is significant overlap with the concerns expressed in the Strategic and Operational Objectives and in the Gaps and Priorities of the Implementation Challenges; we decided to avoid reiterating the descriptions of connections that have already been made above. Similar to section 3.1 above, there is a corresponding section in Annex 1 which contains further background and analysis relating to these SRIA General Objectives.

3.2.1. General Objective 1: Ensure that Open Science practices and skills are rewarded and taught, becoming the ‘new normal’

Considering their activities in general, RDA WGs all in some way contribute to the implementation of Open Science practices in research. Though there are fewer WGs whose activities are of relevance to this General Objective compared to the others, there are nevertheless direct connections between WG outputs and the concerns outlined with respect to this Objective. Table 8 below shows the 18 RDA WGs whose work is of relevance to this General Objective.

Table 8. RDA Working Groups relevant to SRIA Priority Stage 3 - General Objective 1

Building Immune Digital Twins WG*	RDA COVID-19 WG
Capacity Development for Agriculture Data WG	RDA/CODATA Data Systems, Tools, and Services for Crisis Situations WG*
Community-based catalogue of requirements for trustworthy Technical Repository Service Providers Working Group (TRSPs WG)*	RDA/CODATA Summer Schools in Data Science and Cloud Computing in the Developing World WG
Computational Modelling of Health Data WG*	RDA/WDS Publishing Data Bibliometrics WG
Coordinating Earth, Space, and Environmental Science Data Preservation and Scholarly Publication Processes	RDA/WDS Publishing Data Services WG
Data Usage Metrics WG	RDA/WDS Publishing Data Workflows WG
Ethics in Agricultural (Ag) Data WG*	RDA/WDS Scholarly Link Exchange (Scholix) WG
Health Data Commons GORC Profile WG*	WDS/RDA Assessment of Data Fitness for Use WG
Raising FAIRness in health data and health research performing organisations (HRPOs) WG	Wheat Data Interoperability WG

*RDA TIGER-supported Working Group

From the analysis the following were the principle WGs identified whose work and outputs contribute to this General Objective:

- The [RDA/CODATA Summer Schools in Data Science and Cloud Computing in the Developing World WG](#) has produced two Recommendations^{22,23} and has run over 20 iterations of its CODATA-RDA Research Data Science Schools since 2016. These have provided pupils (most of whom are early career researchers) with the skills to implement Open Science and data sharing techniques in their work;
- The Recommendation²⁴ produced by the [WDS/RDA Assessment of Data Fitness for Use WG](#) contributes to the European-level priority associated with this General Objective regarding the appraisal of data requiring long-term preservation.

The community-developed standards, guidelines and practices for data, which represent a key class of outputs that RDA WGs produce, all directly and indirectly contribute to the standardisation and spread of Open Science practices. One recommendation here would be for further harmonisation within the RDA community of WG activities which, taken together, could feed into the areas requiring attention with respect to this General Objective and efforts to make Open Science, and attendant practices with respect to research data, the “new normal”.

3.2.2. General Objective 2: Enable the definition of standards, and the development of tools and services, to allow researchers to find, access, reuse and combine results

Of the three, this General Objective aligns with the largest amount of RDA WGs. In our analysis, the activities of 46 WGs relate in some way to defining standards and/or developing tools and services to further the use and reuse of research outputs and data. There is a large degree of overlap in the way this General Objective is characterised and the requirement for RDA WGs’ “overarching goal of increasing data-driven innovation” and “to promote data sharing and exchange, interoperability, data use and re-use, data discoverability and analysis, data stewardship and preservation, and best practice for substantive communities.”²⁵ Table 9 below shows the RDA WGs whose work is of relevance to this General Objective.

²² Materials associated with this framework can be found in this Zenodo community:

<https://zenodo.org/communities/codata-rda-research-data-science-summer-school/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest>

²³ Shanahan, H., Quick, R., Córdoba, M. A., Clement, G., Bezuidenhout, L., Shanmugasundaram, V., ... Short, H. (2019). A curriculum for foundational Research Data Science skills for Early Career Researchers (Version 1). <https://doi.org/10.15497/rda00038>

²⁴ Austin, C., Cousijn, H., Diepenbroek, M., Petters, J., Soares E Silva, M. (2019): WDS/RDA Assessment of Data Fitness for Use WG Outputs and Recommendations. <https://dx.doi.org/10.15497/rda00034>

²⁵ See RDA requirements for WGs: <https://www.rd-alliance.org/working-groups/>

Table 9. RDA Working Groups relevant to SRIA Priority Stage 3 - General Objective 2

Agrisemantics WG	Mapping the Landscape of Digital Research Tools II WG ⁺
Alignment of multilingual vocabularies in the Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) WG ⁺	Metadata Standards Catalog WG
Building Immune Digital Twins WG ⁺	Metadata Standards Directory WG
Community-based catalogue of requirements for trustworthy Technical Repository Service Providers Working Group (TRSPs WG) ⁺	Multi-omics Metadata Standards Integration (MOMSI) WG ⁺
Complex Citations Working Group	National PID Strategies WG ⁺
Computational Modelling of Health Data WG ⁺	Persistent Identification of Instruments WG
CoreTrustSeal Maintenance WG	PID Information Types WG
CURE-FAIR WG	Raising FAIRness in health data and health research performing organisations (HRPOs) WG
Data Citation WG	RDA / TDWG Metadata Standards for attribution of physical and digital collections stewardship
Data Description Registry Interoperability (DDRI) WG	RDA & ReSA Policies in Research Organisations for Research Software WG ⁺
Data Foundation and Terminology WG	RDA Reproducibility Checklist Working Group ⁺
Data Repository Attributes WG	RDA-OfR Mapping the landscape of digital research tools WG
Data Usage Metrics WG	RDA/WDS Publishing Data Services WG
FAIR for Research Software (FAIR4RS) WG	RDA/WDS Scholarly Link Exchange (Scholix) WG
FAIR for Virtual Research Environments WG	Repository Audit and Certification DSA–WDS Partnership WG
FAIR Mappings WG ⁺	Research Data Collections WG
FAIRification of Genomic Annotations WG ⁺	Research Data Repository Interoperability WG
FAIRsharing Registry: Connecting data policies, standards and databases RDA WG	Sample Type Classification WG
Global Open Research Commons International Implementations WG ⁺	Scientific Knowledge Graphs - Interoperability Framework (SKG-IF) WG

GORC International Model WG*	Small Uncrewed Aircraft and Autonomous Platforms Data WG*
Harmonised terminologies and schemas for FAIR data in materials science and related domains WG*	WDS/RDA Assessment of Data Fitness for Use WG
I-ADOPT WG*	Wheat Data Interoperability WG
International Materials Resource Registries WG	Wind Energy Community Standards WG*

*RDA TIGER-supported Working Group

In order to demonstrate how RDA WG activities align with this General Objective it is useful to parse its description and identify examples of relevant outputs and activities of completed and current WGs which focus on the definition of standards and the development of both tools and services.

Standards

Developing standards themselves as well as the guidelines for their interoperation is a core part of RDA WG activities overall. Central to RDA efforts in these areas the following WGs and their outputs have facilitated the setting, describing, cataloguing and sharing of standards:

- The [FAIRsharing Registry: Connecting data policies, standards and databases RDA WG's Recommendation](#)²⁶ was central to the establishment of fairsharing.org, which enables users to identify appropriate standards for their own data and, key for this General Objective, allows producers to describe and align their standards with others;
- Similarly, the work of the [Metadata Standards Catalog WG](#) led to the establishment of the Metadata Standards Catalog²⁷, an open directory of research metadata schemas by facilitating access to standards which enable the sharing and reuse of data and other research outputs across domains.
- The [CoreTrustSeal Maintenance WG](#) (and its precursor Repository Audit and Certification DSA-WDS Partnership WG) contributed to the [CoreTrustSeal](#) repository certification standard, which contributes to the trustworthiness of the repository ecosystem;
- Both the RDA TIGER-supported [Multi-Omics Metadata Standards Integration \(MOMSI\)](#) and the [FAIRification of Genomic Annotations WGs](#) focus on the development and integration of metadata schemas in the omics domains.

Tools and services

²⁶ McQuilton, P., Hodson, S., Lawrence, R., Sansone, S.-A., & FAIRsharing Registry: Connecting Data Policies, Standards and Databases RDA WG. (2019). The FAIRsharing Registry and Recommendations: Interlinking Standards, Databases and Data Policies (Version 1). Research Data Alliance. <https://doi.org/10.15497/RDA00030>

²⁷ The catalogue can be accessed here: <https://rdamsc.bath.ac.uk/>

There are many active and completed RDA WGs whose activities centre on research tools and services and their categorisations, linkages and descriptions. The following WGs contribute to this aspect of the General Objective:

- Two ‘sister’ WGs, [RDA-OfR Mapping the landscape of digital research tools WG](#) and its follow-on [Mapping the Landscape of Digital Research Tools II \(MaLDReTH II\) WG](#) have focused on the categorisation and mapping of digital research tools used across the research lifecycle;
- The [RDA / CODATA Data Systems, Tools, and Services for Crisis Situations WG](#), which among other activities has undertaken a survey to identify the tools used and the potential gaps in tool provision for those working in crisis zones.

3.2.3. General Objective 3: Establish a sustainable and federated infrastructure enabling open sharing of scientific results

A read through the European-level priorities for this General Objectives gives a sense of the wide range of features required for the vision of the sustainable and federated infrastructure for EOSC to be realised. The levels of investment and scope required to address this General Objective are much greater than that needed for the types of activities focused on by RDA WGs. However, if we focus more closely on some of the associated priorities themselves rather than the overarching General Objective then it is possible to identify a significant amount of RDA activities of relevance.

Table 10. RDA Working Groups relevant to SRIA Priority Stage 3 - General Objective 3

Agrisemantics WG	GORC International Model WG ⁺
Alignment of multilingual vocabularies in the Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) WG ⁺	Harmonised terminologies and schemas for FAIR data in materials science and related domains WG ⁺
Brokering Framework Working Group	Health Data Commons GORC Profile WG ⁺
Building Immune Digital Twins WG ⁺	I-ADOPT WG ⁺
Community-based catalogue of requirements for trustworthy Technical Repository Service Providers Working Group (TRSPs WG) ⁺	Multi-omics Metadata Standards Integration (MOMSI) WG ⁺
Coordinating Earth, Space, and Environmental Science Data Preservation and Scholarly Publication Processes	Persistent Identification of Instruments WG
CoreTrustSeal Maintenance WG	PID Information Types WG
Data Description Registry Interoperability (DDRI) WG	Practical Policy WG
Data Foundation and Terminology WG	RDA/WDS Publishing Data Bibliometrics WG

Data Type Registries WG	RDA/WDS TRUST Principles Outreach and Adoption WG*
EOSC-Future/RDA Artificial Intelligence & Data Visitation WG*	Repository Audit and Certification DSA–WDS Partnership WG
FAIR Data Maturity Model WG	Research Data Repository Interoperability WG
FAIR for Virtual Research Environments WG	Research Metadata Schemas WG
FAIR Mappings WG*	Sample Type Classification WG
FAIRification of Genomic Annotations WG*	Scientific Knowledge Graphs - Interoperability Framework (SKG-IF) WG
FAIRsharing Registry: Connecting data policies, standards and databases RDA WG	Small Uncrewed Aircraft and Autonomous Platforms Data WG*
Global Open Research Commons International Implementations WG*	WDS/RDA Assessment of Data Fitness for Use WG

*RDA TIGER-supported Working Group

There are two European-level priorities focused on the provision of semantic artefact-related services: priorities F. “Accelerate the adoption of interoperability and semantic artefact catalogues. Support AI-enabled services that facilitate interoperability in a more automated way”, and G. “Services for dependable semantic artefact catalogues should be part of the EOSC Core, akin to how vocabularies are published by the EC publications Office at EU Vocabularies.”²⁸ From the analysis the following were the principal WGs identified whose work and outputs contribute to this General Objective:

- The [FAIR Mappings WG](#) is developing common guidelines to make mappings between semantic artefacts FAIR, with the aim of enabling automated interoperability and creating an open knowledge base of mapping and crosswalk scenarios;
- The [Alignment of multilingual vocabularies in the Social Sciences and Humanities WG](#) is producing guidelines to improve the homogeneity, reuse and cross-disciplinary, multilingual and cross-cultural adoption of semantic artefacts in social sciences and humanities domains;
- [GORC International Model WG](#) and [GORC International Implementations Working Group \(GORC II WG\)](#) are providing models and implementation guidance that inform how EOSC can operate as part of a federated Global Open Research Commons.

²⁸ SRIA, p.192

3.3. Summary

That there are considerable overlaps and shared areas of concern for the RDA community, its Working Groups and the EOSC ecosystem is not a surprise. The full extent of RDA outputs that could be implemented is representative of the degree to which areas of focus for a global community like RDA are shared with Europe. The analysis above shows the value that the RDA community and WG outputs, largely resourced by volunteer effort, has in achieving the ambitious goals of the EOSC. This value is reflected by the SRIA in the multiple references to the RDA outputs that could be or have already been implemented in addressing the concerns, gaps and priorities described in the Implementation Challenges and in the Multi-Annual Roadmap; though these relationships already exist, often reinforced by those individuals contributing to multiple activities, the practical benefits of RDA WG activities and outputs continue to demonstrate how globally coordinated, community-driven standards can meaningfully advance the next stages of EOSC development.

4. EOSC-related Horizon Europe projects

This section focuses on the relevance of RDA WGs to Horizon Europe (HE) projects related to EOSC and OS activities. To better understand the relationship between the RDA community and the HE projects, we mapped and analysed the activity domains of RDA WGs to the current HE projects. This mapping not only provides an overview of the different activity domains of the RDA community and the HE-funded projects, but also highlights a close link between RDA's activity domains and HE funded-projects, as well as the complementarity of RDA's field of action with the ambitions of future HE funded-projects. Annex 2 contains further information on the methodology used for this section as well as more detail on the analysis results.

4.1. Mapping of RDA Working Groups (WGs) to current OS-related HE-funded projects

This section presents a condensed analysis of the activity domains of RDA WGs and their alignment with HE-funded projects. Each subsection follows the same structure, first with a short description of the five identified domains of activity derived from EOSC operational objectives (these domains are Scalability, Federation, Policy evolution, FAIR compliance and Wider user base)²⁹, followed by information on the overall relevance of RDA WGs activities to HE projects, and then a more detailed description of each domain of activity. In this section RDA WGs and all HE-funded projects are affiliated to one domain based on their main activity. For further details on the overall methodology used in this section, see Annex 2.

²⁹ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/ALL/?uri=COM:2018:436:FIN>

The mapping of RDA WGs to HE-funded projects based on activity domains can be explored further via a [Kumu.io](https://kumu.io) map. The overall mapping can be seen below in Figure 2. The activity domains are shown in yellow, while the RDA WGs are colored in grey, and the HE funded-projects, related to EOSC and OS, are respectively colored in purple and cyan.

EXPLORE THE MAP

Mapping Research Data Alliance Working Groups to HE-funded projects

Figure 2. Kumu map representing mapping of RDA WGs to HE-funded projects based on the domain of activity

RDA TIGER “Research Data Alliance facilitation of Targeted International working Groups for EOSC-related Research solutions” is funded by HORIZON-INFRA-2022-EOSC-0, Project:101094406.

Figure 3 below provides an overview of the domains of activity of RDA WGs and HE-funded projects in relation to the activity domains. Further analysis of each of these can be found in Annex 2.

Figure 3. Distribution of activity domains across RDA WGs, and the HE funded projects from the INFRAEOSC and the OS-related ERA (ERA-OS) calls.

4.1.1. Scalability

The Scalability activity domain refers to the quality of a service or infrastructure to grow and remain operational over the long time. Thus, in this domain of activity both Scalability and Sustainability aspects of the access channel are included. Figure 4 below represents the RDA WGs and the HE-funded projects dealing with the scalability domain.

Figure 4. Kumu map of RDA WGs related to 'scalability' domain and HE-funded projects

As for HE-funded projects, only INFRAEOSC projects cover this domain of activity, with fourteen associated projects: FAIRCORE4EOSC, RDA TIGER, GraspOS, EOSC Beyond, EOSC EDEN and five funded projects: AI4EOSC, EuroScienceGateway, FAIR-EASE, RAISE and Scilake of the 'Innovative and customizable services for EOSC' call, as well as the four funded projects: LUMEN, EOSC Data Commons, DataGEMS and RAISE suite of the 'Innovative and customizable services for EOSC Exchange' call for proposal (see Figure 4).

Table 11. RDA Working Groups relevant to 'Scalability' domain of activity

Community-based catalogue of requirements for trustworthy Technical Repository Service Providers Working Group (TRSPs WG) ⁺
Mapping the Landscape of Digital Research Tools II WG ⁺
RDA/WDS TRUST Principles Outreach and Adoption WG ⁺

RDA TIGER "Research Data Alliance facilitation of Targeted International working Groups for EOSC-related Research solutions" is funded by HORIZON-INFRA-2022-EOSC-0, Project:101094406.

Array Database Assessment WG
CoreTrustSeal Maintenance WG
RDA-OfR Mapping the landscape of digital research tools WG

*RDA TIGER-supported Working Group

There are a total of six RDA WGs covering this domain of activity (Table 11), including three currently supported under the RDA TIGER project.

From the analysis, the RDA WGs dealing with:

- **Scalability:** refers to interoperability of service with [RDA-OfR Mapping the landscape of digital research tools](#) WG and its successor [MaLDReTH II](#);
- **Sustainability:** refers to quality certification and assessment for repositories, with [Community-based catalogue of requirements for trustworthy Technical Repository Service Providers \(TRSPs\)](#) WG, [RDA/WDS TRUST Principles Outreach and Adoption](#) WG, [CoreTrustSeal Maintenance](#) WG, and to a certain extent the [Array Database Assessment](#) WG.

While, INFRAEOSC projects focusing in:

- **Scalability:** refers to expansion of service deployment with [FAIRCORE4EOSC](#), [AI4EOSC](#), [EuroScienceGateway](#), [FAIR-EASE](#), [RAISE](#), [Scilake](#), [LUMEN](#), [EOSC Beyond](#), [EOSC Data Commons](#), [DataGEMS](#) and [RAISE suite](#);
- **Sustainability:** refers to preservation of good practices with [RDA TIGER](#) or long term access with [EOSC EDEN](#), but also to integration to market as mentioned in the call description ‘Innovative and customizable services for EOSC’³⁰

4.1.2. Federation

Federation activity domain refers to the integration of resources, from European, national, regional or institutional origin, into a cohesive system. Figure 5 below represents the RDA WGs and the HE-funded projects dealing with the Federation domain.

³⁰ Innovative and customizable services for EOSC:

<https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/opportunities/topic-details/HORIZON-INFRA-2021-EOSC-01-04?order=DESC&pageNumber=1&pageSize=50&sortBy=startDate&isExactMatch=true&status=31094501,31094502,31094503&frameworkProgramme=43108390&callIdentifier=HORIZON-INFRA-2021-EOSC-01>

Figure 5. Kumu map of RDA WGs related to 'federation' domain and HE-funded projects

As for Scalability activity domain, only INFRAEOSC projects cover this domain, with six associated projects: EO4Cancer, EO4United, FIDELIS, OSCARS and the two funded projects Blue-Cloud2026 and AquaINFRA of the 'FAIR and open data sharing in support of healthy oceans, seas, coastal and inland waters' call for proposal (see Figure 5 above).

Table 12. RDA Working Groups relevant to 'federation' domain of activity

National PID Strategies WG ⁺
GORC International Model WG ⁺
Global Open Research Commons International Implementations WG ⁺
Brokering Framework WG
Coordinating Earth, Space, and Environmental Science Data Preservation and Scholarly Publication Processes

RDA TIGER "Research Data Alliance facilitation of Targeted International working Groups for EOSC-related Research solutions" is funded by HORIZON-INFRA-2022-EOSC-0, Project:101094406.

Data Description Registry Interoperability (DDRI) WG
Data Type Registries WG
Persistent Identification of Instruments WG
Research Data Repository Interoperability WG

*RDA TIGER-supported Working Group

There are a total of nine of the RDA WGs covering this activity domain (see Table 12 above), including three currently supported under the RDA TIGER project.

From the analysis, the RDA WGs affiliate to federation activity domains refers to:

- (Meta)data identification linkage, with [Data Description Registry Interoperability \(DDRI\)](#) WG, [Data Type Registries](#) WG, [Persistent Identification of Instruments](#), and [National PID Strategies](#) WG;
- Services integration, with [Brokering Framework](#) WG, [Coordinating Earth, Space, and Environmental Science Data Preservation and Scholarly Publication Processes](#) WG, [Data Description Registry Interoperability \(DDRI\)](#) WG, Research Data Repository Interoperability WG, and to a certain extent the the [GORC International Model WG](#) and its successor [Global Open Research Commons International Implementations](#) WG which focus on model integration.

INFRAEOSC projects mainly refer on service integration activity, with particular focus on

- Domain specific, with [EOSC4cancer](#), [Blue-Cloud2026](#), [AqualNFRA](#) and [OSCARS](#) projects
- Domain agnostic, with [FIDELIS](#) and [EOSC United](#) projects.

Again, for more further details and analysis, see Annex 2, Federation section.

4.1.3. Policy evolution

Policy and technical evolution domain of activity, here entitled as ‘Policy evolution’, refers to the ability of a service or infrastructure to adapt to emerging research needs and requirements. The policy and technical evolution domain represent the second largest activity domain covered by RDA WGs, with 16 in total, six of which are RDA TIGER-supported WGs (see Table 13 below). Figure 6 represents the RDA WGs and the HE-funded projects dealing with the policy and technical evolution domain.

Figure 6. Kumu map of RDA WGs related to ‘policy evolution’ domain and HE-funded projects

Unlike for two previous activity domains, here both INFRAEOSC and ERA-OS projects cover the policy evolution domain of activity. There is six INFRAEOSC projects affiliated to this domain which are EOSC Focus, CRAFT-OA, EOSC Gravity and the three funded projects: TITAN, EOSC Entrust and SIESTA of the ‘Trusted environments for sensitive data management in EOSC’ call. With 11 out of 17, the policy evolution domain represents the main domain of activity of ERA-OS projects. These eleven projects are: DIAMAS, PathOS, OPUS, CoARA Boost, TRUSTparency, IP4OS, PALOMERA, REINFORCING, and the three funded projects TIER2, OSIRIS and iRISE of the ‘Increasing the reproducibility of scientific results’ call for proposal.

Table 13. RDA Working Groups relevant to ‘policy evolution’ domain of activity

Building Immune Digital Twins WG ⁺
EOSC-Future/RDA Artificial Intelligence & Data Visitation WG ⁺
Ethics in Agricultural Data WG ⁺

RDA TIGER “Research Data Alliance facilitation of Targeted International working Groups for EOSC-related Research solutions” is funded by HORIZON-INFRA-2022-EOSC-0, Project:101094406.

RDA & ReSA Policies in Research Organisations for Research Software WG ⁺
RDA/CODATA Data Systems, Tools, and Services for Crisis Situations WG ⁺
Blockchain Applications in Health WG
Complex Citations WG
Data Usage Metrics WG
Discipline-specific Guidance for Data Management Plans WG
International Materials Resource Registries WG
Practical Policy WG
Raising FAIRness in health data and health research performing organisations (HRPOs) WG
RDA COVID-19 WG
Repository Audit and Certification DSA–WDS Partnership WG
RDA Reproducibility Checklist WG ⁺

⁺RDA TIGER-supported Working Group

From the analysis, the principle RDA WGs affiliated to policy evolution activity domain are grouped below along domain specific and domain agnostic lines:

- Domain specific: [RDA/CODATA Data Systems, Tools, and Services for Crisis Situations](#) WG, [Raising FAIRness in health data and health research performing organisations \(HRPOs\)](#) WG, [Building Immune Digital Twins](#) WG, [RDA COVID-19](#) WG, [Discipline-specific Guidance for Data Management Plans](#) WG and [Ethics in Agricultural Data](#) WG, with the exception for the general [Practical Policy](#) WG;
- Domain agnostic (especially to respect to trustworthiness): [Repository Audit and Certification DSA–WDS Partnership](#) WG, [RDA Reproducibility Checklist](#) WG. and [RDA & ReSA Policies in Research Organisations for Research Software](#) WG, and to assessment activity with [Data Usage Metrics](#) WG.

The INFRAEOSC projects focus on:

- Domain specific, related to data security and protection with [TITAN](#), [EOSC Entrust](#) and [SIESTA](#) projects focusing on sensitive data;
- Domain agnostic, with a focus on expansion and coordination with [EOSC Gravity](#) and [EOSC Focus](#) projects, as well as intellectual property with [CRAFT-OA](#) project

The ERA-OS projects focus on:

- Domain specific, especially on intellectual property with [DIAMAS](#), [IP4OS](#) and [PALOMERA](#) projects;
- Domain agnostic, especially focus on trustability and assessment aspects, with [PathOS](#), [OPUS](#), [CoARA Boost](#), [TRUSTparency](#), [REINFORCING](#), [TIER2](#), [OSIRIS](#) and [IRISE](#) projects.

RDA TIGER “Research Data Alliance facilitation of Targeted International working Groups for EOSC-related Research solutions” is funded by HORIZON-INFRA-2022-EOSC-0, Project:101094406.

4.1.4. FAIR compliance

FAIR compliance domain refers to activity that ensures data interoperability and alignment with FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) principles. Figure 7 below shows the RDA WGs and the HE-funded projects dealing with the federation domain.

Figure 7. Kumu map of RDA WGs related to 'FAIR compliance' domain and HE-funded projects

Both INFRAEOSC and ERA-OS projects cover the FAIR compliance domain of activity. There are five INFRAEOSC projects affiliated to this domain; these are FAIR-IMPACT, OSTrails, EVERISE, CLIMATE-ADAPT4EOSC and FAIR2Adapt. WorldFAIR is the only ERA-OS project addressing this activity domain.

Table 14. RDA Working Groups relevant to 'FAIR compliance' domain of activity

Alignment of multilingual vocabularies in the Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) WG ⁺
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RDA TIGER "Research Data Alliance facilitation of Targeted International working Groups for EOSC-related Research solutions" is funded by HORIZON-INFRA-2022-EOSC-0, Project:101094406.

Computational Modelling of Health Data WG ⁺
Data Granularity WG
FAIR Data Maturity Model WG
FAIR Mappings WG ⁺
FAIRification of Genomic Annotations WG ⁺
Harmonised terminologies and schemas for FAIR data in materials science and related domains WG ⁺
Health Data Commons GORC Profile WG ⁺
I-ADOPT WG ⁺
Multi-omics Metadata Standards Integration (MOMSI) WG ⁺
Small Uncrewed Aircraft and Autonomous Platforms Data WG ⁺
Wind Energy Community Standards WG ⁺
Common maDMPs API WG ⁺
Agrisemantics WG
CURE-FAIR WG
Data Citation WG
Data Foundation and Terminology WG
Data Repository Attributes WG
DMP Common Standards WG
FAIR for Research Software (FAIR4RS) WG
FAIR for Virtual Research Environments WG
FAIRsharing Registry: Connecting data policies, standards and databases RDA WG
Metadata Standards Catalog WG
Metadata Standards Directory WG
PID Information Types WG
RDA / TDWG Metadata Standards for attribution of physical and digital collections stewardship WG
RDA/FORCE11 Software Source Code Identification WG
RDA/WDS Publishing Data Bibliometrics WG
RDA/WDS Publishing Data Services WG
RDA/WDS Publishing Data Workflows WG
RDA/WDS Scholarly Link Exchange (Scholix) WG
Research Data Collections WG

Research Metadata Schemas WG
Scientific Knowledge Graphs - Interoperability Framework (SKG-IF) WG
WDS/RDA Assessment of Data Fitness for Use WG
Wheat Data Interoperability WG
Sample Type Classification WG

*RDA TIGER-supported Working Group

With 37 out of 69, FAIR compliance domain represents the largest selection of WG's addressing this domain of activity. Eleven of the RDA WGs are supported under the RDA TIGER project (Table 14).

From the analysis, the principle RDA WGs affiliated to FAIR compliance domain include:

- Regarding domain specific activity: [Agrisemantics WG](#), [Computational Modelling of Health Data WG](#), [Alignment of multilingual vocabularies in the Social Sciences and Humanities \(SSH\) WG](#), [Small Uncrewed Aircraft and Autonomous Platforms Data WG](#) and [Wind Energy Community Standards WG](#);
- Domain agnostic activity, with [I-ADOPT WG](#), [Data Foundation and Terminology WG](#) and [Metadata Standards Catalog WG](#), [Common maDMPs API WG](#), [FAIR for Research Software \(FAIR4RS\) WG](#), [FAIRsharing Registry: Connecting data policies, standards and databases WG](#), and [RDA/WDS Publishing Data Workflows WG](#).

As well as for the INFRAEOSC projects which also focus on:

- Domain specific activity, with [CLIMATE-ADAPT4EOSC](#) and [FAIR2Adapt](#) projects, as well as the two cross disciplinary projects: [FAIR-IMPACT](#) and [OSTrails](#);
- Domain agnostic activity, with the software focused [EVERSE](#) project.

While FAIR compliance does not represent the main activity of the INFRAEOSC projects, the adoption of FAIR principles may still be required. The single ERA-OS project dealing with the FAIR compliance domain is the [WorldFAIR](#) project which focuses on cross-disciplinary activities.

4.1.5. Wide user base

The wide user base activity domain refers to activities aimed at supporting a broad spectrum of researchers and stakeholders. Figure 8 represents the RDA WGs and the HE-funded projects dealing with the federation domain. Just two RDA WG's were mapped to this activity domain.

Figure 8. Kumu map of RDA WGs related to 'wide user base' domain and HE-funded projects

Both INFRAEOSC and ERA-OS projects cover the FAIR compliance domain of activity. There is only one INFRAEOSC project affiliated to this domain which is Skills4EOSC and five ERA-OS projects: VERITY, POIESIS, IANUS, PATTERN and ALMASI.

Table 15. RDA Working Groups relevant to 'wide user base' domain of activity

Capacity Development for Agriculture Data WG
RDA/CODATA Summer Schools in Data Science and Cloud Computing in the Developing World WG

From the analysis, the RDA WGs affiliated to wide user base domain refers to:

- Domain specific activity, with '[Capacity Development for Agriculture Data](#)' WG;
- Domain agnostic activity, with '[RDA/CODATA Summer Schools in Data Science and Cloud Computing in the Developing World](#)' WG

The only INFRAEOSC project related to this domain is the domain agnostic [Skills4EOSC](#) project, which focuses on upskilling the workforce to effectively operate EOSC related services. The ERA-OS projects

under the wide user base domain mainly refers to trustability, with [VERITY](#), [POIESIS](#), [IANUS](#), [PATTERN](#) and [ALMASI](#) projects.

Further detail and analysis on all five activity domains can be found in their respective sections in Annex 2.

4.2. Mapping of RDA Working Groups (WGs) to future OS-related HE-funded projects

This section assess the alignment between the RDA WGs activities to the future HE-funded projects, particularly regarding the upcoming calls for proposals under the INFRAEOSC and ERA-OS calls, as well as also the next EOSC development phases, the ERA Agenda Policy 2025-2027, and the future HE framework programme 2028-2034.

4.2.1. Future INFRAEOSC funded projects and EOSC strategy

The 2021-2027 phase of EOSC development plan is focused on ‘convergence phase’, which aims to support the implementation of strategic priorities identified in the Multi-Annual Roadmap (MAR) and Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA) (for further detail on the relevance of RDA WGs to specific aspects of the SRIA and MAR please see section 3 above and Annex 1 at the end of this document).

From the analysis, the 32 analysed INFRAEOSC projects were funded under the 2022-2024 call for proposals, and can be considered as a good but partial representative sample of the activity domains covered by the 2021-2027 phase of the EOSC development. With a predominance of INFRAEOSC projects (14 out of 32) focusing on the scalability activity domain, these results highlight that INFRAEOSC projects' domains of activities are aligned with the EOSC development phase.

Thus, we can map the future INFRAEOSC domains of activity based on the next EOSC development stages and predict the future related activity.

The next phase of the EOSC development, scheduled for 2027, will focus on the operational phase of the deployment of services to offer a trusted environment for researchers in Europe³¹. This phase suggests an increase of INFRAEOSC-call for proposals focusing on scalability but also on the federation and policy evolution domains to foster technical and legal cooperation between services

³¹ European Commission: Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, IDEA Consult, PPMI and UNU-MERIT, *Evaluation study on excellent science in the European framework programmes for research and innovation – Phase 2 – EOSC partnership report*, Publications Office of the European Union, 2024, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/7356844>

or infrastructures, as well as on the wider user base domain to ease their accessibility with knowledgeable users.

4.2.2. Future ERA-OS funded projects and ERA Policy Agenda strategy

From the analysis, the 17 analysed ERA-OS projects were funded under the 2022-2024 call for proposals, which correspond to the [ERA Agenda Policy 2022-2024](#). 93% of the ERA-OS projects' activities are covered by two domains: the policy evolution (64%) and the wide user base domains (29%) (for more details on this evaluation, see Annex 2).

ERA-OS projects align with the first priority area of the ERA Policy Agenda 2022-2024 entitled: 'Deepening a truly functioning internal market for knowledge' which actions to implement this priority.³² Based on this, we can map future ERA-OS activity domains using the upcoming ERA Policy Agenda actions under this Priority Area and anticipate the future related activity.

The new ERA Policy Agenda is covering the 2025-2027 and introduces new ERA actions of the priority area 1 which focus on³³:

- Promoting equity in OS,
- Advancing the European Science for Policy (S4P) ecosystem,
- Facilitating and accelerating the responsible use of AI in science in the EU,
- Enhancing research security³⁴.

Based on this trend, we can suggest that the future ERA-OS projects will strengthen activities in the policy evolution domain, but as well as in the federation domain, to reduce technical and legal barriers and enhance synergies. The continuous emergence of new technologies will also drive an increase in activities within the wide user base domain.

4.2.3. Future Horizon Europe Framework Programme 2028-2034

The future HE framework programme, which will cover the 2028-2034 period, will be organised into four pillars³⁵, so one more pillar than the current three-pillars HE 2021-2027 (see Figure 9 below). This new pillar is called the European Research Area (ERA).

³² See the following documents: [The Match-up... ERA Actions by Priority Areas](#) and [ERA Factsheet No.5: Results from the Horizon Europe ERA Calls: Exploring the Facts and Figures](#)

³³ https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=OJ:C_202503593

³⁴

https://european-research-area.ec.europa.eu/sites/default/files/documents/2025-02/COM_2025_62_F1_PROPOSAL_FOR_A_RECOMMENDATION_EN_V5_P1_3951028.PDF

³⁵ European Commission: Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, *Europe's budget – Horizon Europe (2028-2034)*, Publications Office of the European Union, 2025, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/8979807>

Figure 9. Structure of the current and future Horizon Europe work programmes. Work programmes focusing on OS implementation within the 2021-2027 HE programme are highlighted in pink.³⁶

Thus, the Research Infrastructures (RIs) work programme, which is currently including the INFRAEOSC calls and funding projects, will be integrated into the new ERA pillar, as well as the ERA calls of the WIDERA work programme. This new organisation clearly highlights the central role of ERA within the future HE framework programme, emphasising the positioning of the RIs and EOSC-related initiatives objectives to be more closely aligned with the ambitions of the ERA Agenda Policy.

4.3. Summary

The mapping of RDA WGs with the current and future HE-funded projects reveals a considerable complementarity based on their activity domains, reflecting a close relationship between RDA community and EOSC and OS-related HE projects and ambitions.

The analysis shows that, even if the RDA WGs address the same activity domains as current HE-funded projects, their approaches can differ, providing a broader view of the domain and its various components. While RDA WGs focus their activities mainly on digital objects, INFRAEOSC projects approach the domain from a services perspective, whereas ERA-OS projects concentrate on impact and assessment approaches, by producing evidence-base for policymakers. This triangular approach across all domains highlights the complementarity between the two ecosystems: RDA community and HE work programmes.

³⁶ Figure adapted from 'How Horizon Europe was developed' and Horizon Europe factsheet

By using this methodology to map the activities of RDA WGs with current HE-funded projects, we are able to anticipate future activity domains of the HE-funded projects based on roadmap documents. Indeed, the future activity domains of INFRAEOSC projects were estimated based on the EOSC development phase described in the EOSC partnership report³⁷, while the upcoming activity domains of ERA-OS projects were projected from the forthcoming ERA Policy Agenda 2025-2027³⁸.

This analysis reveals that the RDA community and specifically its WGs are concerned with the activities related to the development and implementation of EOSC and OS practically, and that they also produce (and will continue to produce) outputs that have the potential to be directly implementable by both current projects and future projects.

5. RDA and European Research Infrastructures

RDA Working Groups (WGs) are also relevant to European Research Infrastructures (RIs). To understand better the potential for exchange and collaboration between the RIs and the RDA, we mapped the current [European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures \(ESFRI\) Roadmap](#) and [Landscape Analysis](#), and in particular the challenges these documents identify for the ESFRI landscape, as well as the recognised [European Research Infrastructure Consortia \(ERICs\)](#) to the activity areas and focus of RDA TIGER-supported RDA Working Groups. See Annex 3 for further information on the methodology for this mapping. Such mapping provides an impression of the overlapping activity focus and shared interest between the European RIs and the RDA community and suggests that RDA can provide a useful forum where to develop technical and social solutions to the data-related challenges that the RIs in Europe face.

5.1. ESFRI Roadmap and RDA TIGER-supported RDA WGs

The ESFRI Roadmap 2021 and the ESFRI Landscape Analysis 2024 identified a number of challenges impacting the ESFRI landscape. RIs are becoming increasingly integrated and cross-disciplinary and interdisciplinary; they need to be conceived and deployed at an increasingly global scale to respond to complex scientific and socio-economic challenges³⁹. The ESFRI landscape is also facing complex organisational and funding challenges arising from the need for interdisciplinary and cross-disciplinary approaches, as well as from the continued integration of the R&I ecosystem in

³⁷ European Commission: Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, IDEA Consult, PPMI and UNU-MERIT, *Evaluation study on excellent science in the European framework programmes for research and innovation – Phase 2 – EOSC partnership report*, Publications Office of the European Union, 2024, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/7356844>

³⁸ <https://european-research-area.ec.europa.eu/era-policy-agenda-2025-2027>

³⁹ ESFRI Roadmap 2021, Challenges and Strategies for the Future, p. 24; ESFRI Landscape Analysis 2024, pp. 117-118.

Europe and the development of EOSC and the expected consolidation of e-infrastructure service provisioning and federation of services⁴⁰. ESFRI Cluster projects support collaboration between ESFRIs and linking them to EOSC. There are currently 5 such clusters: [PaNOSC](#), [ENVRI](#), [LifeScience RI](#), [ESCAPE](#), and [SSHOC](#). RDA WGs develop technical and social solutions that can support RIs in responding to the challenges related to increasing consolidation, integration and federation. RDA TIGER-supported RDA WGs, like for example the [RDA Global Open Research Commons International Model \(GORC IM\) WG](#) and the [RDA GORC International Implementations \(GORC II\) WG](#), offer outputs that support interoperability between research environments and infrastructures and their work can help ESFRIs to respond to challenges impacting the RI landscape in Europe.

The engagement of ESFRIs with EOSC has also facilitated the development of FAIR-by-design data management practices in RIs and the sharing of these practices between clusters and across RIs in different domains.⁴¹ The ESFRI Roadmap 2021 recognised RIs as both key providers of data and services to EOSC, as well as the key consumers of EOSC services.⁴² In this regard, RDA WGs that develop solutions in support of FAIR implementation can be of high potential interest and impact to ESFRIs. All RDA TIGER-supported WGs, for example, “concretely align, harmonise and standardise Open Science developments and technologies”⁴³, and develop outputs that facilitate FAIR implementation at either cross-domain or domain-specific level.

At domain level, both ESFRI Roadmap 2021 and ESFRI Landscape Analysis 2024 highlighted specific challenges the thematic RIs are facing. Data standardisation and data quality were identified as a key challenge across thematic areas, with the 2024 report linking these issues to RIs capacity to integrate and benefit from new technical advances (e.g. AI)⁴⁴. Several RDA TIGER-supported RDA WGs produce outputs that respond to this challenge, including, for example, the [RDA Wind Energy Community Standards WG](#) for the Energy thematic area, the [RDA I-ADOPT WG](#) for the Environment thematic area, [the RDA Multi-omics Metadata Standards Integration \(MOMSI\) WG](#), the [RDA FAIRification of Genomic Annotations WG](#) and the [RDA Computational Modelling of Health Data WG](#) for the Health and Food thematic area, the [RDA Harmonised terminologies and schemas for FAIR data in material science and related domains WG](#) for the Physical and Engineering thematic area, and the [RDA Alignment of multilingual vocabularies in social sciences and humanities WG](#) for the Social and Cultural Innovation thematic area. Moreover, WGs like the [RDA FAIR Mappings WG](#), the [RDA FAIR](#)

⁴⁰ ESFRI Roadmap 2021, Landscape Analysis, p. 47; ESFRI Landscape Analysis 2024, pp. 118-120.

⁴¹ ESFRI Roadmap 2021, Landscape Analysis, p. 121.

⁴² ESFRI Roadmap 2021, Landscape Analysis, p. 158.

⁴³ See the RDA TIGER Open Call:

<https://www.rd-alliance.org/working-groups/rda-tiger/open-call-rda-working-group-facilitation-support/>

⁴⁴ ESFRI Roadmap 2021, Landscape Analysis, Thematic Areas; ESFRI Landscape Analysis 2024, pp. 24, 54, 70, 93, 110.

[Data Maturity Model WG](#) and the [RDA Data Granularity WG](#) support data standardisation and harmonisation across domains.

The ESFRI Roadmap 2021 and the ESFRI Landscape Analysis 2024 also identified ethical and legal considerations, Artificial Intelligence, and data management and stewardship as challenges across several thematic areas, including Energy, Health and Food, Physical Sciences and Engineering, and Social and Cultural Innovation/Social Sciences and Humanities. There is an increasing number of RDA WGs that identify best practice, develop guidance and produce technical and social solutions to address these challenges. Among the RDA TIGER-supported RDA WGs, for example, the [EOSC-Future/RDA Artificial Intelligence and Data Visitation WG](#), the [RDA Building Immune Digital Twins WG](#) and the [RDA Health Data Commons GORC Profile WG](#) develop outputs that support RIs in approaching challenges related to ethics and AI across the Health and Food and Social and Cultural Innovation domains.

5.2. RDA TIGER-supported RDA Working Groups and the ERICs

Moving from the ESFRI landscape level to individual RI level, we continue to see that RDA WGs develop technical and social solutions relevant to European RIs. The mapping here considered RDA TIGER-supported RDA WGs and ERICs with reference to the RDA taxonomy for the technology focus (see Annex 3 for a discussion of methodology). The mapping reveals a landscape of overlapping interest and activity areas.

Figure 10: Kumu visualisation of the mapping between RDA TIGER-supported RDA WGs and ERICs

RDA TIGER “Research Data Alliance facilitation of Targeted International working Groups for EOSC-related Research solutions” is funded by HORIZON-INFRA-2022-EOSC-0, Project:101094406.

[Mapping Research Data Alliance Working Groups to European Research Infrastructures](#)

A number of RDA TIGER-supported RDA WGs develop discipline-agnostic technical and social solutions related to access management and licenses, search and discovery, ingest and appraisal that are of relevance to most ERICs. These WGs include groups like the [RDA Global Open Research Commons International Model \(GORC IM\) WG](#) and the [RDA GORC International Implementations \(GORC II\) WG](#) that developed and now maintain the GORC IM, which provides a framework for developing individual research commons and for furthering interoperability between research commons, but also RDA WGs like the RDA [National PID Strategy WG](#), [RDA FAIR Mappings WG](#), [RDA Data Granularity WG](#), [RDA FAIR Data Maturity Model WG](#), and [RDA Mapping the Landscape of Digital Research Tools II \(MaLDReth II\) WG](#) that respond to more specific, but still discipline-agnostic challenges related to access management and licenses, search and discovery, and ingest and appraisal.

Other RDA TIGER-supported RDA WGs with a more specialised technology focus are relevant to a cross-disciplinary section of ERICs due to the specific activity areas of those ERICs. These include RDA WGs like the [RDA Common maDMP API WG](#), which is relevant to those ERICs whose activities include data (output) management planning, and the [RDA/WDS TRUST Principles Outreach and Adoption WG](#), whose work is relevant to RIs across the ERIC landscape that actively work on data archiving and long-term preservation.

A number of ERICs also integrate approaches and methods from across disciplines, meaning that even RDA WGs with a more specialised technology or disciplinary focus can still be relevant to a cross-disciplinary section of ERICs. For example, [RDA Small Uncrewed Aircraft and Autonomous Platforms Data WG](#) that develops standards and best practice for data coming from drones can be of relevance to both Life-Watch ERIC (Environment) as well as E-RIHS (Social and Cultural Innovation) as both RIs cover domains that work with data collected by drones. The [EOSC-Future/RDA Artificial Intelligence and Data Visitation \(AIDV\) WG](#) has produced outputs relevant to ERICs in the Health & Food, Environment, and Social and Cultural Innovation domains that implement, or plan to implement, environments that support data visitation.

There are also RDA WGs that address domain specific challenges related to FAIR and CARE implementation and based on our mapping are relevant only to ERICs in those domains. From among RDA TIGER-supported RDA WGs for example, the [RDA Alignment of multilingual vocabularies in the](#)

[social sciences and humanities WG](#) that develops recommendations for FAIR multilingual controlled vocabulary development is likely of relevance to ERICs in the Social and Cultural Innovation domain; the [RDA I-ADOPT WG](#) developed a framework for representing observable properties that is likely most relevant to ERICs in the Environment domain; and the [RDA Multi-omics Metadata Standards Integration \(MOMSI\) WG](#) and the [RDA FAIRification of Genomic Annotations WG](#) are likely most relevant to ERICs in the Health and Food domain.

We identified only two RDA TIGER-supported RDA WGs - [RDA Wind Energy Community Standards WG](#) and [RDA/ReSA Policies in Research Organisations for Research Software \(PRO4RS\) WG](#) - that we could not map to ERICs using the RDA technology focus taxonomy. However, this does not mean that these groups and their outputs are irrelevant to the ERIC landscape. For example, the resources and guidance offered by the PRO4RS WG in support of institutional research software policy development⁴⁵ can benefit those ERICs whose data management policies also incorporate research software or that intend to update their data management policies to include research software management.

5.3. RDA as a Partner for ESFRIs and ERICs

The mapping of RDA TIGER-supported RDA WGs to the ESFRI Roadmap 2021 and the ERIC landscape reveals a close overlap in the technology focus on RDA TIGER-supported RDA WGs and ERICs as well as a close relevance of those WGs to addressing the challenges facing the ESFRI landscape. As the European RI landscape becomes more complex, more cross-disciplinary, and more globally engaged, RDA as a global, community-based organisation can provide a forum where to develop solutions to the technical and social data-related challenges ESFRIs face. A number of experts from ERICs, and the broader ESFRI landscape, already actively contribute to the activities of RDA WGs. The ESFRI Landscape Analysis 2024 also recognises RDA as a venue to address cross-disciplinary challenges.⁴⁶ This mapping suggests that there is potential for ever greater collaboration between the RDA Community and the RI communities, and that ESFRIs can benefit from the adoption of RDA Recommendations and Outputs, in particular as such adoption, at least at formal level, still remains limited.⁴⁷

⁴⁵ Barker, M., Cohen, J., Hernández Serrano, P. V., Katz, D. S., Martin, K., Rudmann, D., & Shanahan, H. (2025). PRO4RS WG Final Report (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17330928>

⁴⁶ ESFRI Landscape Analysis 2024, p. 25.

⁴⁷ Formal adoption of RDA Recommendations and Outputs by ERICs remains low. RDA Adoption Stories catalogue includes one Adoption Story submitted by CLARIN-ERIC <https://www.rd-alliance.org/adoption-stories/making-social-sciences-and-humanities-language-datasets-accessible-for-humans-and-machines/>

6. Mapping of RDA WG outputs to European National Strategies

Many European countries have adopted national Open Science policies.⁴⁸ These public policies outline strategies and recommendations to further Open Science, in conformity with the EU Directive on Open Data and the Re-use Public Sector Information (PSI Directive).⁴⁹ Mapping both RDA Interest and Working Group activities to European national Open Science policies demonstrates how the RDA's community-driven approach addresses specific strategic needs across Europe. This taxonomy-based mapping analysis identifies current focus areas where the RDA effectively supports national Open Science policies, as well as future focus areas where the RDA can focus to strengthen the European research data landscape in the future.

The methodology employed for this section centred around mapping both the set of RDA Groups and the National Open Science Policies, using the FOSTER Open Science Taxonomy⁵⁰ as the framework to establish these connections. Relevant documentation on National Open Science policies (or equivalent documents) was sourced for all 27 European Union Member states. These were analysed using [Claude.ai](#) and mapped to the FOSTER Taxonomy. A similar approach was taken for the 1943 RDA WGs and IGs, with these mapped onto the FOSTER Taxonomy. A detailed summary of the methodology employed here, including the prompts used for [Claude.ai](#), an AI disclaimer, and the initial findings of the analysis of National Open Science Policies, can be found in Annex 4 in Part 3 below.

6.1 Representation of mapping

The FOSTER Open Science taxonomy-based mapping of RDA groups to European national Open Science policies was visualised using [Kumu.io](#), a web-based platform for creating interactive network visualisations and system maps (Figure 11 below).

⁴⁸ Rochambeau, M., Konach, T., & Schmolmüller, A. (2022). Report on existing policies and guidelines. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10687296>

⁴⁹

<https://www.europeansources.info/record/directive-eu-2019-1024-on-open-data-and-the-re-use-of-public-sector-information/>

⁵⁰ Pontika, N., Knoth, P., Cancellieri, M., & Pearce, S. (2015). Fostering open science to research using a taxonomy and an eLearning portal. *In Proceedings of the 15th International Conference on Knowledge Technologies and Data-driven Business* (pp. 1–8). i-KNOW '15: 15th International Conference on Knowledge Technologies and Data-Driven Business. ACM.

Figure 11. Interactive visualisation of the taxonomy-based mapping of Research Data Alliance groups to European national Open Science policies.

[Mapping Research Data Alliance Groups to European National Open Science Policies: A Taxonomy-based Analysis](#)⁵¹

The interactive map allows the user to explore the connection between RDA Groups and European national Open Science policies via multiple pathways. A user can select individual European member states (27 elements decorated by national flags, central circle) to examine their national policy document (see Figure 12 below) or select specific Open Science taxonomy domains (28 colour-coded elements, outer circle) to discover and read descriptions of RDA groups relevant to those domains (Figure 13).

⁵¹ <https://embed.kumu.io/052d014588ac21f5aaf7ec639c6845e7>

RDA TIGER “Research Data Alliance facilitation of Targeted International working Groups for EOSC-related Research solutions” is funded by HORIZON-INFRA-2022-EOSC-0, Project:101094406.

Figure 12. Austria’s National Open Science policy description and its connections with Open Science taxonomy domains.

Figure 13. Research Data Alliance (RDA) groups relevant to the ‘Open Source Software’ taxonomy domain (profile, left panel).

The colour-coded connection lines between countries and taxonomy domains show how each national policy addresses specific Open Science domains, with different colours indicating coverage levels. Users can filter using buttons (top centre) to display connections by coverage intensity. **0 (NOT SPECIFICALLY ADDRESSED)** indicates Open Science taxonomy domains not specifically addressed in national policy documents; **1 (PARTIAL)** addresses limited domains; **2 (COMPREHENSIVE)** covers most domains; and, **3 (FULL)** shows countries addressing all taxonomy domains (see Figure 14 below).

Figure 14. Open Science taxonomy domains fully addressed by the Austrian Open Science policy are illustrated by green connections within the map.

Clicking on any coloured line shows detailed information about how that country's policy covers that Open Science domain, including direct quotes from the policy document as supporting evidence (see Figure 15 below).

Figure 15. Coverage information for the Austrian national Open Science policy within the Open Source Software domain (profile, left panel).

6.2 Results and Analysis

Analysis of national Open Science policies across 27 European countries reveals distinct patterns in current policy strengths and emerging opportunities, with findings interpreted within the methodological framework described above.

6.2.1. Current Focus: Building Foundations for Open Science

European countries prioritise foundational Open Science infrastructure, with Repository Systems achieving universal coverage across all countries, recognising digital repositories as essential ecosystem components. Near-universal adoption of Open Access Policies, Research Data Management, Data Sharing, Data Standards, Impact Assessment, and Ethics frameworks indicates countries focus on core requirements: policies mandating access, systems for responsible data management, interoperable protocols, and ethical guidelines. These domains represent the *minimum requirements* for participating in the global research ecosystem, establishing the foundation for advanced Open Science practices.

6.2.2. RDA Groups Supporting Existing Strengths

The RDA actively supports these foundational strengths through Working and Interest Groups that enhance policy implementation and technical capabilities. For repository systems, the [Data Repository Attributes Working Group](#) defines essential characteristics and quality indicators that strengthen national repository infrastructure, while the [RDA/WDS Certification of Digital Repositories Interest Group](#) establishes trust frameworks that complement countries' universal repository policies. Open access policies benefit from the [Research Data Policy Interest Group's](#) frameworks for policy development across stakeholders, and the [Research Funders and Stakeholders Interest Group](#) that coordinates mandates and incentives.

Research data management capabilities are reinforced through practical tools like the [DMP Common Standards Working Group's](#) standardised formats for data management plans, and the [Active Data Management Plans Interest Group's](#) frameworks for dynamic, machine-actionable data management plans that facilitate data sharing throughout the research lifecycle. Data sharing practices benefit from the [Data Citation Working Group's](#) citation standards and the [FAIR Data Maturity Model Working Group's](#) assessment frameworks for evaluating and improving data FAIRness. Data standards development receives comprehensive support through the [FAIRsharing Registry](#) that maintains connections between policies, standards, and repositories, while multiple groups like [Data Foundation and Terminology Working Group](#) and [Metadata Standards Catalog Working Group](#) provide the technical vocabularies essential for interoperability. These RDA outputs assist countries

in implementing their national policy commitments and provide shared infrastructure for effective Open Science implementation.

6.2.3. Future Focus: Emerging Policy Opportunities

European countries have opportunities to develop policies in emerging Open Science domains that are gaining recognition in the research community. Open Source Hardware and Collaborative Review remain unaddressed in European national Open Science policies, reflecting their status as emerging practices that have yet to gain mainstream policy recognition. Real-time Documentation and Review Transparency, with minimal national policy coverage, represent approaches to transparent research that could enhance how scientific processes are conducted and communicated.

Educational domains like Open Teaching Resources and Open Learning Platforms show early development, indicating awareness of open education but limited policy coverage. Reproducibility Tools and Alternative Metrics, while still emerging, demonstrate slightly higher recognition as countries begin to acknowledge their critical role in research integrity and impact assessment. These domains represent areas of Open Science where practices are developing ahead of formal policy frameworks, creating opportunities for countries to advance their Open Science strategies.

6.2.4. RDA Groups Supporting Policy Evolution

The RDA provides valuable infrastructure and frameworks that could significantly advance European national policies in these emerging Open Science domains. For Open Source Hardware, the [FAIR Principles for Research Hardware Interest Group](#) offers established frameworks for making hardware designs findable, accessible, and reusable, while the [Persistent Identification of Instruments Working Group](#) provides identification systems for research instruments that could support hardware attribution and discovery. Collaborative Review and Review Transparency benefit from the [Evaluation of Research Interest Group's](#) perspectives on alternative assessment methods and the [SHARC Interest Group's](#) recognition systems that could incentivise transparent peer review participation, while the [Data Usage Metrics Working Group](#) creates transparent indicators that could revolutionise how review processes are measured and communicated.

Reproducibility Tools receive support through multiple RDA groups supporting policy implementation pathways. The [FAIR for Research Software Working Group](#) provides established principles for computational reproducibility, while the recently established [RDA Reproducibility Checklist Working Group](#) aims to develop systematic evaluation tools that countries could integrate into research quality frameworks. The [Data Versioning Interest Group](#) and [Research Data Provenance Interest Group](#) offer technical standards for tracking research processes, providing solutions for ensuring reproducible research practices.

Alternative Metrics benefit from RDA outputs that transform how research impact is measured and rewarded. The [Data Citation Working Group's](#) standards enable new forms of impact measurement, while the [Data Usage Metrics Working Group](#) develops metrics for measuring research data usage and impact, complementing traditional article-based metrics. The [SHARC Interest Group](#) provides recognition systems that countries could adopt to incentivise broader research activities including data sharing and collaboration.

Open educational domains receive strong support through groups developing practical implementation pathways. Open Teaching Resources can leverage the [Education and Training on Handling of Research Data Interest Group's](#) comprehensive curricula, while Open Learning Platforms benefit from the [FAIR for Virtual Research Environments Working Group](#) and [Virtual Research Environment Interest Group](#), which develop technical standards that could be applied to development of collaborative open learning infrastructure. These RDA outputs represent established solutions that forward-thinking countries could incorporate into their policy frameworks, transforming emerging practices into systematic national capabilities.

6.3 Summary

The RDA provides immediate implementation opportunities for strengthening and advancing European national Open Science policies through the work of its diverse community groups. Countries could prioritise leveraging RDA frameworks for reproducibility tools, open peer review, and educational resources to address the significant policy gaps, while fostering collaboration with established RDA groups that support data management and repository systems. Cross-cutting groups, such as the [Evaluation of Research IG](#) and [Sharing Rewards and Credit \(SHARC\) IG](#), offer particular value by developing alternative assessment methods that can simultaneously advance multiple emerging domains, enabling European countries to integrate emerging research practices into their national policy frameworks and advance their national Open Science strategies.

7. Community engagement activities in support of the landscape analysis

During the lifetime of the RDA TIGER project, a number of targeted events were held to engage with stakeholders beyond the project consortium and to gather broader community perspectives. These external activities complemented the analyses conducted for this report by leveraging the existing strengths of the global RDA community and incorporating both Europe-focused and international contributions to ensure that the insights informing this report reflect diverse regional and disciplinary contexts. Section 7 provides key results of these socialising activities and highlights recurring

concerns while demonstrating the role RDA can play in addressing them. The methodology and expansive results of each engagement activity are provided in Annex 5.

7.1. RDA TIGER Cross-fertilisation webinars

The project organised five cross-fertilisation webinars planned around the following themes:

- [Semantic Interoperability](#) (November 2024)
- [\(Meta\)Data Standards](#) (December 2024)
- [FAIR/CARE/TRUST Principles adoption](#) (December 2024)
- [Making mappings FAIR](#) (November 2025)
- [Repositories, trustworthiness and certification](#) (December 2025)

A recurring challenge that was raised across the series was the **need for greater harmonisation of community-developed outputs developed in the Open Data and Open Science ecosystems, with the goal of addressing the fragmentation in the landscape described in the SRIA, enhancing interoperability and subsequent uptake of these shared solutions**. RDA TIGER provided a forum for alignment towards producing solutions for the identified gaps and challenges, not only among RDA WGs but between the RDA and other European actors. Concrete examples of the value of such alignment are

- A. The resulting outputs of the FAIRification of Genomic Annotations WG using the FAIR Mappings WG work on how to describe mappings into its recommendations for a minimal FAIR metadata schema for genomic annotations, and;
- B. The upcoming collaborations between the EOSC EDEN and FIDELIS projects and the Technical Repository Service Providers RDA WG as a result of these cross-fertilisation webinars.

The resulting collaborations also demonstrate the value of initiatives like RDA TIGER in de-fragmenting and harmonising the European landscape. This can be achieved by facilitating these discussions on common causes, making connections more explicit, operationalising collaborations and providing the global perspectives that are a feature of the RDA community.

7.2. ‘Community insights on use, adoption and impact of RDA Outputs’ workshop

In April 2025 RDA TIGER held a session at RDA Virtual Plenary 24 titled “Community insights on use, adoption and impact of RDA Outputs”⁵² exploring the different ways in which the community uses

⁵² A recording of the session is available on Youtube <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=BkMiGDscII0> ; a link to the slidedeck used can be found on the RDA VP24 programme page: <https://www.rd-alliance.org/plenaries/p24/programme-24/>

RDA outputs and recommendations. The session intended to provide early direction for this report and a better understanding about how RDA Recommendations and Supporting Outputs can be leveraged to address concerns across institutional, disciplinary and regional boundaries.

The key outcome of this session is the recurring topic of a **need for fostering dialogue between different communities who are working on shared or similar issues, and the need for practical and active coordination of efforts taking place at disciplinary, organisational and sometimes individual levels**. This clear indication towards a need for alignment reiterates that an opportunity exists for EOSC to strategically leverage the RDA community and adoption of its Groups' outputs as a common reference point for aligning practices, stimulating dialogue between communities, and coordinating implementation activities so that local efforts can scale into shared European solutions.

7.3. Mapping of RDA outputs to European National Strategies: Outcomes from the RDA in Europe Summit

As coherence and alignment at a national level underpins endeavours to federate infrastructures and services within the EOSC ecosystem, RDA TIGER endeavoured to consult the community on the most common issues identified in the analysis of section 6 'Mapping of RDA outputs to European National Strategies', aiming to support practical next steps coming out of this report. A white paper is in preparation⁵³ due to be published in January 2026 with a full account of the sessions and recommendations.

The first of these is that cross-country dialogues on policy are needed at the European level. The SRIA addresses this point directly in relation to the General Objective 3: 'Establish a sustainable and federated infrastructure enabling open sharing of scientific results'; there is a specific national level priority outlined in the Multi-Annual Roadmap to "encourage national policy makers to review and adjust national policies and regulations to enable services to be used in a cross-border context, and engage in a series of in-depth trials to evaluate the utility of proposed resourcing models to agree approaches for EOSC."⁵⁴ These discussions can be facilitated by the RDA community with the potential solutions presented by RDA WG outputs for addressing concerns described in national policies playing a role in this. Establishing mechanisms for translating global RDA WG outputs into regional practices would facilitate this coordinated alignment of national level policies.

A second significant conclusion arising from these roundtable discussions was that Europe can learn from less well-resourced parts of the world outside the region. Europe has the ambition to lead the

⁵³ Reserved doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18097746>

⁵⁴ SRIA, p.172

way in terms of science and research on a global stage, also based on the aim of positioning EOSC as the “European component of a Global Open Research Commons”.⁵⁵ It is therefore important to consider the advantageous global component of RDA, as it brings together its community and proposes solutions in a non-hierarchical approach; that is to say, no region’s concerns are prioritised over others’ when Groups choose their areas of focus.

These RDA TIGER consultations at the RDA in Europe Summit event highlight the shared set of national challenges across Europe and demonstrated strong community interest in aligning these with broader EOSC ambitions and concerns. They also pointed to the value of EOSC engaging more deeply with the globally diverse RDA community, using its inclusive, non-hierarchical perspective to strengthen the continued development of the EOSC.

8. Recommendations

Recommendation A: Activity alignment in a rich, multi-stakeholder European environment

- Based on RDA TIGER’s effort to socialise the impact of RDA WGs in EOSC and Europe in general, there is a clear need for closer collaboration between RDA, EOSC and other major actors in Europe, working towards a less fragmented environment and removing duplication of effort. The reuse and sharing of data according to the FAIR principles which underpins EOSC needs to be supported by community-developed and endorsed solutions that are adaptable across boundaries.

Recommendation B: International cooperation for European solutions

- Many of the RDA outputs highlighted as potential solutions for EOSC and European-related challenges have been adopted and operationalised by initiatives outside Europe. RDA is not only the venue where these solutions are developed, but can also be the platform where knowledge exchange between EOSC and global counterparts should take place. The relationship should be fostered to allow EOSC to realise its ambition to continue to be competitive in the global data economy, while also cooperating with other international counterparts in a global setting.

Recommendation C: EOSC Association Opportunity Area Expert Groups, Task Forces and adopted RDA solutions

- The purview of EOSC Association Opportunity Area Expert Groups and Task Forces is closely linked to the key action areas, priorities, gaps and challenges described throughout the SRIA.

⁵⁵ SRIA, p.13

As these groups and future iterations continue in their work, newly formed OAEs and TFs should engage with RDA and use this report and the extensive mapping of RDA Working Groups to SRIA Implementation Challenges and MAR General Objectives as an example for the potential available solutions within the RDA community, especially those that have been widely implemented and adopted (see Annex 2 below for more information on the relevance of RDA WG outputs to OAEs and EOSC TFs).

Recommendation D: RDA to play integral role in policy evolution and FAIR compliance in Europe

- The analysis highlighted cross-cutting concerns of the funding streams (i.e., Scalability, Federation, Policy evolution, FAIR compliance, and Wider user base); it is clear from this that the RDA WGs activities map more strongly onto ‘Policy evolution’ and ‘FAIR compliance’. For future funding calls that address these concerns, a directive can be included by the funder for consortia to engage with suitable RDA WGs and report this dialogue in periodic reports; This alignment will enable projects to identify existing solutions and where possible make connections with those who have adopted or implemented these solutions for insights on how these concerns are being practically addressed.

9. Conclusion

This report demonstrates that the RDA, reinforced through the targeted support provided to the community by the RDA TIGER project, has become an integral contributor to the development of EOSC and the wider European research ecosystem. By aligning globally developed, community-driven solutions with European priorities, RDA provides practical mechanisms for addressing the technical, organisational, and social challenges that underpin Open Science and data sharing in Europe. The analysis highlights how RDA can act as a foundational partner whose outputs can be readily implemented to support EOSC’s current operations and future evolution.

The report also highlights the importance of international cooperation in delivering European solutions. Many RDA outputs relevant to EOSC have already been successfully adopted outside Europe, demonstrating their robustness and adaptability. RDA therefore provides not only a source of technical and policy solutions, but also a platform for global knowledge exchange. Strengthening the relationship between EOSC and RDA will allow Europe to remain competitive in the global data economy while actively contributing to, and benefiting from, international Open Science developments.

The analysis underscores RDA’s critical role in supporting policy evolution and FAIR compliance in Europe. RDA activities align particularly strongly with these cross-cutting priorities, offering

frameworks and practices that can be embedded into funded projects and national strategies. Encouraging structured engagement with RDA in future funding programmes would strengthen policy coherence, promote reuse of existing solutions, and ensure that EOSC development continues to be grounded in globally coordinated, community-driven standards.

A central conclusion is that stronger alignment and coordination across the European Open Science landscape is both necessary and achievable. The diversity of actors involved in EOSC, while a strength, has also contributed to fragmentation and duplication of effort. RDA offers a proven, neutral forum where interoperable, FAIR-enabling solutions are co-developed and endorsed by the community. Closer collaboration between RDA, EOSC bodies, and other major European initiatives would enable greater reuse of existing solutions, reduce inefficiencies, and accelerate progress towards a more coherent and sustainable EOSC ecosystem.

PART C: ANNEXES

Annex 1: Background and Methodology for Mapping of RDA Working Groups to EOSC Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda

This annex contains further information regarding the methodology and analysis of Section 3: Mapping of RDA Working Groups to EOSC Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda.

Methodology

The methodology employed for the mapping of RDA WGs to aspects of the EOSC Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda consisted primarily of desk-based research; the overall focus areas of each WG were examined and associated with the Action Areas and General Objectives where relevant. This analysis was underpinned by a close reading and interpretation of the documents associated with RDA Working Groups (Statements of Work, and all WG Outputs) and a similarly close reading of the SRIA. It should be noted here that this analysis is subject to the same potential shortcomings as other subjective analyses. The results of the mapping of RDA WGs to SRIA Implementation Challenges has been recorded and made available via the [Kumu.io](https://kumu.io)-enabled mapping software with the possibility of being updated at a later date.⁵⁶

Background

In mapping the activities of RDA WGs to the SRIA Implementation Challenges, the decision was made to not limit the WGs to only one Implementation Challenge; as is shown in Table 16 below, the work of the majority of WGs was of relevance to more than one Implementation Challenge. 58 RDA WGs overall were of relevance to at least one Implementation Challenge, with 11 of no relevance to any Implementation Challenges. The high proportion of RDA WGs of relevance to more than one SRIA Implementation Challenge (i.e., 34 WGs) can be understood when considering that while WGs often focus on a specific issue, these issues cannot be addressed without taking into consideration other related issues (for example, a WG focused on User environments within a specific discipline will often need to address Resource providers environments for researchers in this discipline; or a WG aiming to develop guidelines for ontologies will take into account existing interoperability frameworks, like the EOSC Interoperability Framework).

Table 16. Number of RDA WGs relevant to SRIA Implementation Challenges

⁵⁶ The representation of this mapping on Kumu can be accessed here:
<https://embed.kumu.io/98654e2d40b6855bb4025e7ced2dfde6>

WGs of relevance to 0 SRIA Implementation Challenges	11
WGs of relevance to 1 SRIA Implementation Challenge	24
WGs of relevance to 2 SRIA Implementation Challenges	20
WGs of relevance to 3 SRIA Implementation Challenges	7
WGs of relevance to 4 SRIA Implementation Challenges	6
WGs of relevance to 5 SRIA Implementation Challenges	1

Though 11 RDA WGs were not mapped onto a specific Implementation Challenge, the work of the remaining 58 WGs was deemed relevant to at least one Implementation Challenge (it is worth noting here that the WG whose work was judged relevant to five Implementation Challenges was the [WDS/RDA Assessment of Data Fitness for Use WG](#), with those Implementation Challenges being Metadata and ontologies, FAIR metrics and certification, User environments, Resource provider environments, and EOSC Interoperability Framework).

As can be seen below in Figure X, multiple WGs were associated with all seven Implementation Challenges. Figure 16 below presents the amount of WGs focusing on each SRIA Implementation Challenge, in order to provide insight into the volume of related work. The ‘EOSC Interoperability Framework’ and ‘Resource provider environments’ are the challenges most commonly addressed by RDA WGs, followed closely by ‘Metadata and ontologies’.

Figure 16. Number of WGs relevant to SRIA Implementation Challenges

A number of factors could explain the prominence of focus on these three Implementation Challenges over the other four:

- RDA WGs are mandated to focus on a specific issue or challenge they have identified and propose an output of some type (standard, guidelines, technical solutions, etc.); as such it is more achievable to produce work that addresses issues to do with domain-specific or cross-domain metadata, ontologies (and other semantic artefacts), and interoperability across various boundaries in a WG’s 18-month lifespan, than it is to address topics such as FAIR (or other) certification processes or the technical nature of Authentication and authorisation infrastructure. An illustration of this is evident when we consider that some of the most common keywords for WG areas of focus include “metadata”, “standards”, and “interoperability”.
- The preponderance of WGs who address the ‘Resource provider environments’ Implementation Challenge can be explained in part by the fact that this challenge is one which underpins much of the activity of RDA WGs on interoperability and data sharing; there are many examples of RDA WGs whose activity has focused on enabling the integration of data and other research outputs with existing infrastructures and platforms, and on creating the guidelines and standards to support this. All these activities contribute to the “composability of resources and across resource providers”, which has been identified as a priority for this Implementation Challenge.

It is also useful to look at how the RDA WGs relate to the SRIA Implementation challenges in the context of the WGs’ domain areas. A breakdown of this can be seen in Figure X. below. It is worth noting here that each WG can be linked with one or more domain areas, so the total connections represented in Figure 17 exceeds the number of WGs (Agricultural and Veterinary Sciences = 8, Computer and information sciences = 44, Domain Agnostic = 29, Engineering and Technology = 9, Natural Sciences = 22, Social Sciences and Humanities = 2).

Figure 17. RDA WGs relevant to SRIA Implementation Challenges, by domain area

As RDA in general looks to address issues relating to data sharing and re-use, RDA Groups (both Interest Groups and Working Groups) tend to approach these from cross-domain or domain agnostic perspectives; as such, the Domain Agnostic and Computer and Information Sciences domains account for over half of the domain areas associated with WGs. As Figure X. shows, WGs’ domain areas are evenly distributed in relation to the Implementation Challenges.

However, it is worth noting here two slight outliers: the larger share of Domain Agnostic WGs related to the ‘Resource provider environments’ Implementation Challenge, and the significantly greater share of Natural Sciences WGs in relation to the Metadata & Ontologies Implementation Challenge compared to the other Implementation Challenges: the former can be explained due to WG efforts focused on the technical prerequisites for integrating systems of resources, regardless of the community or domains these resources are used by; the latter demonstrates that a lot of focus in Natural Sciences-related WGs (for example, WGs focusing on health sciences, omics, and materials science) has been on developing standards and guidelines for managing and describing data in these fields, perhaps representing a need for more discipline-specific schemas, ontologies, vocabularies and other semantic artefacts within this domain.

Implementation Challenges - further analysis

Identifiers

Relevant to the Identifiers Implementation Challenge, the [PID Information Types \(PIT\) WG](#) produced an endorsed RDA Recommendation that detailed the “essential types of information associated with persistent identifiers”⁵⁷; despite this Recommendation being produced ten years ago, it is still worth considering as it provides a basis for structuring PIDs which can be adopted by diverse communities to develop specific PIDs according to a “well-accepted set of core types”, allowing these to be federated into wider PID infrastructures (as is evident from an [RDA Adoption Story](#) which describes how the Deutsches Klimarechenzentrum (DKRZ) adopted the PIT WG and other RDA outputs in efforts to improve data tracking and versioning in the Earth System Grid Federation data infrastructure). As is clear from the Priorities, though various identifiers have been in use for 20 years, the need to “[d]evelop standardised identifiers for resource types that have not as yet become standard practice” is yet to be addressed; further exploration and building on the work of this WG would be of clear benefit here.

Another WG which addresses this emerging need, described in the SRIA 5.1.2 Gaps, is the [Persistent Identification of Instruments WG](#), focused on developing an identifier system for instruments used for measuring in scientific research. This WG produced two resources on this: an RDA Supporting Output titled ‘Persistent Identification of Instruments’⁵⁸ and an RDA-endorsed Recommendation titled ‘Metadata Schema for the Persistent Identification of Instruments’⁵⁹ in 2020 and 2021 respectively. The latter in particular responds to the first of the Identifiers’ gaps from the SRIA, i.e., “Establishing mature and recognised PID infrastructures for emerging resource types”, which specifically references the need for reliable infrastructures for PIDs for instruments; the metadata schema proposed in this WG Recommendation would be of value for laying the foundation for any infrastructure for instruments.

More recently, RDA TIGER has funded through its Cascade Grant process a project from the National Open Research Forum in the Republic of Ireland. This project is aiming to implement the Recommendations of the [RDA National PID Strategies Working Group](#) in order to develop the

⁵⁷ Weigel, T., DiLauro, T., & Zastrow, T. (2015). PID Information Types WG final deliverable. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.15497/FDAA09D5-5ED0-403D-B97A-2675E1EBE786>

⁵⁸ Stocker, M., Darroch, L., Krahl, R., Habermann, T., Devaraju, A., Schwardmann, U., D’Onofrio, C. and Häggström, I., 2020. Persistent Identification of Instruments. *Data Science Journal*, 19(1), p.18. DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5334/dsj-2020-018>

⁵⁹ Krahl, R., Darroch, L., Huber, R., Devaraju, A., Klump, J., Habermann, T., Stocker, M., & The Research Data Alliance Persistent Identification of Instruments Working Group members. (2021). Metadata Schema for the Persistent Identification of Instruments. Research Data Alliance. <https://doi.org/10.15497/RDA00070>

country’s existing national PID strategy and bring it further in line with the EOSC PID policy. This project addresses the specific gap outlined in the SRIA with respect to “Quality of service for PIDs” (i.e., ensuring that PID services and providers comply with the EOSC PID policy. This cascade grant project also provides a concrete example of the application of an RDA output with a view towards harmonising activities in the country with the priorities defined in the SRIA.

Figure 18. Kumu map representing mapping of RDA WGs to Identifiers Implementation Challenge

Metadata and ontologies

Importantly for this report the SRIA highlights that “coordination with activities around metadata and ontologies outside of EOSC, for example in the Research Data Alliance (RDA), is of course essential” (p89). The SRIA also notes that there is fragmentation in this landscape, with homogenous metadata, ontologies and other semantic artefacts having “evolved organically over time, addressing the needs of individual communities and sub-communities”; as such, the RDA WGs that contribute to this

Implementation Challenge serve a key role in addressing this coordination gap by supporting both domain-agnostic and domain-specific work.

Among the key outputs to date is the [Metadata Standards Catalog WG](#), which produced a searchable, curated registry of metadata standards intended to assist researchers and infrastructure providers in selecting and aligning appropriate schemas. [reference and explanation] Another major contribution is the [I-ADOPT \(InteroperAble Descriptions of Observable Property Terminologies\) WG](#), which developed a formalised approach to describing observable properties in a machine-actionable way, supporting semantic interoperability particularly in the environmental and earth sciences domain. The FAIRsharing Registry, developed as part of a joint [RDA and FORCE11 Working Group](#), is also a central output of relevance. The [FAIRsharing.org](#) website, which was the result of this WG's efforts and its Recommendation⁶⁰, provides a registry of metadata standards, data policies, and databases, and has been implemented widely across European and global initiatives, as catalogued on the [FAIRsharing.org website](#)).

Current work being supported by the RDA TIGER project continues to address SRIA priorities and gaps. The [Multi-Omics Metadata Standards Integration \(MOMSI\) WG](#) is tackling the integration of heterogeneous metadata standards in the complex and data-intensive field of multi-omics research. The [Building Immune Digital Twins WG](#), another RDA TIGER-supported WG, is addressing the metadata and ontological challenges specific to biomedical simulations and digital twin technologies.

A particularly important and high-impact contribution comes from the [RDA FAIR Mappings WG](#). This WG builds directly on work conducted within the FAIR-IMPACT⁶¹ and FAIRCORE4EOSC⁶² projects. Again, it is supported by RDA TIGER and it aims to create community-agreed guidelines and tooling to support the alignment of metadata elements and semantic artefacts across different schemas, vocabularies, and ontologies. This work is directly aligned with the SRIA's priority to develop methods to "establish crosswalks between existing ontologies and other semantic artefacts", and complements EOSC's broader efforts to ensure interoperability between disciplinary and cross-disciplinary metadata frameworks. Planned outputs from the WG include a best practices

⁶⁰ McQuilton, P., Hodson, S., Lawrence, R., Sansone, S.-A., & FAIRsharing Registry: Connecting Data Policies, Standards and Databases RDA WG. (2019). The FAIRsharing Registry and Recommendations: Interlinking Standards, Databases and Data Policies (Version 1). Research Data Alliance.
<https://doi.org/10.15497/RDA00030>

⁶¹ See this FAIRsFAIR webinar on the topic:

<https://fair-impact.eu/events/fair-impact-events/documenting-mapping-community-practices>

⁶² Specifically, the FAIRCORE4EOSC work on the Metadata Schema and Crosswalk Registry (MSCR):
<https://faircore4eosc.eu/eosc-core-components/metadata-schema-and-crosswalk-registry-mscr>

framework, reference implementations, and evaluation mechanisms that are intended to be applicable across domains.

Figure 19. Kumu map representing mapping of RDA WGs to Metadata and ontologies Implementation Challenge

FAIR metrics and certification

While the FAIR principles themselves are now well established and broadly accepted across the research ecosystem, their practical instantiation in research workflows, and how this can be measured, remains an issue. Of the 12 WGs identified as relevant to this Implementation Challenge, six have produced Recommendation and Supporting Outputs, with the other six active at the time of writing. These 12 WGs focus primarily on the infrastructure, services, and assessment frameworks necessary to foster a FAIR data ecosystem. Though there is less activity of relevance here, the alignment of the activity and outputs of these WGs make them potentially highly impactful. The explicit recognition of RDA’s work in the SRIA highlights the role that RDA can play in the development of the FAIR ecosystem in EOSC.

RDA TIGER “Research Data Alliance facilitation of Targeted International working Groups for EOSC-related Research solutions” is funded by HORIZON-INFRA-2022-EOSC-0, Project:101094406.

The importance of the FDMM work is further emphasised by the SRIA’s call to “support the assessment and improvement of the RDA FAIR Data Maturity Model” (p92), identifying this as a priority action for EOSC. A supplementary, related priority is the need to “assess and test the proposed EOSC FAIR data metrics in a neutral forum”, with the suggestion that such an activity might be undertaken by a Working Group under the auspices of the Global Open Research Commons (GORC) initiative⁶³. This presents a clear and concrete avenue for further alignment between EOSC and RDA, and a mechanism by which RDA’s community processes can help validate and implement FAIR metrics at a European and global level.

Additional ongoing RDA WG activities are also highly relevant to the certification aspects of this IC. The [RDA/WDS TRUST Principles Outreach and Adoption Working Group](#) and the [Community-based catalogue of requirements for trustworthy Technical Repository Service Providers Working Group \(TRSPs WG\)](#) are particularly important in this regard. The former has explored the relationships between the TRUST Principles, existing repository certification schemes (such as [CoreTrustSeal](#)), and emerging metrics frameworks. The latter focuses on extending certification approaches to repository service providers, thus aligning operational practices with FAIR principles. Both WGs contribute directly to multiple “Priorities for FAIR Certification” identified in the SRIA⁶⁴, and help to bridge existing certification standards with evolving FAIR assessment practices.

⁶³ There are three main GORC-related RDA Groups: the [Global Open Research Commons Interest Group](#), the [GORC International Model WG](#), and the [GORC International Implementations Working Group \(GORC II WG\)](#).

⁶⁴ SRIA, p.93

Figure 20. Kumu map representing mapping of RDA WGs to FAIR metrics and certification Implementation Challenge

Authentication and authorisation infrastructure

With respect to this Implementation Challenge the SRIA notes that, despite the successes of services like eduGAIN and eduroam, “both the user experience and the service provider experience remain confusing for large parts of the R&E AAI ecosystem.”⁶⁵ The situation as it is described in the SRIA concerns not only the EOSC ecosystem but the wider e-research environment; as such, an argument could be made that it is the Implementation Challenge requiring the largest amount of investment, both financial and in intellectual resources.

The gaps associated with this Implementation Challenge are summarised as follows in the SRIA:

- There is no consistent user experience for AAI across the e-science ecosystem;
- There is no consistent interface for service providers in the e-science ecosystem;

⁶⁵ SRIA, p.93

- The AAI ecosystem must grow to match the growth of EOSC beyond the research and education community.

None of the seven RDA WGs of relevance here address these gaps in their entirety; however, if we consider how they are broken down and described in the SRIA, and how the associated priorities are articulated, it is clear that there are areas where the activities of WGs can apply.

As discussed previously, the GORC International Model⁶⁶ features nine essential elements which are used to group the categories and attributes of the model (where relevant, there are also subcategories and features associated with each category). One of these essential elements is ‘ICT Infrastructure’, which has a specific ‘Authentication and Authorization Infrastructure (AAI)’ category. The GORC Typology defines AAI as the “services and procedures that enable members of different institutions to access protected information that is distributed on different servers.” The model contains two subcategories, ‘Base AAI Infrastructure’ and ‘Add on AAI infrastructure’ noting that the consideration levels for these are ‘Core’ and ‘Desirable’ respectively. Though the model itself does not go further than this in addressing any of the concerns raised with respect to this Implementation Challenge in the SRIA, it is worth noting that the follow-on [GORC International Implementations WG](#) will be working with commons developers to produce different profiles of the model, which will feed into the priorities associated with this Implementation Challenge. A concrete example of this is the RDA TIGER-supported [Health Data Commons GORC Profile WG](#).

⁶⁶ Payne, K., Corrie, B., Crawley, F., Harrower, N., Macneil, R., Maxwell, L., Sansone, S.-A., Treloar, A., Woodford, C., Åkerström, W. N., & RDA GORC International Model WG. (2023). The Global Open Research Commons International Model Report, Version 1 (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.15497/RDA00097>

Figure 21. Kumu map representing mapping of RDA WGs to Authentication and authorisation infrastructure Implementation Challenge

User environments

One initiative taking place as part of RDA of relevance to the User environments Implementation Challenge is the development of the Global Open Research Commons (GORC) International Model⁶⁷ by the [GORC International Model WG](#), which has resulted in follow-on work in new RDA WGs. One of the gaps identified in relation to the User environments Implementation Challenge is composability, i.e., making available and accessible tools, services and resources to EOSC users, which “requires a legal and organisational framework”; the GORC International model, and the subsequent work of the [GORC International Implementations WG](#) is of relevance here. Though the Model has been designed

⁶⁷ *Ibid.*

for use by those developing and integrating commons (and is of relevance to the Resource Provider Environments Implementation Challenge, to be addressed in the section below) implicit in this is a concern with the experiences of users and other stakeholders of federated systems. The Model is directly applicable to some of the priorities of this Implementation Challenge, i.e., “integration of existing catalogues and portals should be addressed to ensure users can find the services and resources they need” and “the distributed architecture model must address legal and organisational frameworks to enable researchers to compose resources”.⁶⁸

Other WGs relevant to this Implementation Challenge include [FAIR for Virtual Research Environments WG](#), which focuses on how the FAIR principles can be adopted by VREs (Virtual Research Environments, or similar research infrastructure platforms), and the [RDA-OfR Mapping the landscape of digital research tools \(MaLDReTH\) WG](#), which has produced a research data lifecycle model and a categorisation schema for research tools which can be used by those designing and implementing research tools and infrastructure. Again, similar to the GORC International Model, though these WGs do not explicitly address the experiences of users within the EOSC environment, there is a natural overlap with their concerns and those described in the SRIA.

⁶⁸ SRIA, p.98, 99

Figure 22. Kumu map representing mapping of RDA WGs to User environments Implementation Challenge

Resource provider environments

The current resource provider environment is heterogeneous due to a combination of geographical, political, and domain focus factors: “Resource providers are widely distributed across Europe, have the mandate to serve one or more research disciplines and have to comply with different national and European legislations.”⁶⁹ There is some natural overlap in the focus of this Implementation Challenge and the SRIA’s proposals for how it ought to be addressed with the User Environments Implementation Challenge; what is specific to the Resource Provider Environments Implementation Challenge is the concern with interoperability of resources themselves with respect to service providers and their users, along with the accessibility of metadata and information regarding the resources.

⁶⁹ SRIA, p.99

The [Research Data Repository Interoperability WG](#) has produced an endorsed Recommendation⁷⁰ to address one of the specific priorities for this Implementation Challenge action area. Its Recommendation, titled Research Data Repository Interoperability WG Final Recommendations,⁷¹ directly addresses the priority of “enabl[ing] the composability of resources and across resource providers.” This Recommendation focused on a use case where a digital object migrated or was replicated from one repository to another. It considered the different conditions under which this replication/migration could take place, and proposed a common exchange format to facilitate this process. It is clear from the description in the SRIA that this WG’s work can be built on to address this ongoing concern.

Other WGs who have produced Recommendations of relevance to this Implementation Challenge include the [Data Granularity WG](#), whose Recommendation helps data producers and infrastructure providers determine the appropriate levels of granularity to discover and exchange data and metadata across disparate systems⁷² (this Recommendation was produced with support from an RDA TIGER external expert grant⁷³), and the GORC International Model WG; the model can be used to evaluate and define the wider resource provider landscape within EOSC, as it states in the Gaps section: “The EOSC Rules of Participation and Interoperability Framework should contain legal and organisational aspects that allow resource provisioning in a sustainable way across resource providers and across national, community and partnership boundaries.”⁷⁴

As mentioned above, there is a lot of activity currently underway across RDA WGs which is of relevance for this Implementation Challenge, including the [FAIR for Virtual Research Environments WG](#), the [Scientific Knowledge Graphs - Interoperability Framework \(SKG-IF\) WG](#), and the [Mapping the Landscape of Digital Research Tools II \(MaLDReth II\) WG](#). The latter of these WGs, which is being supported by the RDA TIGER project, addresses one concern identified in relation to the

⁷⁰ The RDA endorsement process involves WGs opening the initial draft of their Recommendation(s) for public comment and evidence that the Recommendation could be adopted by at least two organisations. More information can be found here:

<https://www.rd-alliance.org/recommendations-and-outputs/recommendations-guidelines/>

⁷¹ RDA Research Data Repository Interoperability WG. (2018). Research Data Repository Interoperability WG Final Recommendations. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.15497/RDA00025>

⁷² Jenkyns, R., Mathiak, B., McNeill, K., Smith, G., Sun, G., Little, C., Jones, B., Elbert, D., Hellström, M., Schabinger, R., & RDA Data Granularity WG. (2025). Guidance on Data Granularity: Report of the RDA Data Granularity WG (Version 1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.15497/RDA00126>

⁷³ See Lehtsalu, L., & Delipalta, A. (2025). RDA TIGER D1.4: Final report on the external and direct support provision and lessons learned. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17876865> for further detail on this and other external expert grants.

⁷⁴ SRIA, p.100

Figure 23. Kumu representation of RDA WGs related to Resource Provider Environments Implementation Challenge

EOSC Interoperability Framework

A separate report could go into much greater detail on how the activities of RDA Working Groups align with these various layers of interoperability described (i.e., technical, semantic, organisational, and legal) in the EOSC Interoperability Framework. The SRIA Implementation Challenge adheres to this layer paradigm and adds to it, noting that there are “three overarching areas under which these various gaps and associated priorities fall” (p102); these are: Support for standards development and adoption, Engagement with research communities, and Robust governance and implementation. These are general enough concepts that they could be of relevance to a large number of RDA WGs, without these WGs necessarily producing work that could be used to support them. As such, rather than looking at these three overarching areas, the analysis conducted for this report focuses on the four layers of technical, semantic, organisational and legal interoperability.

At the technical level, the SRIA describes gaps related to disparate Authentication and Authorisation Infrastructures, data format heterogeneity, granularity of repository holdings and their searchability, and divergent PID mechanisms and policies. A further examination of the analysis of WGs of relevance to this Implementation Challenge show that there is work underway in existing RDA WGs and outputs already published which can be built on to address these concerns. Regarding the searchability of repository holdings by users, as pointed out in relation to other Implementation Challenges, the [Data Granularity WG’s Recommendation](#)⁷⁶ sets out guidance on data granularity approaches and how best to implement these considerations within an infrastructure. It directly addresses the gap associated with this Implementation Challenge to “[m]ake available search tools for coarse-grained and fine-grained datasets (and other research objects)”⁷⁷ and provides guidance specifically to data infrastructure providers on “levels of data granularity on which to operate” with respect to user needs.

Another RDA WG which has produced guidance to address issues with the technical layer of the EIF Implementation Challenge is the [National PID Strategies WG](#). This WG’s Recommendation⁷⁸ draws on extensive global case studies and allows those developing PID policies to compare their existing or prospective policy to others and use a checklist to develop it further. One of the priorities identified

⁷⁶ Jenkyns, R., Mathiak, B., McNeill, K., Smith, G., Sun, G., Little, C., Jones, B., Elbert, D., Hellström, M., Schabinger, R., & RDA Data Granularity WG. (2025). Guidance on Data Granularity: Report of the RDA Data Granularity WG (Version 1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.15497/RDA00126>

⁷⁷ SRIA, p.105

⁷⁸ Brown, C., Simons, N., Bangert, D., & Sadler, S. (2023). RDA National PID Strategies Guide and Checklist (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.15497/RDA/00091>

in the SRIA in relation to this topic is to “implement the EOSC PID policy, accommodating any appropriate PID usage, recognising that established practices are at different levels of maturity for different resources and that new PID types may emerge.”⁷⁹ The extent to which the approach advocated by the National PID Strategies WG Recommendation aligns with the EOSC PID policy⁸⁰ is clear, especially with respect to the National PID Strategies WG checklist’s focus on governance, sustainability, stakeholder engagement, and engaging with the wider international community. This work is being further developed under the [National PID Strategies IG](#); of particular note here is the IG’s focus on incorporating different types of PIDs (i.e., grant identifiers, person identifiers, organisation identifiers) into the value propositions for national PID strategies, something that has been referenced as a gap to be addressed in the SRIA with respect to interoperability: “Multiple service providers for different types of PIDs exist. As a result, different sets of policies are enforced to varying degrees, and sometimes the identifiers are not even resolvable.”⁸¹

Regarding the semantic layer of the EIF, the SRIA notes gaps concerned with silos arising from varying approaches to the development of semantic artefacts, lack of harmonisation across disciplines and data types, and the inadequacy of federation across repositories and repository systems which inhibits discovery within and across disciplines. There is a variety of RDA WGs actively addressing each of these concerns, approaching them from both domain-specific and domain-agnostic perspectives.

Looking first at the concern with the interoperability of repositories and repository systems, the main WG of relevance here is the [Research Data Repository Interoperability WG](#). This WG has produced two outputs (an endorsed Recommendation and a Supporting Output⁸²) on this topic and has precipitated the formation of related Working and Interest Groups. This WG’s work is also of relevance to the Resource Provider Environments Implementation Challenge and, as referenced in that section, this WG recommended a common exchange format which built on existing efforts to facilitate content exchange within and across repositories, generalising it to propose a process which can be adopted easily. This WG addresses directly the gap identified in the SRIA of a “need for federated access over existing research data repositories” and the associated gap that “EOSC should define clear protocols and building blocks for the federation/harvesting of these repositories of semantic artefacts.”⁸³ Related recommendations and other outputs on this topic have been

⁷⁹ SRIA, p.105

⁸⁰ (2020). *A Persistent Identifier (PID) policy for the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC)*. Publications Office. <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/926037>.

⁸¹ SRIA, p.103

⁸² Both outputs can be accessed here:

<https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/research-data-repository-interoperability-wg/outputs/>

⁸³ SRIA, p.105

completed by the [RDA/WDS Certification of Digital Repositories Interest Group](#) and the subsequent [Repository Audit and Certification DSA–WDS Partnership WG](#), which formed the basis of the CoreTrustSeal certification system.

The gaps identified in the SRIA related to the “need for principled approaches and tools for ontology and metadata schema creation, maintenance, governance and use” and the “need for harmonisation across disciplines”⁸⁴ are addressed in two related WGs currently active in the omics domain: [Multi-Omics Metadata Standards Integration \(MOMSI\) WG](#) and [FAIRification of Genomic Annotations WG](#). The former addresses the proliferation of community standards and approaches in multi-omics research data in recent years, developing a curated database of multi-omics semantic artefacts and, through a gap analysis, identifying common data and metadata standards elements across these related disciplines. The FAIRification of Genomic Annotations WG is focused more narrowly on genomic research, specifically on developing a minimal metadata schema for genomic annotation data, based on an analysis and synthesis of existing standards and schemas, and interrogated against relevant use cases. Both of these WGs, which are supported by RDA TIGER, clearly address this Implementation Challenge priority: “Research communities should be well supported (independently of their current state of semantic artefact adoption) so as to generate clear and precise definitions for the terms they use, as well as for their metadata and data schemas (and to incorporate those that they are already using) and their documentation” (p105), and by using the RDA as the platform to progress their work, ensure that community consensus plays a key role here, increasing the potential for the uptake of their results within the EOSC ecosystem.

As noted above, the impact of RDA WG activities is related mainly to the technical and semantic layers of the EIF. However, it is worth noting here two final WGs who are at the time of writing focused on a specific concern elaborated in the SRIA with respect to the organisational layer of the EIF. The SRIA notes that there is a “need for interoperability certification mechanisms for service providers, so that service users can set their own expectations about the support for interoperability of those services”⁸⁵: Both the [TRUST Principles Outreach and Adoption WG](#) and the [Community-based catalogue of requirements for trustworthy Technical Repository Service Providers Working Group \(TRSPs WG\)](#) both address this gap specifically. The TRUST Principles Outreach and Adoption WG is addressing this by examining the different sets of principles (e.g., FAIR, CARE, data repository attributes, etc.) that feed into certification process and criteria, how they relate to the TRUST principles themselves, and how the TRUST principles map to existing certification processes (i.e., CoreTrustSeal, ISO16363, Nestor). One of the outcomes of this WG’s activity will be to contribute to the interoperability of certification mechanisms. The TRSPs WG, meanwhile, is focused

⁸⁴ SRIA, p.103

⁸⁵ SRIA, p.104

on extending the applicability of certifications and certification mechanisms to technical service providers. This WG is aiming to compile an inventory of performance expectations for repositories and related services and, through a series of community consultations, use these criteria to identify where certification can be extended to service providers to repositories.

The work of both of these WGs is clearly of relevance to the organisational layer gap referenced above. Their work is also relevant to two recently funded Horizon Europe INFRA-EOSC projects, EOSC EDEN and FIDELIS. The RDA TIGER project, which is providing support to the [RDA/WDS TRUST Principles Outreach and Adoption WG](#) and [Community-based catalogue of requirements for trustworthy Technical Repository Service Providers Working Group \(TRSPs WG\)](#), is facilitating further cooperation between these initiatives and helping to identify where their efforts can feed directly into these projects' objectives. Again, this is a concrete example of how RDA community activities have a direct bearing on not only the situations as they are described in the SRIA, but also on how major EC-funded projects can successfully contend with them.

Figure 24. Kumu representation of RDA WGs related to EOSC Interoperability Framework Implementation Challenge

RDA TIGER “Research Data Alliance facilitation of Targeted International working Groups for EOSC-related Research solutions” is funded by HORIZON-INFRA-2022-EOSC-0, Project:101094406.

Multi-Annual Roadmap - further analysis

The SRIA Multi-annual Roadmap (MAR) is set out in three Priority Stages, covering specific periods, each with a high-level objective⁸⁶. The latest version of the SRIA (version 1.3)⁸⁷ focuses on the period of Priority Stage 3, particularly on 2026-27. Given that part of this report's purpose is to describe ways in which RDA activities can support and have impact on the European landscape, this report focuses on the situation as described in SRIA 1.3 and the new proposed priorities for 2026-2027.⁸⁸ It is also worth noting that the priorities of the General Objectives are divided into European, national and institutional levels. Where relevant, it will be indicated which specific priorities and their respective level that RDA WG activities relate to.

General Objective 1: Ensure that Open Science practices and skills are rewarded and taught, becoming the 'new normal'

The description of the aims and expected outcomes of this General Objective concerns activities that are for the most part downstream of the types of activities that RDA WGs focus on. Much of the European, national and institutional level priorities described in the SRIA regarding the embedding of Open Science practices concern 'soft skills', the development of communities, and changes to the existing culture of research assessment.

Regarding the overall concern of General Objective 1, that is, the need to teach researchers the skills they need for Open Science, the [RDA/CODATA Summer Schools in Data Science and Cloud Computing in the Developing World WG](#) has been contributing to this effort since its inception in 2016. In that time, it has produced two Recommendations; the first outlines the framework the WG developed to run short 'school' courses to teach Open Science and data sharing skills in low and middle income countries (LMICs)⁸⁹, the second sets out a curriculum and example materials for Early Career Researchers (ECR's) on the foundational skills in Data Science⁹⁰. Together, these materials have

⁸⁶ These are Stage 1 (2021–2022): Development towards added value from a functional federation of Infrastructures, Stage 2 (2023–2024): Expansion to production that generates added value, and Stage 3 (2025–2027 and beyond): Expansion to develop impact from Open Science.

⁸⁷ Horizon Europe Co-programmed Partnership for the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). (2024). Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA) of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) (v1.3, 2024) (1.3). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17582648>

⁸⁸ SRIA, p.141

⁸⁹ Materials associated with this framework can be found in this Zenodo community: <https://zenodo.org/communities/codata-rda-research-data-science-summer-school/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest>

⁹⁰ Shanahan, H., Quick, R., Córdoba, M. A., Clement, G., Bezuidenhout, L., Shanmugasundaram, V., ... Short, H. (2019). A curriculum for foundational Research Data Science skills for Early Career Researchers (Version 1). <https://doi.org/10.15497/rda00038>

contributed to the running of over 20 CODATA-RDA Research Data Science Schools globally⁹¹. These schools offer practical training in data science, cloud computing, and FAIR data principles to early-career researchers and scientists. As well as the curriculum on the practical skills needed by researchers, the School has also run a data stewardship strand, focusing on the specific requirements and skills of those working in or interested in pursuing a career in this area. Overall, this WG has set a high standard in terms of how a WG's work (its outputs and their implementation) can have an impact in the research ecosystem. As well as addressing the 'European' aspects of this SRIA General Objective, this example shows that there is a need on a global scale to upskill researchers with respect to Open Science and data management skills, a concern shared by the European community with its international counterparts.

One of the specific, European-level priorities associated with this General Objective is: "Support and embed appraisal and preservation procedures for long-term data preservation and monitor their value and costs. Practices should be transparent, aligned where possible and interoperable (i.e. through machine actionable rights management)." This is evidently a wide-ranging priority (itself within a wide ranging General Objective), but one RDA WG which addresses at least part of this priority is the [WDS/RDA Assessment of Data Fitness for Use WG](#). In its Recommendation, the WG sets out the criteria and procedures for assessment of research data fitness for use, with these criteria themselves mapping to the CoreTrustSeal requirements for trustworthy repositories and to the FAIR principles⁹².

A tangential point to note here is in relation to the European-level priorities to "collect, connect and scale up ongoing good practices and case studies for the research and career assessment of open science practices in collaboration with the Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment (CoARA)" and to "support and complement the CoARA movement with developing tools and processes for the research and career assessment of open science practices". At the time of writing, RDA Europe is contributing to the CoARA Boost project titled, '[Teaming for self-evaluation in research assessment across scales: from researchers to institutions](#)'. While not directly related to the work of any specific WGs, this project will leverage the RDA Europe team's detailed knowledge of WGs' activities and promote the activities of CoARA and this specific project within the RDA community.

⁹¹ See full list of previous schools on the CODATA-RDA Research Data Science Schools website: <https://www.datascienceschools.org/previouschools/>

⁹² Austin, C., Cousijn, H., Diepenbroek, M., Petters, J., Soares E Silva, M. (2019): WDS/RDA Assessment of Data Fitness for Use WG Outputs and Recommendations. <https://dx.doi.org/10.15497/rda00034>

General Objective 2: Enable the definition of standards, and the development of tools and services, to allow researchers to find, access, reuse and combine results

The first of the WGs is the [FAIRsharing Registry: Connecting data policies, standards and databases RDA WG](#). As mentioned previously, the WG's Recommendation⁹³, published in 2018, was central to the establishment of [fairsharing.org](#), which is a widely used, global resource connecting data and metadata standards along with databases and policies. This resource, founded on the work done by the RDA WG, supports this General Objective as it enables users to identify appropriate standards for their own data, supporting the reuse and combination of research outputs, and it allows standards producers to describe their resources such that they can be more easily identified and implemented.

The second WG supporting the describing, cataloguing and sharing of standards is the [Metadata Standards Catalog WG](#). Similar to the previous example, this WG's activity resulted in the Metadata Standards Catalog⁹⁴. This is a community-collated directory of research metadata schemas. The catalogue also contains indexes of other metadata-related resources, such as mapping between schemas, metadata tools, and standards organisations. Again similar to [fairsharing.org](#), this RDA WG-related output supports researchers and related professionals in efforts to work towards this General Objective by providing a structured, openly accessible catalogue of metadata standards and related resources that helps communities identify appropriate schemas and understand relationships and mappings between standards, enabling the discovery and reuse of research outputs across disciplines and infrastructures.

The [CoreTrustSeal Maintenance WG](#) (set up as a successor to and maintainer of the outputs of the Repository Audit and Certification DSA–WDS Partnership WG) support this General Objective through its stewardship of the [CoreTrustSeal](#) certification requirements and process for trustworthy digital repositories. These were first developed as part of an RDA WG and directly contribute to increasing trustworthiness in the repository ecosystem and facilitate the standards-based benchmarking and comparison of certified repositories. This in turn underpins and supports repository users to select, appraise and reuse data from across different sources.

Other current WGs whose activities support the efforts to meet this General Objective include two related WGs, the [Multi-Omics Metadata Standards Integration \(MOMSI\) WG](#) and the [FAIRification of Genomic Annotations WG](#), both of whom address the issue of there being a lack of standardisation

⁹³ McQuilton, P., Hodson, S., Lawrence, R., Sansone, S.-A., & FAIRsharing Registry: Connecting Data Policies, Standards and Databases RDA WG. (2019). The FAIRsharing Registry and Recommendations: Interlinking Standards, Databases and Data Policies (Version 1). Research Data Alliance.
<https://doi.org/10.15497/RDA00030>

⁹⁴ The catalogue can be accessed here: <https://rdamsc.bath.ac.uk/>

when it comes to metadata in genomics and other omics research. The modus operandi of these RDA WGs here in particular addresses the European-level priority of this General Objective to “continue to invest in the creation, adoption and governance of community-based metadata and data standards in adequacy with latest EOSC developments towards a minimum common metadata schema.”⁹⁵

This General Objective also mentions that appropriate tools and services are central to allow for the identification and (re)use of research outputs. In much the same way that RDA WGs approach issues related to data standards, there are many active and completed RDA WGs whose activities centre on research tools and services and their categorisations, linkages and descriptions. The most relevant WGs here are a set of two ‘sister’ WGs: [RDA-OfR Mapping the landscape of digital research tools WG](#) and its follow-on [Mapping the Landscape of Digital Research Tools II \(MaLDReTH II\) WG](#). Essentially, these WGs have focused on the categorisation and mapping of digital research tools used across the research lifecycle. In its first iteration, the WG produced a new research lifecycle model, followed by a mapping of different types of tools to each stage; in its second iteration, the RDA TIGER-supported MaLDReTH II WG is currently enhancing the framework with use cases, descriptions of the interactions between various tools, and integrations of the framework with other models (e.g., the GORC International Model).

This framework produced by the MaLDReTH WGs, and its ongoing enhancement, is just one example yet again of how the RDA community, in contributing its expertise and resource to WG activities is helping to further efforts within Europe to achieve the General Objectives of the Multi-Annual Roadmap. Further examples include the [Community-based catalogue of requirements for trustworthy Technical Repository Service Providers Working Group \(TRSPs WG\)](#), which is working to the develop a modular catalogue of requirements for providers of technical supporting services to repositories in order to enable more flexible certification in the repository landscape, and the [RDA / CODATA Data Systems, Tools, and Services for Crisis Situations WG](#), which among other activities has undertaken a survey to identify the tools used and the potential gaps in tool provision for those working in crisis zones.

General Objective 3: Establish a sustainable and federated infrastructure enabling open sharing of scientific results

Aspects noted in relation to General Objective 3 cover a wide range of features required for the vision of the sustainable and federated infrastructure for EOSC to be realised; these include Authentication and Authorization Infrastructure (AAI) protocols, standardised Rules of Participation for EOSC users, governance and funding models, etc. There are echoes here between the relevance

⁹⁵ SRIA, p.169

of RDA WG activities to this General Objective and the relevance of RDA WG activities to some of the SRIA Implementation Challenges mentioned above (i.e., Authentication and authorisation infrastructure and User Environments)

There are two European-level priorities focused on the provision of semantic artefact-related services: priorities F. “Accelerate the adoption of interoperability and semantic artefact catalogues. Support AI-enabled services that facilitate interoperability in a more automated way”, and G. “Services for dependable semantic artefact catalogues should be part of the EOSC Core, akin to how vocabularies are published by the EC publications Office at EU Vocabularies.” Implicit in this need for semantic artefact catalogues services is that semantic artefacts themselves should be used as widely as possible, and where necessary, there should exist methods for linking semantic artefacts within and across disciplines. Two RDA TIGER-supported WGs, both in the process of producing their Recommendations at the time of writing, focus on these aspects; the [FAIR Mappings WG](#) is working toward a set of common guidelines to make different types of mappings between semantic artefacts FAIR with a view to producing an open knowledge base of mapping and crosswalk scenarios; the [Alignment of multilingual vocabularies in the Social Sciences and Humanities WG](#) is focused on the issue of homogeneity of semantic artefacts in social sciences and humanities disciplines by producing guidelines for semantic artefact producers to increase their usage across disciplinary, linguistic and cultural boundaries.

As has been referred to already in this report, the [GORC International Model WG](#) and [GORC International Implementations Working Group \(GORC II WG\)](#) already play a significant role in the discussions about how the EOSC will define itself (in one section in the SRIA focused on the role that Europe can play on a global scale, the point is made that “the ultimate goal of EOSC is to lead the development of a Global Open Research Commons, of which EOSC will form the European component.”⁹⁶) This is also applicable specifically in relation to this Global Objective, which is concerned with the overall view of how the EOSC will operate. The GORC International Model and associated work by associated GORC WGs and IGs will be particularly crucial in establishing just how a fully sustainable and federated research infrastructure can and should operate. The GORC International Model can be used not only to describe and benchmark the activities that are taking place on a European level, but also at national, regional and institutional levels, thus facilitating the interoperation and federation of services, policies, and infrastructures, ultimately supporting EOSC to achieve this General Objective.

⁹⁶ SRIA, p.138

EOSC Task Forces and Opportunity Area Expert Groups

The EOSC Association has convened two types of groups to address key areas of concern for the development of the EOSC. The Opportunity Area Expert Groups (OAEs) and Task Forces (TFs) have been set up to bring together experts from the EOSC-related Horizon Europe projects, from EOSC Association members organisations and observers, and from the wider community of EOSC stakeholders. Their areas of focus are displayed in Figure 25.

Figure 25. EOSC Task Forces and Opportunity Area Expert Groups

By focusing on a set of topics derived from the SRIA and decided on in the EOSC Winter School 2024, the current set of OAEs and TF will serve as a bridge between projects whose lifespans either begin or end in the 2024-2026 period.

In the initial design of this report, the intention was to provide an analysis of the commonalities in focus between the OAEs, TFs and RDA Working Groups, focusing on which of the latter’s outputs could be employed by Horizon Europe projects and in addressing SRIA concerns and targeted areas of EOSC’s development. However, as all of these concerns are described in the SRIA and analysed in the sub-sections above, the decision was made to omit a detailed analysis here in order to avoid the risk of reiterating points made above. The analysis above should be of use to the current and future iterations of OAEs and TFs.

Annex 2: Background and Methodology for the Mapping of RDA WGs to OS-related HE-funded projects

This annex contains further information regarding the methodology and analysis of Section 4: Mapping of RDA WGs to OS-related HE-funded projects.

Background

Horizon Europe (HE) is a framework programme which finance science, research and innovation projects during the 2021-2027 period⁹⁷. Open Science (OS) is modus operandi of HE programme⁹⁸ and to achieve these objectives sets different types of enablers^{99,100} such as the OS infrastructure called European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) and the legislative and regulatory environment for practising OS, the European Research Area (ERA) Policy Agendas.

EOSC¹⁰¹ is a trusted, virtual, federated environment that cuts across borders and scientific disciplines to store, share, process and reuse research digital objects (like publications, data, and software) that are FAIR. Thus, EOSC is a world-class infrastructure that supports the development of a web of FAIR data and its consolidation through dedicated partnership.

ERA aims to create a single and seamless market for research and innovation to foster scientific knowledge and innovation¹⁰². Since its creation ERA has achieved major achievements such as the European Strategy Forum of Research Infrastructures (ESFRI) (see Part B section 5: RDA and European Research Infrastructures of this report) by mobilising more than 50 RIs to join and coordinate their efforts to reduce the barriers on sharing resources. Moreover, ERA also enhanced the OS practices and collaborative sharing of scientific information through the EOSC.

To operate these activities, implementation documents of the HE calls and project funding are assigned through ‘work programmes’. The subject areas, also called ‘destinations’ of each work

⁹⁷ https://www.europarl.europa.eu/thinktank/en/document/EPRS_BRI%282018%29628297

⁹⁸ European Commission: Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, *Horizon Europe, open science – Early knowledge and data sharing, and open collaboration*, Publications Office of the European Union, 2021, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/18252>

⁹⁹

https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/strategy/strategy-research-and-innovation/our-digital-future/op-en-science_en

¹⁰⁰ <https://euraxess.ec.europa.eu/worldwide/asean/eus-open-science-policy>

¹⁰¹

https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/strategy/strategy-research-and-innovation/our-digital-future/op-en-science/european-open-science-cloud-eosc_en

¹⁰² <https://european-research-area.ec.europa.eu/era-history>

programme are defined under the call for proposal. Figure 26 shows the two work programmes and their destinations that directly support EOSC development and OS practising of the ERA Policy Agendas.

Figure 26. Calls' destinations of 'Research Infrastructures' and 'Reforming & Enhancing the European R&I system' work programmes. Destinations and areas that directly support EOSC development and Open Science practices are highlighted in pink.

Thus, the EOSC-related HE projects are funded under the INFRAEOSC destination calls of the 'Research Infrastructures' work programme, while the ERA OS-related HE projects are funded under the 'Reforming & Enhancing the European R&I system' (ERA) destination calls of the WIDERA work programme.

Methodology

Data collection

INFRAEOSC and ERA-OS HE-funded projects are retrieved from 'EU Funding & Tender Portal'¹⁰³. To collect HE funded-projects under INFRAEOSC destination, the call identifier format is manually entered in the 'Call' filter as HORIZON-INFRA-YEAR-EOSC, and the year of each call for proposals is added manually (e.g., HORIZON-INFRA-2021-EOSC for the 2021 call). The same approach is applied to the ERA calls for proposals by using the call identifier format as HORIZON-WIDERA-YEAR-ERA.

¹⁰³ <https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/opportunities/calls-for-proposals>

OS-related ERA projects are identified on ERA platform and on the ‘ERA Factsheet N°5’ document, produced by the HE-funded NCP_WIDERA.NET project

Table 17. List of the HE-funded projects under the INFRAEOSC destination and ‘Deepen the ERA’ strand by year. * indicates ERA-OS projects, falling under the OS challenge of ‘Deepen the ERA’

	2021	2022	2023	2024
INFRAEOSC (32)	FAIR-IMPACT AI4EOSC EuroScienceGateway FAIR-EASE RAISE SciLake Skills4EOSC EOSC4Cancer FAIRCORE4EOSC EOSC Focus	Blue-Cloud 2026 AqualNFRA RDA TIGER CRAFT-OA GraspOS	OStrails EVERSE TITAN EOSC ENTRUST SIESTA EOSC Beyond OSCARS	FIDELIS LUMEN EOSC Data Commons DataGEMS RAISE suite EOSC Gravity EOSC EDEN CLIMATE-ADAPT4EOSC FAIR2Adapt EOSC United
ERA-OS (17)	VERITY POIESIS IANUS DIAMAS WorldFAIR* PathOS OPUS	PATTERN TIER2 OSIRIS iRISE PALOMERA REINFORCING	CoARA Boost	TRUSTparency IP4OS ALMASI

During the 2021-2024 period, 32 projects have been funded under the INFRAEOSC calls and 17 projects OS-related to the ERA-OS calls (Table 17). The full dataset of retrieved projects, with the year of call for proposal, the destination call, the topics, and the funded-project name and webpage is available [here](#).

Domain of activity description

To achieve the alignment of RDA WGs activities with the ESOC- and OS-related HE-funded projects, we establish domains of activity or criteria that will be used for mapping.

According to the broad line of the HE main programme, the EOSC operational objectives include “scalability and sustainability of the access channel; effective federation of European, national, regional and institutional resources; technical and policy evolution to cope with new research needs and requirements (e.g. usage of sensitive data sets, privacy by design); data interoperability and compliance with the FAIR principles; and a wide user base”¹⁰⁴. These objectives cover a wide range of domains of activity, from technical to societal aspects, all-encompassing many aspects of OS

¹⁰⁴ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=COM%3A2018%3A436%3AFIN>

practices supported by the HE programme, such as ethics and trust through policy aspects, as well as inclusion through the diverse user-base.

Thus, based on their representativeness of the aspects covered, we decided to use these objectives as criteria for the mapping analysis between RDA WGs and EOSC and OS-related HE-funded projects.

Table 18. Criteria used for the mapping analysis, their abbreviations and description generated by ChatGPT5-mini (accessed 2025-10-30)

Activity domain abbreviation	Activity domain description
Scalability	Scalability and sustainability of the access channel, ensuring that the infrastructure can grow and remain operational over the long term.
Federation	Effective federation of resources, integrating European, national, regional, and institutional resources into a cohesive system.
Policy evolution	Technical and policy evolution, adapting to emerging research needs and requirements, such as handling sensitive datasets and implementing privacy by design.
FAIR compliance	Data interoperability and FAIR compliance, ensuring data is Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable.
Wider user base	Wide user base, supporting a broad spectrum of researchers and stakeholders.

The description of each domain of activity or criteria is refined by ChatGPT5-mini (Table 18), by providing a brief definition of each category,

Categorisation by domain of activity

RDA WGs and all HE-funded projects are affiliated to one domain based on their main activity. The domain of activity of the RDA WGs is based on the case of statement of the WG, or to its page description when the case of statement isn't available. For the HE-funded projects (INFRAEOSC and ERA-OS), the main activity domain is identified based on the topic description of the calls for proposal in their respective working programmes. This means that projects funded under the same topic call are classified within the same category, although their activities may differ. This approach aims to focus on the main operational objectives outlined in the call for proposal of the work programme, rather than on the specific activity of the funded project.

The methodology used for the categorisation of the INFRAEOSC, ERA-OS projects and RDA WGs according to defined OS criteria is described in the Box 1 below.

Box 1. Methodology used to categorise RDA WGs and HE-funded projects based on their main domain of activity

LLM model and version: ChatGPT-5 min version (free version), accessed 2025-10-30

Queries:

- 1) Paste the description of the OS criteria into the chat
- 2) Ask *'Provide one sentence description of the main activity for each initiatives'*;
 - For INFRAEOSC and ERA-OS: by using 'topics description' of calls of proposal, based on the URL
 - For RDA WGs: use the case of statement or homepage URL
- 3) Ask *'based on the initiative descriptions, categorise them according to the identified OS categories'*.

The dataset gathering the categorisation of the HE-funded projects (INFRAEOSC and ERA-OS) and RDA WGs is available [here](#), with the project name and website, the URL used for the categorisation, the one-sentence description of the project and the corresponding domain of activity or criteria.

This categorisation and the relationships to RDA WGs can be explored further via a Kumu.io mapping of the same.

[Mapping Research Data Alliance Working Groups to HE-funded projects](#)

Prior to analysing the results of each activity domain addressed by RDA WGs and HE-funded projects, some important information should be noted. Only one category has been assigned to the RDA WGs and the HE-funded projects, according to their main activity or objective. It is possible that a WG or project pursues multiple objectives simultaneously, which may introduce a bias in the categorisation of activity domains. Verification with the stakeholders would confirm the confidence of the categorisation and the results obtained, with this mapping activity potentially serving as the basis for any future work in this area.

Horizon Europe - further detail and analysis

This section provides a deeper analysis of domains of activity of the RDA WGs and the current HE-funded projects, as well as their alignment based on their domain. Figure 27 provides an overview of the domains of activity of RDA WGs and HE-funded projects. HE-funded projects related to EOSC originate from the INFRAEOSC calls for proposals, and those related to OS come from the OS area of the ERA calls for proposals, here referred as ERA-OS.

	RDA WGs (based on case of statement or homepage)	INFRAEOSC (based on topic of the call)	ERA-OS (based on topic of the call)
Scalability	6	14	0
Federation	9	6	0
Policy evolution	15	6	11
FAIR compliance	37	5	1
Wide user base	2	1	5
Total	69	32	17

Figure 27. Distribution of activity domains across RDA WGs, and the HE funded projects from the INFRAEOSC and the OS-related ERA (ERA-OS) calls.

The activity domains of the RDA WGs cover all the five domains, with a clear predominance of FAIR compliance activities (37 out of 69, or 53%). Similarly to RDA WGs, the INFRAEOSC projects also cover all five activity domains, but mainly focus their activities on the scalability domain (14 out of 32, or 43%). As for the ERA-OS projects, their activity domains are more limited, with only three of the five domains covered, and they mainly focus on the policy evolution domain (11 out of 17, or 64%).

Scalability

The RDA WGs dealing with the scalability domain are mainly related to sustainability of repositories or catalogues with certification and assessment such as the [Community-based catalogue of requirements for trustworthy Technical Repository Service Providers \(TRSPs\)](#) WG, [RDA/WDS TRUST Principles Outreach and Adoption](#) WG, [CoreTrustSeal Maintenance](#) WG, and to a certain extent the [Array Database Assessment](#) WG. However, the [RDA-OfR Mapping the landscape of digital research tools](#) WG and its successor [MaLDReTH II](#) WG, for their part, focus on the scalability area through the interoperability aspect of the overall stage of the data lifecycle.

For their part, the INFRAEOSC projects dealing with the scalability domain are mainly referring to two aspects: the service deployment and the sustainability. Services deployment aspects are covered by

RDA TIGER “Research Data Alliance facilitation of Targeted International working Groups for EOSC-related Research solutions” is funded by HORIZON-INFRA-2022-EOSC-0, Project:101094406.

the funded [FAIRCORE4EOSC](#) project of the ‘Deploying EOSC-Core components for FAIR’ call for proposal, and the five funded projects: [AI4EOSC](#), [EuroScienceGateway](#), [FAIR-EASE](#), [RAISE](#) and [Scilake](#) of the ‘Innovative and customizable services for EOSC’ call, as well as the four funded projects: [LUMEN](#), [EOSC Data Commons](#), [DataGEMS](#) and [RAISE suite](#) of the ‘Innovative and customizable services for EOSC Exchange’ call for proposal. The sustainability aspect is tackled by the [RDA TIGER](#) project of the ‘Support for initiatives helping to generate global standards, specifications and recommendations for open sharing of FAIR research data, publications and software’ call for proposal, as well as the [EOSC EDEN](#) project of the ‘Long-term access and preservation infrastructure development for EOSC’ call. Sustainability aspects can also refer to integration within the market or industry, as mentioned in the activity description for the ‘[Innovative and customizable services for EOSC](#)’ call which aims to improve the Technology Readiness Level of the future funded projects.

Federation

The RDA WGs dealing with the federation domain focused on linking identification and service aspects. RDA WGs focusing on identification aspects include the [Persistent Identification of Instruments](#) WG which focuses on persistent identification of instruments and supports them in the implementation federation within a cohesive system; the [Data Type Registries WG](#) which works on a registry framework for describing dataset structures in a machine-readable way, enabling discovery, reuse and federation across communities, and the [National PID Strategies](#) WG which aims to harmonise PID policies and practices at national level. The federation of service includes the [Coordinating Earth, Space, and Environmental Science Data Preservation and Scholarly Publication Processes](#) WG which aims to enhance collaboration and coordination between repository and publisher workflows; the [Brokering Framework](#) WG which focuses on the federation of distributed data services, and the [Research Data Repository Interoperability](#) WG which aims to federate access of research data repositories. Finally, the [GORC International Model](#) WG and its successor the [GORC International Implementation](#) WG focus their activities on the federation of research data commons across institutions.

The federation domain of the INFRAEOSC projects covers mainly services aspects and especially domain specific services. Indeed, the [EOSC4cancer](#), the two funded-projects: [Blue-Cloud2026](#) and [AqualNFRA](#) of the ‘FAIR and open data sharing in support of healthy oceans, seas, coastal and inland waters’ call for proposal covers domain specific services as well as [OSCARS](#) project which focus on federation of services across multidisciplinary domains. The [FIDELIS](#) project focuses its federation activity on a specific service which is repository-centric. Only [ESOC United](#) project is tackling federation thought institutional aspects

Policy evolution

The policy and technical evolution domain represent the second main activity domain covered by RDA WGs. It covers a wide range of topics, from general aspects, such as the [Practical Policy](#) WG, to more specific frameworks, such as [RDA/CODATA Data Systems, Tools, and Services for Crisis Situations](#) WG, [Raising FAIRness in health data and health research performing organisations \(HRPOs\)](#) WG, [RDA COVID-19](#) WG, [Discipline-specific Guidance for Data Management Plans](#) WG and [Ethics in Agricultural Data](#) WG. Moreover, policies specific to the data lifecycle are also addressed, by [Repository Audit and Certification DSA–WDS Partnership](#) WG for digital repository, or software-specific policies like the [RDA & ReSA Policies in Research Organisations for Research Software](#) WG.

INFRAEOSC projects affiliated to the policy evolution domain focus on EOSC partnership deployment, such as the [EOSC Gravity](#) project of the ‘Supporting the EOSC Partnership in further consolidating the coordination and sustainability of the EOSC ecosystem’ call for proposal; and the [EOSC focus](#) project of the ‘Supporting the development and coordination of activities of the EOSC Partnership’ call. Although the federation domain within the INFRAEOSC project also refers to security aspects. The first focus on sensitive data, with the three projects: [TITAN](#), [EOSC Entrust](#) and [SIESTA](#), funded under the ‘Trusted environments for sensitive data management in EOSC’ call, and the second focus on securing intellectual propriety of Diamond model like the the [CRAFT-OA](#) project.

ERA-OS projects affiliated to the policy evolution domain focus on the impact of OS practices on the trustability via reproducibility and way to assess it, such as with the [Pathos](#), [OPUS](#), [TrustParency](#), [REINFORCING](#) projects as well as the three projects [TIER2](#), [OSIRIS](#) and [iRISe](#) of the ‘Increasing the reproducibility of scientific results’ and the [CoARA Boost](#) project of the ‘Support to reforms of research assessment in the European Research Area’ call. A specific effort is made on assessment of open access publication and impact on intellectual propriety with the [DIAMAS](#), [IP4OS](#) and [PALOMERA](#) projects.

FAIR compliance

The activities related to FAIR compliant domain among the RDA WGs is broad and addresses multiple facets of FAIRness. It ranges from domain-specific approaches to agnostic, as well as focusing on particular stages of the data lifecycle. For example, RDA WGs focusing on domain-specific FAIR aspects include [Agrisemantics](#) WG, [Computational Modelling of Health Data](#) WG, [Alignment of multilingual vocabularies in the Social Sciences and Humanities \(SSH\)](#) WG, [Small Uncrewed Aircraft and Autonomous Platforms Data](#) WG and [Wind Energy Community Standards](#) WG. Those working on domain-agnostic aspects include [I-ADOPT](#) WG, [Data Foundation and Terminology](#) WG and [Metadata Standards Catalog](#) WG. Finally, among the WGs addressing FAIR aspects according specific stages of

the data lifecycle, such as the (meta)data planning, description, analysis, storage and publication, we can mention the [Common maDMPs API](#) WG, [FAIR for Research Software](#) (FAIR4RS) WG, [FAIRsharing Registry: Connecting data policies, standards and databases](#) RDA WG, and RDA/WDS Publishing Data groups.

INFRAEOSC projects dealing with FAIR compliant domain also focus on domain specific discipline, like the climate adaptation like the [CLIMATE-ADAPT4EOSC](#) and [FAIR2Adapt](#) projects of the ‘FAIR and open data sharing in support of the mission adaptation to climate change’ call, as well as projects focusing on cross-disciplinary activities such as [FAIR-IMPACT](#) and [OSTrails](#), respectively funded ‘Planning, tracking, and assessing scientific knowledge production’ from the ‘Enabling discovery and interoperability of federated research objects across scientific communities’ and calls. Only one INFRAEOSC project, the [EVERSE](#) project, is focusing on domain agnostic discipline, especially on the software quality through the ‘Development of community-based approaches for ensuring and improving the quality of scientific software and code’ call.

Although the FAIR compliance domain does not represent a significant part of the domain of activity covered by INFRAEOSC projects, the adoption of FAIR principles may still be required, as is the case for the ‘Innovative and customizable services for EOSC Exchange’ call which specifies that the future funded projects must align with FAIR-by design approach¹⁰⁵.

Regarding ERA-OS funded-project, only the [WorldFAIR](#) project is dealing with the FAIR compliance domain. WorldFAIR was funded under the ‘Global cooperation on FAIR data policy and practice’ call and aims to support international cooperation to increase the FAIRness of research on digital objects through cross discipline-specific best practices.

Wide user base

The two RDA WGs focusing on a wider user base domain include [RDA/CODATA Summer Schools in Data Science and Cloud Computing in the Developing World](#) WG which aims to foster the capacity building of the user. The [Capacity Development for Agriculture Data](#) WG, is domain specific to agriculture, and aims to provide training on data management in this field.

The only INFRAEOSC project dealing with the wide user base domain is [Skills4EOSC](#). It aims to upskill a digitally prepared research and infrastructure workforce to effectively operate EOSC related OS services.

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<https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/opportunities/topic-details/HORIZON-INFRA-2024-EOSC-01-05?order=DESC&pageNumber=1&pageSize=50&sortBy=startDate&isExactMatch=true&status=31094501,31094502,31094503&frameworkProgramme=43108390&callIdentifier=HORIZON-INFRA-2024-EOSC-01>

ERA-OS projects under the wider user base domain reflect the ambition to strengthen trust and responsible framework surrounding OS practices with open, responsible and ethical research, for instance the three projects [VERITY](#), [POIESIS](#) and [IANUS](#) from the ‘Societal trust in science, research and innovation’ call, as well as [PATTERN](#) project from the ‘Developing and piloting training on the practice of open and responsible research and innovation’ call. [ALMASI](#) project from the ‘Global cooperation in not-for-profit open access publishing’ call focuses especially on the open access publication aspect by promoting global cooperation through gathering, sharing and implementing best practices to strengthen equitable and trusted publishing venues.

Annex 3: Background and Methodology for the Mapping of RDA TIGER-supported RDA WGs to the ESFRI Roadmap and ERICs

This annex contains further information regarding the methodology and analysis of Section 5: Mapping of RDA TIGER-supported RDA WGs to the ESFRI Roadmap and ERICs.

Background

The European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures (ESFRI) is composed of national delegates from EU Member States and Associated Countries. ESFRI’s mandate is to support a strategy-led and coherent development and implementation of Research Infrastructures in Europe¹⁰⁶. A key tool to this end is the ESFRI Roadmap for European Research Infrastructures (RIs) that analyses the European landscape of research infrastructures and provides directions for further development of RIs in Europe. The ESFRI Roadmap defines ESFRI Projects (RIs in preparation phase that receive support from ESFRI for their timely implementation) and ESFRI Landmarks (RI implemented under the ESFRI Roadmap that constitute major elements of the European Research Area (ERA))¹⁰⁷.

Most, but not all of the ESFRI Landmarks are part of European Research Infrastructure Consortia (ERICs)¹⁰⁸. An ERIC is “a specific legal form that facilitates the establishment and operation of

¹⁰⁶

https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/strategy/strategy-research-and-innovation/our-digital-future/european-research-infrastructures/esfri_en; <https://www.esfri.eu/>

¹⁰⁷ <http://www.esfri.eu/glossary>

¹⁰⁸ <https://roadmap2021.esfri.eu/projects-and-landmarks/view-the-table/>

Research Infrastructures with European interest”¹⁰⁹. As of June 2025, there are 32 recognised ERICs that function as hubs that provide RI, services and resources¹¹⁰.

Methodology

To map RDA WGs to the European RI landscape, we performed desk research covering ESFRI Roadmap 2021¹¹¹, ESFRI Landscape Analysis 2024¹¹², the websites of all 32 ERICs, and the websites of RDA TIGER-supported WGs on the RDA website. The first ESFRI Roadmap was published in 2006¹¹³; Roadmap 2021 is the latest iteration; the next Roadmap iteration is scheduled for 2026¹¹⁴. The ESFRI Landscape Analysis 2024 decoupled the landscape analysis from ESFRI roadmaps and proposed a stand-alone overview.

The aim of the desk research was to identify the advances and challenges ESFRI Roadmap 2021 and ESFRI Landscape Analysis 2024 recognised for the European RI landscape and to determine the scope and activity areas of both the current ERICs as well as all RDA TIGER-supported RDA WGs. As second step, RDA TIGER-supported RDA WGs were mapped manually to the challenges determined in ESFRI Roadmap 2021 and ESFRI Landscape Analysis 2024 as well as mapped to ERICs based on their technology focus in order to highlight the potential value and impact of RDA WGs to the European RI landscape. To map RDA TIGER-supported RDA WGs to ERICs we used the RDA taxonomy for the technology focus, which includes the following classes: policy-related, grant preparation, data (output) management planning, performing research, depositing research outputs, ingest and appraisal, archiving, long-term preservation, dissemination, search and discovery, access management and licenses, re-use, VREs, citation and provenance.

The ERIC websites were accessed and analysed over a period of several months in spring 2025, with a final review and revision of analysis completed in September 2025. The same timeframe applied for the consultation and analysis of the RDA TIGER-supported RDA WG pages on the RDA website. The decision to limit analysis to RDA TIGER-supported RDA WGs for the purposes of this mapping was mainly practical; however, since the 25 RDA TIGER-supported RDA WGs included in the analysis, constitute about half of the currently active RDA WGs in total, we consider that the report still

¹⁰⁹

https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/strategy/strategy-research-and-innovation/our-digital-future/european-research-infrastructures/eric_en

¹¹⁰

https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/strategy/strategy-research-and-innovation/our-digital-future/european-research-infrastructures/eric/eric-landscape_en

¹¹¹ <https://roadmap2021.esfri.eu/>

¹¹² <https://landscape2024.esfri.eu/landscape-analysis/>

¹¹³ <https://www.esfri.eu/roadmap-archive>

¹¹⁴ <https://www.esfri.eu/roadmap-2026>

provides a substantial overview of the overlapping activity focus and shared interest between the European RI landscape and the RDA community.

Table 19: RDA TIGER-supported RDA WGs relevant to ERICs in different domains (based on mapping)

RDA TIGER-supported RDA WGs relevant to ERICs in the Energy domain
RDA Global Open Research Commons (GORC) International Model WG
RDA GORC International Implementations WG
RDA TIGER-supported RDA WGs relevant to ERICs in the Environment domain
RDA Global Open Research Commons (GORC) International Model WG
RDA GORC International Implementations WG
RDA FAIR Data Maturity Model WG
RDA Data Granularity WG
RDA Mapping the Landscape of Digital Research Tools II WG
RDA/WDS TRUST Principles Outreach and Adoption WG
RDA National PID Strategies WG
RDA FAIR Mappings WG
RDA Community-based catalogue of requirements for trustworthy Technical Repository Service Providers WG
RDA I-ADOPT WG
RDA Ethics in Agricultural (Ag) Data WG
RDA Reproducibility Checklist WG
RDA Small Uncrewed and Autonomous Platforms Data WG
RDA/CODATA Data Systems, Tools, and Services for Crisis Situations WG
EOSC-Future/RDA Artificial Intelligence and Data Visitation WG
RDA TIGER-supported RDA WGs relevant to ERICs in the Health and Food domain
RDA Global Open Research Commons (GORC) International Model WG
RDA GORC International Implementations WG
RDA FAIR Data Maturity Model WG

RDA Data Granularity WG
RDA Mapping the Landscape of Digital Research Tools II WG
RDA/WDS TRUST Principles Outreach and Adoption WG
RDA National PID Strategies WG
RDA FAIR Mappings WG
RDA Community-based catalogue of requirements for trustworthy Technical Repository Service Providers WG
RDA Health Data Commons GORC Profile WG
RDA Multiomics Metadata Standards Integration (MOMSI) WG
RDA FAIRification of Genomic Annotations WG
RDA Computational Modeling of Health Data WG
RDA Building Immune Digital Twins WG
EOSC-Future/RDA Artificial Intelligence and Data Visitation WG
RDA/CODATA Data Systems, Tools, and Services for Crisis Situations WG
RDA TIGER-supported RDA WGs relevant to ERICs in the Physical Sciences and Engineering domain
RDA Global Open Research Commons (GORC) International Model WG
RDA GORC International Implementations WG
RDA FAIR Data Maturity Model WG
RDA Data Granularity WG
RDA Mapping the Landscape of Digital Research Tools II WG
RDA/WDS TRUST Principles Outreach and Adoption WG
RDA National PID Strategies WG
RDA FAIR Mappings WG
RDA Harmonised terminologies and schemas for FAIR data in materials science and related domains WG
RDA TIGER-supported RDA WGs relevant to ERICs in the Social and Cultural Innovation domain
RDA Global Open Research Commons (GORC) International Model WG
RDA GORC International Implementations WG

RDA FAIR Data Maturity Model WG
RDA Data Granularity WG
RDA Mapping the Landscape of Digital Research Tools II WG
RDA/WDS TRUST Principles Outreach and Adoption WG
RDA National PID Strategies WG
RDA FAIR Mappings WG
RDA Community-based catalogue of requirements for trustworthy Technical Repository Service Providers WG
RDA Alignment of multilingual vocabularies in the Social Sciences and Humanities WG
EOSC-Future/RDA Artificial Intelligence and Data Visitation WG
RDA Small Uncrewed and Autonomous Platforms Data WG
RDA Reproducibility Checklist WG

Annex 4: Mapping of RDA WG outputs to European National Strategies

This annex contains further information regarding the methodology and analysis of Section 5: Mapping of RDA WG outputs to European National Strategies

Methodology

Collating National Open Science Policies

[EOSC-A country pages](#)¹¹⁵ were consulted in May 2025 as the primary resource for identifying relevant national Open Science policy documents for each European member state country and understanding the Open Science policy landscape across Europe. Relevant documentation has been published by all 27 EU member states, including Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Croatia, Cyprus, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Latvia,

¹¹⁵ <https://eosc.eu/tripartite-collaboration/#countries>

Lithuania, Luxembourg, Malta, Netherlands, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, and Sweden.

Research Data Alliance country representatives were contacted to inform them about the mapping analysis and its objectives. These communications served two purposes: alerting representatives to the study, and verifying the location and availability of each country's national Open Science policy document. English-language versions were prioritised where available, and translation by Artificial Intelligence (AI) was used for documents only available in national languages. This approach ensured comprehensive coverage of European national Open Science policies while maintaining accuracy and accessibility of all documentation collected for analysis.

Further analysis

Analysis of National Open Science Policies

Analysis of policy documents from 27 European member states revealed considerable diversity in both policy types and Open Science implementation approaches. While many countries have adopted comprehensive national Open Science policies, others have published more targeted strategies focusing specifically on open access mandates, data management frameworks, or regulatory decrees.

Implementation timelines also vary significantly, ranging from short-term (2 to 4 year) strategies in Austria, France, and Greece to ambitious long-term visions extending to 2030 in countries like Ireland, the Netherlands, and Sweden. Some documents are notably older and potentially outdated. This variation reflects diverse national priorities, Open Science implementation readiness levels, and varying financial resources and political commitment across the European research landscape.

National Open Science policies can also be differentiated from national laws on Open Science, which can generally be considered as stronger commitments to Open Science, as they are legally binding.¹¹⁶ This analysis focuses on policies rather than laws, as policies tend to be more descriptive and detailed in their articulation of Open Science practices, making them more suitable for analysing RDA synergy on specific topics.

Regulatory stringency differs markedly across the national Open Science policy documents. Some countries like Slovenia and Lithuania have implemented strict mandatory frameworks with enforceable requirements and contractual penalties, while others such as Finland and Sweden have

¹¹⁶ Rochambeau, M., & Konach, T. (2022). Report on existing policies and guidelines. Zenodo. p.13, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10807012>

adopted aspirational guidance documents that serve as best practice frameworks rather than binding obligations. This creates a spectrum from hard policy mandates with compliance mechanisms to softer strategic visions that encourage voluntary adoption of Open Science principles.

The documents also vary considerably in their level of detail and granularity, ranging from high-level strategic frameworks that establish broad principles to comprehensive operational documents with specific implementation timelines, funding allocations, and detailed compliance requirements. Some policies provide extensive technical specifications and procedural guidance, while others focus on aspirational goals and general direction setting.

Several policies demonstrate alignment with European frameworks, such as the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) and Horizon Europe, though the depth of integration varies significantly across countries. Of particular interest is that several countries explicitly reference the Research Data Alliance in their policy documents, indicating the RDA's influence in shaping national Open Science strategies. These references suggest that countries recognise the value of community-endorsed standards and best practices, and highlight the RDA's role in bringing an international perspective that extends beyond European borders to incorporate global approaches within the European research ecosystem.

Mapping RDA Groups to National Open Science Policies

In July 2025, a [list of 193 RDA groups](#)¹¹⁷ was exported from the RDA website. This list included all RDA group types: Working Groups, Interest Groups, Communities of Practice, Historical Groups, and Coordination Groups. All group types were included because groups frequently connect and evolve, with one group often leading to the creation of new Working Groups.

Groups were also selected based on their current status to represent the complete RDA group lifecycle. The included statuses were: 'In Community Review', 'In TAB Review', 'In Council Review', 'In Group Revisions', 'Recognised and Endorsed' and 'Completed'. This approach captured groups at every stage of development, from newly forming groups still under review, to established active groups, as well as completed historical groups. Historical groups were included as their outputs may contain valuable insights relevant to European national Open Science policies.

¹¹⁷ <https://drive.google.com/file/d/186pInOXpWUErxYKcdmYwrzv1zrhbJpRU/view?usp=sharing>

Adaption of the FOSTER Open Science Taxonomy

To systematically map the 193 RDA groups to the diverse collection of European national Open Science strategies, this section of the study employed the [FOSTER Open Science taxonomy](#)¹¹⁸ as the analytical framework. The taxonomy was converted from a tree diagram into a [hierarchical list structure](#)¹¹⁹ and groups were mapped to each Open Science domain using [Claude.ai](#) Sonnet 4 (Pro) (AI prompt: ‘Map the RDA groups to each domain of the following Open Science Taxonomy list, consulting the Group Home page, Statement of Work, Plenaries and Outputs’).

Mapping RDA Groups to the Open Science Taxonomy

The methodology for mapping RDA groups to the Open Science Taxonomy employed an integrated multiple analytical approach that analysed and validated each group's connection to Open Science practices (Table 20). This process combined automated text analysis with domain expertise and real-time, human validation to ensure accurate mapping of RDA groups to multiple Open Science taxonomy domains. The methodology was designed to acknowledge the cross-cutting nature of many groups while maintaining systematic criteria for reproducible analysis.

Table 20. The [Claude.ai](#)-assisted multiple analytical approach to mapping RDA groups to the Open Science taxonomy.

AI-Assisted Methodology	
Textual Analysis	Semantic parsing of group titles, descriptions and available metadata from group Statements of Work ¹²⁰ extracted key terms (e.g. 'data management', 'FAIR', 'reproducibility', 'standards') and identified naming conventions and correlations between group types and focus areas.
Domain Expertise Application	Domain knowledge about RDA’s infrastructure-building mission and Open Science principles provided essential context for understanding how groups function within the broader ecosystem, including recognition that FAIR principles span multiple domains and that RDA emphasises cross-disciplinary collaboration and technical interoperability.

¹¹⁸ Pontika, N., Knoth, P., Cancellieri, M., & Pearce, S. (2015). Fostering open science to research using a taxonomy and an eLearning portal. *In Proceedings of the 15th International Conference on Knowledge Technologies and Data-driven Business* (pp. 1–8). i-KNOW '15: 15th International Conference on Knowledge Technologies and Data-Driven Business. ACM. <https://doi.org/10.1145/2809563.2809571>

¹¹⁹ https://drive.google.com/file/d/1jVPur_kZkQBRUvL9JSBGvvpOG-otAcJ/view?usp=drive_link

¹²⁰ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/working-groups/working-group-development/>

Web-based Verification	Targeted searches validated group activities, outputs, and real-world adoption where additional context was needed. Official RDA sources and peer-reviewed publications were prioritised to confirm actual deliverables beyond what group titles alone conveyed.
Multi-Categorical Classification	Groups we systematically assigned to multiple Open Science taxonomy domains where their activities warranted it, with distinctions between primary functions and secondary contributions. This approach recognised that infrastructure groups often enable multiple Open Science practices simultaneously.
Consistency and Documentation	Evidence-based explanations were provided for each group-domain mapping to ensure consistency across similar groups and enable reproducibility of classification decisions.

While the methodology minimised subjective interpretation and all AI outputs were checked and validated by the author, some subjectivity remains due to the interpretive nature of mapping diverse group activities to predefined Open Science domains. Additionally, the mapping analysis is necessarily limited to the taxonomy structure, meaning some nuances and details of group activities may be missed or oversimplified in the mapping process.

Among the 193 RDA groups analysed, 99 were mapped to the Open Science taxonomy. Due to the multi-categorical classification approach employed, some groups appear across multiple categories within the framework. The remaining groups that could not be mapped were discipline-specific groups focused on particular fields (including life sciences and health, earth and environmental sciences, agricultural sciences, social sciences and humanities, and physical sciences and engineering), and administrative or governance groups (such as coordination groups) that lacked direct connections to Open Science taxonomy domains.

Mapping European National Open Science Policies to the Open Science Taxonomy

The methodology for mapping 27 European national Open Science policy documents to the Open Science taxonomy employed a systematic document analysis approach that evaluated policy coverage across all taxonomy domains using [Claude.ai](#) (Table 21). This process involved reviewing policy content to determine coverage levels while distinguishing between explicit mandates and implied requirements.

Table 21. *Claude.ai-assisted systematic approach to mapping European national Open Science policies to the Open Science taxonomy.*

AI-Assisted Methodology	
Document Comprehension	Systematic reading and analysis of European national Open Science policy documents to understand overall structure, strategic goals, and specific mandates, identifying key themes and policy priorities across different Open Science domains.
Content Identification	Extraction of specific statements, requirements, and commitments related to Open Science practices, cataloguing explicit mentions of taxonomy domains alongside identification of relevant policy mechanisms and implementation frameworks.
Taxonomic Comparison	Systematic comparison of identified policy elements against the Open Science taxonomy, evaluating coverage levels for each taxonomy domain and sub-domain.
Evidence Documentation	Recording direct quotations from policy documents as evidence for each mapping decision, distinguishing between explicit mentions and implied coverage.

Some mapping decisions relied on implied connections rather than direct statements. For example, when a document mandated FAIR data principles, the analysis inferred support for metadata standards and interoperability even if those specific terms were not explicitly mentioned. The methodology attempted to distinguish clearly between explicit mentions and implied coverage in all analyses.

The research conducted for section 6 - Mapping of RDA WG outputs to European National Strategies utilised [Claude.ai](#) Sonnet 4 (Pro version) to assist with mapping RDA groups to national Open Science policies, as well as for editorial support and language refinement throughout the preparation process.

AI Assistance Disclaimer

Rationale for AI Use

AI-assisted analysis was employed for this study because manually analysing and mapping the extensive volume of policy documents, RDA group descriptions, and related textual sources would have been infeasible within reasonable time constraints and potentially more inconsistent due to

human fatigue and variable interpretation across such large datasets. AI tools offer advantages in systematically processing large volumes of text, identifying patterns across multiple documents simultaneously, and maintaining consistent analytical frameworks.

Collaborative Approach

The combination of AI's computational capabilities with human oversight creates a mutual verification process; AI can rapidly identify connections and patterns that might be missed in manual review, while human validation ensures contextual accuracy and guards against AI-generated errors or misinterpretations. This collaborative approach leverages the complementary strengths of both computational analysis and human validation. The AI-generated analyses presented have been reviewed for accuracy.

Limitations and Caveats

While AI technology provides valuable analytical capabilities, readers should be aware that AI-generated content may contain inaccuracies, omissions, or interpretive errors. The mapping relationships identified through this AI-assisted analysis should be considered preliminary findings that may not capture the complete scope or nuanced connections between RDA groups and European national Open Science policies. Given the dynamic nature of RDA group activities and the continuous evolution of national Open Science policies, some information may require updates or verification through primary sources.

Recommendations for Users

Users are encouraged to consult original policy documents and engage directly with relevant RDA groups to confirm specific relationships and assess current implementation status.

For questions, clarifications, or additional information regarding this analysis, please contact RDA Secretariat (secretariat@rda-foundation.org).

Annex 5: Community Engagement activities in support of the landscape analysis

Background & Methodology

RDA TIGER Cross-Fertilisation Webinars

The RDA TIGER project held two Cross-Fertilisation Webinar Series during the project's lifetime: the first of this two-part series consisted of three webinars held in November and December 2024; two more were held in November and December 2025. These were organised in order to provide a platform for knowledge exchange and interdisciplinary/inter-domain collaboration among RDA TIGER-supported Working Groups. Each webinar was thematically focused, allowing WGs to share their work with peers and identify shared challenges and opportunities for collaboration. The brief given to presenters and contributors was not only to focus on introducing their WGs' activities to webinar attendees, but to engage with the theme of each webinar with the aim of finding overlaps and commonalities in WG efforts.

The topics were selected following discussion among the WGs' RDA TIGER facilitators on shared focus areas of each WG, and then linked to concerns described directly and indirectly in the SRIA. These were then presented at the outset of each webinar by the RDA TIGER chair and moderator to 'set the scene', encouraging questions and discussions to be anchored to these concerns.

The series helped identify gaps and challenges, many of which align closely with the Implementation Challenges that are outlined in the EOSC SRIA (and analysed in detail in section 3 above), and facilitated alignment within the RDA WGs towards addressing these challenges. For example, the webinar on Semantic Interoperability initiated a discussion between the co-chairs of the FAIR Mappings and FAIRification of Genomic Annotations WGs which has fed into their respective outputs; the FAIRification of Genomic Annotations WG will use the FAIR Mappings WG work on how to describe mappings into its recommendations for a minimal FAIR metadata schema for genomic annotations.

Similar conversations were instigated in the FAIR/CARE/TRUST Principles adoption webinar in December 2024 between the RDA/WDS TRUST Principles Outreach and Adoption WG and the Community-based catalogue of requirements for trustworthy Technical Repository Service Providers Working Group. These conversations formed the basis of the Repositories, trustworthiness and certification webinar in December 2025 and fed into efforts to align the WGs' outputs, which were in the process of development at the time of the latter webinar, with other European initiatives, specifically the EOSC EDEN and FIDELIS projects.

‘Community insights on use, adoption and impact of RDA Outputs’ workshop

At the RDA Virtual Plenary 24 in April 2025, the RDA TIGER project held a plenary session (i.e., one not competing with other sessions for attendees) to gather inputs from the RDA community on how RDA Group outputs are used and the factors affecting their uptake. The session, titled ‘Community insights on use, adoption and impact of RDA Outputs’¹²¹, was also used to seek feedback from the community via Mentimeter on the early direction of this report, getting a sense of how RDA Recommendations and Supporting Outputs can be put to use to address concerns across institutional, disciplinary and regional boundaries.

A significant share of those who attended indicated that they used RDA Recommendations and Supporting Outputs as part of their individual roles, or applied them at an organisational or institutional level (see Figure 28 below).

Figure 28. Responses at RDA Virtual Plenary 24 workshop

Furthermore, attendees gave an indication of how they used Recommendations and Supporting Outputs; as shown in Figure 29 below, the most significant share of responses indicated that they were used “[a]s part of active research data and/or software curation or management” with the remainder split relatively evenly the set responses provided.

¹²¹ A recording of the session is available on Youtube <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=BkMiGDscII0> ; a link to the slidedeck used can be found on the RDA VP24 programme page: <https://www.rd-alliance.org/plenaries/p24/programme-24/>

Figure 29. Further responses at RDA Virtual Plenary 24 workshop

These questions served as precursors to the discussion where attendees were asked a series of open-ended questions and invited to respond via a free text or by un-muting their microphones. Across the topics discussed in this portion of the session (many of which were relevant for RDA operations in general and will be communicated to the relevant bodies; see section 5.1 in D6.5 ‘Final Quality Evaluation Report on the RDA TIGER WG Services’¹²² for further information on this) there were two recurring concerns: the need for more and richer use cases describing how RDA Outputs are implemented, and how to use these shared instances of adoption and implementation of RDA Outputs to build connections. Taken separately, these concerns present opportunities for RDA itself to develop its processes around describing cases of adoption and the benefits of doing so.

Mapping of RDA outputs to European National Strategies: Outcomes from the RDA in Europe Summit

Leveraging the opportunity of the RDA in Europe Summit, the final RDA TIGER meeting, 69 individuals from 15 European countries were consulted. The 11 policy areas most frequently identified across the European policies in section 6 Mapping of RDA outputs to European National Strategies’ were grouped together thematically and discussed in five parallel roundtable sessions at the event.

The five roundtables addressed the following topics:

- Ethics & Legal Issues;

¹²² O’Connor, R., GRAU, N., Saldner, S., Minichiello, F., Lehtsalu, L., & Delipalta, A. (2025). RDA TIGER D6.5: Final quality evaluation report on the RDA TIGER WG services. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17877446>

- Research Data Management, Data Sharing, Data Standards;
- Impact assessment (Societal, economic, academic), Community engagement;
- Transparent Methodology (software), Verification methods;
- Open Access policies, Repository Systems.

Rapporteurs from RDA TIGER were assigned to each table to ensure the discussions stayed on the designated topic and to summarise any key points that were raised. Similar to the ‘Community insights on use, adoption and impact of RDA Outputs’ workshop described above, some of the issues and potential remedies discussed concerned internal RDA processes (e.g., suggestions of forming RDA IGs or WGs on specific topics, diversifying the RDA community to bring in those with expertise in legal, intellectual property and ethics issues).

In addition, there were discussions touching on how the wider European research community could benefit from the work carried out within the RDA, using the policy environment described in this report as a basis. These suggestions and outcomes, summarised below, could potentially feed into evolving efforts to develop EOSC.

Annex 6: Survey results and use cases: Leveraging the RDA in Horizon Europe projects

A survey was launched in early 2025 addressed to INFRA-EOSC projects to gauge the current engagement level of projects with the RDA platform and community. In addition to the survey, projects were invited to present at the [RDA in Europe Summit](#) in November 2025 use cases of leveraging the RDA in their work. Out of those contacted, 6 projects responded. The response rate was not significant, so a full analysis is not possible. Indicatively, out of the respondents, 6 indicated ‘yet to be decided’ to the question ‘does your project make use of existing RDA outputs’, 2 indicated that they plan to make use of RDA outputs in the future, with 3 undecided. One project noted that they plan to adopt the SKG-IF, one plans to align with the TRE WG. 2 responded ‘yes’ to the question ‘do you contribute to any current RDA Groups.

An exception to the lack of engagement with the survey was the [FAIR IMPACT](#) project, who provided an extensive list of activities through the RDA with presentations in Plenaries in WG meetings, special webinars, as well as the organisation of co-located events aiming to gather global perspectives on interoperability. The full overview of touchpoints between FAIR-IMPACT and RDA is below in a report provided by the project coordinator.

Ingrid Dillo

29-01-2025

RDA Europe is a FAIR-IMPACT beneficiary.

Interactions according to the FAIR-IMPACT Work Packages

WP1

- Partnered with RDA TIGER and other relevant EOSC projects in terms of exploring sustainability for project outputs in the context of the EOSC.

WP2

- Presented during the RDA 10th anniversary event “Regional Support to Certification of Data Repositories: A Workshop”
<https://www.rd-alliance.org/regional-support-certification-data-repositories>

WP3

RDA TIGER “Research Data Alliance facilitation of Targeted International working Groups for EOSC-related Research solutions” is funded by HORIZON-INFRA-2022-EOSC-0, Project:101094406.

- Presentation delivered at RDA 20th Plenary Progressing Machine Actionable Data Management Plans in DMP Roadmap 20 March, 2023. Mejias, & Nordling. (2023, March 20). PID work in the FAIR-IMPACT project. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8069888>
- Invited presenters from the RDA Complex Data Citation WG: Deb Agarwal and Shelley Stall & Andreas Rauber from RDA Data Citation WG, online workshop titled “PID best practices for complex data citation, semantic artefacts and related services” (May 25th, 2023).
- RDA National PID Strategies WG recommendations titled “National PID Strategies Guide and Checklist” (from 2023) used for an infographic titled “Practical PID Guide for National Initiatives”, still to be published.

WP4

- WP4 is interacting with multiple RDA WGs.
- Refined recommendations for FAIR mappings and launched, in partnership with FAIRCORE4EOSC, the new RDA FAIR mapping Working Group contributing to the project’s objective “A framework for metadata crosswalks and mappings between semantic artefacts”.
- Actively participates in the RDA Vocabulary and Semantic Services IG and the RDA software source code IG, by embracing and continuing the work on MOD (<https://github.com/FAIR-IMPACT/MOD>) started in RDA and now continued and adopted within FAIR-IMPACT.
- Agri-food community involved in FAIR-IMPACT has adopted the Recommendations from the RDA Agrisemantics WG (part of the RDA IGAD), especially with respect to developing and consolidating AgroPortal as a reference semantic artefact catalogue for agri-food.
- Organised the Research Software workshop co-located with RDA P20 - <https://faircore4eosc.eu/events/research-software-workshop-guidelines-and-metrics-metadata-curation-co-located-rdap20>.
- A proposal for a “Bird-of-a-Feather” session during the RDA P21 was submitted in collaboration with FAIRCORE4EOSC and the EOSC Semantic Interoperability Task Force.
- Dissemination of D4.4 Research Software MetaData guidelines, coordinated community review and presentation at RDA P21.
- RDA Birds of a Feather session aimed at proposing the creation of a dedicated RDA mapping WG which is currently being concretised with the support of the RDA Tiger program and in close collaboration with FAIRCORE4EOSC.
- In the context of T4.3 Standard metadata for research software consortium members participate in the RDA software source code IG.

WP5

RDA TIGER “Research Data Alliance facilitation of Targeted International working Groups for EOSC-related Research solutions” is funded by HORIZON-INFRA-2022-EOSC-0, Project:101094406.

Used the following RDA outputs:

- CoreTrustSeal;
- RDA FAIR Data Maturity Model (FAIR Indicators - F-UJI, FAIR-Aware);
- RDA Data Repository Attributes Working Group;
- RDA Metadata Standards Catalog WG (F-UJI based on this output).

Contributes to the following groups:

- o RDA Data Repository Attributes Working Group;
 - o The Vocabulary and Semantic Services Interest Group (VSSIG);
 - o FAIR for Research Software (FAIR4RS) WG;
 - o Community-based catalogue of requirements for trustworthy Technical Repository Service Providers Working Group (TRSPs WG);
 - o RDA/WDS TRUST Principles Outreach and Adoption Working Group
 - o FAIR for Machine Learning (FAIR4ML) IG.
- A workshop on research software metrics co-located with the RDA P20 Plenary event provided considerable valuable participation, interaction, and input:<https://www.rd-alliance.org/plenaries/rda-20th-plenary-meeting-göthenburg-hybrid>.
 - Engaged with RDA Data Repository Attributes Working Group to monitor and engage with relevant developments for repository requirements and exposing information.
 - WP5: Priddy, M., Verburg, M., Dillo, I., Brinkman, L., Reijnhoudt, L., Ulrich, R., Neidiger, C., Huber, R., L'Hours, H., Davidson, J., & Mejias, G. (2023). Transparency of Trust: guidelines for the discovery of trustworthiness status for digital repositories. International Data Week 2023 (IDW2023), Salzburg, Austria.
 - WP5 (T5.2 FAIR metrics for research software) presented at an RDA webinar.

WP6

- Organised [a workshop](#) as a RDA P23 co-located event in San José, Costa Rica. The workshop explored how research infrastructures, projects, and initiatives are approaching interoperability challenges in research commons.
- A shared presentation with FAIRCORE4EOSC and the RDA Brokering Framework Working Group took place at the RDA P20 Plenary event in March 2023.
- For the Winter School 2025 co-located interoperability workshop our RDA partners played a significant role in planning, execution and follow-up.
<https://fair-impact.eu/events/fair-impact-events/fair-impact-announces-co-located-final-interoperability-workshop-eosc>.

